

Trajectory-based reasoning model: PathThinker v0

A Theoretical Framework

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<https://github.com/weberBen/paththinker-v0>

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Abstract

We introduce PathThinker v0, a conceptual framework for neural networks that explicitly models information flow through trajectory-based reasoning.

In this framework, trajectories are treated as first-class computational entities instead of natural language that exert active influence on the behavior of the network. This paradigm is designed to support several key properties: rapid adaptation from limited data, decentralized computation without reliance on global update mechanisms, and self-organizing learning processes in which the network models data actively rather than processing it passively.

Although this work does not include an implementation yet, it proposes a theoretical foundation intended to guide and inspire our future development and practical instantiations of the PathThinker architecture.

1 Introduction

Current approaches in neural networks predominantly rely on passive data modeling, wherein the model adapts its predictions based on error signals computed against target values. The absence of strong inductive biases in such architectures is typically compensated by access to large-scale training datasets.

Some recent approaches attempt to move toward active data modeling, as exemplified by predictive coding frameworks [1] [2], which internally anticipate the expected state of subsequent layers before error correction. These architectures hint at the potential benefits of more proactive mechanisms for internal representation and learning.

Building on the initial conceptual roadmap of PathThinker [3], we now extend the discussion toward a potential implementation framework. The central objective is to rely heavily on internal self-consistency and hypothesis generation about what should exist, thereby aiming to drastically reduce the amount of external data required for effective training. In this paradigm, external target signals are not the primary driver of learning but are instead used only for fine-tuning. The model's primary goal is to produce internally coherent representations, even if these structures do not strictly correspond to real-world validity, as long as they remain within the realm of possibility.

Core principles

We reiterate below the key design goals that define the PathThinker framework:

- Rapid adaptability

- Decentralized computation
- Self-organizing learning processes
- Compatibility with diverse neuron typologies
- Self-inductive reasoning mechanisms
- Active rather than passive data modeling
- Support for continuous learning

The ultimate objective of PathThinker is to achieve compatibility with decentralized, continuous architectures such as spiking neural networks (SNNs). Although the current formulation is grounded in conventional artificial neural network (ANN) structures, the architecture is explicitly designed to be transferable and specialized for lower-level, biologically inspired implementations in future iterations.

2 Motivation

A core motivation of this architecture is to move beyond passive data representations and toward *computational trajectories* : internal structures that encode not just information, but executable algorithms the model can apply. Unlike embeddings or statistical associations, these trajectories should carry operational meaning, allowing the model to reason, transform, and generalize through the active manipulation of structured internal processes.

The central hypothesis of our work is as follows :

Can a model reproduce such abilities without relying on natural language, thus demonstrating true internal understanding ?

We argue that such capabilities are necessary for solving tasks where natural language is insufficient, ambiguous, or nonexistent. In these cases, the model must be capable of inventing its own internal rules, abstractions, and even languages to reason effectively. This implies that for certain classes of problems, relying solely on linguistic structures may not be sufficient, and starting from scratch, or inventing entirely new formalisms may be required.

To illustrate this, consider the task of handling objects viewed from different perspectives. The model should learn to group various views as belonging to the same object, generalize to the idea that most objects have multiple sides, and ultimately construct a rotation trajectory : a horizontal trajectory that, when applied to one face of an object, generates the next face by simulating the object’s rotation.

Beyond geometric intuition, the model should also be able to ask abstract questions such as: What is the equivalent of a Euclidean rotation in a topological space ? It should identify what a rotation is, what it should achieve, and search for objects or transformations in the topological domain that exhibit similar functional properties. It should then generate examples, test for generalization, and seek counterexamples to define the limits of this analogy, essentially constructing, testing, and refining new conceptual mappings.

One could argue that modern LLMs also provide mechanisms to “execute” transformations, such as through the embedding of the word ”rotate”, which may guide the model to generate a rotated version of an object. However, the key question remains.

We do not claim that language-based intelligence is invalid, nor that pretrained foundation models are inherently limited. Indeed, transfer learning will likely remain effective for many real-world

tasks. However, we posit that for certain radically novel problems, especially those lacking linguistic grounding models will require internal reasoning capabilities that transcend natural language representations.

Whether such problems will emerge in practice, and whether language-based systems can adapt sufficiently when they do, remains an open question. Our architecture aims to explore that frontier and explain the similarity with existing methods because our goal is to create a proto-language, context-agnostic, that will carry the reasoning. With such framework our goal is to answer if it's only a reformulation of existing work, a valid intuition, or infeasible.

Language emerges from environmental constraints and the need for coordination between individual agents. With natural language, we bypass these constraints by using a pre-structured and human-designed form, already shaped by environmental pressures. But a key question remains : Why hasn't language-like behavior naturally emerged in purely visual or robotic systems, even after extended exposure to complex environments ? Maybe because we constraint too much the models on specif task, not letting it expand to produce structure language like form. A non existent constraint with LLM because the task it to understand the underlying digested structural form carry by natural language.

Everything carries a form of language, a medium that transports information and entropy. Some tasks do not require a sophisticated representational setup, while others benefit from strong inductive biases to make learning feasible. Our initial hypothesis is that:

Forms are the structure of life.

Just as in chemistry, where each molecule has properties defined by its structure and reacts with others to form new compounds, we envision language similarly : each word is a "living" agent with intrinsic, dynamic properties, never static, which interact with others when combined on a substrate. And one possible solution for such a language could be literally shaped, like atomic orbitals where the spatial configuration that electrons occupy through their wave functions encodes computational information.

From a more technical perspective, the model should act as the substrate that enables these reactions, but the outcome depends heavily on the properties of each individual element. The closest existing architecture to this idea is the Capsule Network, where each "neuron" has an intrinsic role and shares its state with others, which in turn decide, through agreement, whether to combine; Despite its limits [4, 5, 6].

Embeddings, too, carry intrinsic information and interact through the model. However, in current architectures, the rules of combination are embedded directly in the model itself, making the embeddings relatively static and limiting their modularity.

3 Discussion

The above section is a work in progress as of 2026-02-10 (first time discussed here: 2025-12-31). For now, the section is an exposition of the main idea that lacks sufficient mathematical formulation and term formalization. It will be added progressively. However, this thesis reformulation seems more feasible than previous drafts.

This section brings together different ideas and explores their implications before considering practical implementation. Although the approach may seem ambitious, it does not claim to propose a unified theory of everything. The objective is to establish a coherent vision and evaluate a

priori the compatibility with existing theoretical problems, thus allowing for early reorientation if necessary.

Some identified problems fundamentally modify the way the model's grounds are approached. The approach therefore consists of first exploring all conceptual avenues, then progressively refining them to arrive at a limited number of testable propositions. This preliminary stage could require several dozen pages before leading to concrete experimental protocols.

3.1 Thesis reformulation

The work proposed in this paper can in fact be unified and reformulated more concretely through the lens of Homotopy Type Theory (HoTT) [7]. Notably through the prism of hypergraph transformations which, subject to a few extensions, describes HoTT. This is particularly the case for Wolfram transformations [8] [9] [10] not for their attributed physical properties but for their ability to represent a computable and falsifiable mathematical system (in fact an $(\infty, 1) - \text{topos}$). The falsifiability (the inconsistency) of a topos remains an arduous task whether in HoTT or in Category Theory (CT) but remains feasible with continuous exploration of the space in search of inconsistencies (e.g. two paths that should meet but do not). And at this stage, it is not clear that it is possible to rigorously satisfy the conditions of a real HoTT. Thus, depending on advances, it is possible that the proposal stops at CT. But the inspiration from HoTT remains a sufficiently fertile source to be able to produce interesting results even if partial.

The transformations in question can be understood in the following way [9]:

We might have a collection of relations like

$$\{\{1, 2\}, \{2, 3\}, \{3, 4\}, \{2, 4\}\}$$

that can be represented by a graph (see figure 1)

Figure 1: Example of an hypergraph

All we're specifying here are the relations between elements (like $\{2,3\}$). The order in which we state the relations doesn't matter (although the order within each relation does matter), [...] and it also doesn't matter what the elements are called.

[...] We [can] just apply a simple rule to them, over and over again. Here's an example of a possible rule:

$$\{\{x, y\}, \{x, z\}\} \rightarrow \{\{x, z\}, \{x, w\}, \{y, w\}, \{z, w\}\}$$

What this rule says is to pick up two relations, from anywhere in the collection, and see if the elements in them match the pattern $\{\{x,y\},\{x,z\}\}$. [...] If there's a match, then replace these two relations with the four relations on the right. The w that appears there is a new element that's being created, and the only requirement is that it's distinct from all other elements.

We can represent the rule as a transformation of graphs (see figure 2)

Figure 2: Example of an hypergraph rewrite

Now let's apply the rule once to [initial graph], [... and] the result is:

$\{\{1, 2\}, \{3, 4\}, \{2, 4\}, \{2, 5\}, \{3, 5\}, \{4, 5\}\}$

We can represent this result as a graph [...] (see figure 3):

Figure 3: Example of an hypergraph rewritten

The three most interesting properties are:

- (1) the representation of a topological space, envisaged here as continuous, from discrete links.
- (2) the purely relational representation of constraints (i.e. simple graphs whose vertices and edges have no intrinsic properties). In other words, the simplicity and universality of the representation of transformations (without symbols and without values); which moreover corresponds to what CT represents: defining a category by its relations.
- (3) the existence of input "data", transformations, rules in the same format: hypergraphs. This can correspond to any homogeneous system such as transformers on text, with the notable difference that hidden layers here act in the same space as the inputs.

This furthermore allows providing an easily manipulable language to define the properties embodied by a neural network (NN). The conversion of NNs into symbolic representation exploitable by a solver [11] [12] to verify in critical environments that certain properties (expressed in logic) are respected is a major field of interest. But they face a major problem on large neural networks which is the combinatorial explosion of paths to verify, although mitigations exist [13]. And often

these properties to verify are manually selected rather than automatically explored, although alternatives exist such as Gated Continuous Logic Networks [14], or more distant but semantically close in the task to be accomplished, Neural Architecture Search (NAS).

The translation of NNs into symbolic form is obviously critical since it determines the quality of verification. The general idea of solvers is to clarify the contribution of each neuron, so that it is activated or deactivated but not in an intermediate state.

In less critical and less restricted environments, one can ask from a NN what are its intrinsic properties. In other words, what is the minimum information that I must possess about this NN to reconstruct it from scratch, or at least minimize its adjustments once placed in a similar environment (i.e. once exposed to the same types of data). This is generally formulated as which d -dimensional vector (either used as start vector or as model weights) minimizes the resources (time and data) necessary for finetuning the target model. There are numerous meta learning methods to do this [15] [16] [17] [18] [19].

Nevertheless, each time the meta model is (necessarily) preserved between different tasks, because the produced vector is specific to the meta model. One can then ask if there isn't a way to learn meta-model agnostic information. In other words, once the meta model is learned, to be able to find, at least approximate, the entire chain of networks without having to resort to data, except for few-shot learning. This question is actually the question of knowing how a network can form itself without any external information simply from a target function. This can be approached from the task that biological neurons perform during formation phases and where structures appear with a low cost signal through the stimuli available at that moment which does not justify the complexity created.

In other words, we often try to compress the network itself, but rarely to compress the cost function so that it does not use data but another learned property that represents what the NN does; at least what allows it to be created and which with some additional constraints could be what the NN actually performs. Indeed, our current cost functions are the reflection of the absence of known or implementable properties on what we wish to accomplish. And when we identify some of these properties we can change the structure of networks (MLP/CNN/GNN/transformer) to induce these constraints, but which should also be able to be expressed in the cost function since it then infuses the entire network.

This raises the question of extracting this property from a NN. The verification of this symbolic/logical property can then be done by including it in the cost function as a binary function (property respected or not) [13], or combined with a potentiality function (Reward Annealing/Entropy-based switching) to balance formal verification (Sparse rewards) and guidance (Shaped reward) in learning.

As for the formal property to verify, if we consider a diffusion model or any model starting from noise, as a function in a stochastic calculus whose conditioning represents the bias introduced in randomness, we can then draw a graph of interactions. But, more simply, we can identify the decision boundaries of the model that uniquely determine it, even by distillation or finetuning [20]. Thus, with for example a dozen data points, we can identify a model. Of course, storing data in the properties would lose the interest of this property, as it becomes too specific. We can then extend this idea by representing the link between data classes (classes that we automatically cluster [21] on the fly or continuously). Then, we find ourselves with a graph whose only property is the links between categories, and a way to evaluate the relevance of this property by finetuning a new model with a few examples. The model starting from noise, we can in principle do its pre-training without data, only with the properties. On the other hand, this model in charge of finding the good representation from a NN, does not learn a particular representation but indeed to efficiently explore the possible properties which are based only on the categories induced by the model itself and the links between them (i.e. how from one category I can go to another, with what bias, what conditioning, and from this conditioning, or this starting noise how I can reach the others).

Obviously, the larger the model, the more complex the task. But this is where property (1) comes in.

Our objective here is not verifiable verification, but verifiable reasoning. In other words, we seek to infuse into a model formal reasoning capabilities via HoTT or CT, without otherwise constraining the system to follow it. We want to achieve a relaxation of the formally correct to reduce it during exploration phases, and to push it to the maximum during logical phases. The idea is that these logical phases requiring strict verification such as doing mathematics, already have their own formal languages, and therefore it is possible to assign to each symbol an equivalence in hypergraph and continue all the mathematical reasoning by bypassing the NNs and doing it in a verifiable and computable language that follows HoTT or CT. For example, one can imagine that an embedding linked to a mathematical symbol is a direct hypergraph correspondence.

And in other situations what we want to do is simply estimate the formality of the reasoning and the feasibility of the reasoning done. In other words, allow a fluid intuition/logic system as we will describe later.

If we consider that the data is hypergraph, and that the rewriting rules are also hypergraphs (more exactly the composition of two hypergraphs), then what NNs do are in reality only discrete operations on discrete structures that we can then train thus. In particular, the execution of an MLP on data then amounts to having:

- a set of allowed transformations (the axioms)
- a space that describes the order and link of these transformations
- a guidance mechanism to explore the most relevant path

Thus, we can envision reformulating the attention mechanism as the Keys allowing to identify the parts to transform for a particular rule, and the Values as being the transformation that we apply to the identified parts. A continuous approach to the hypergraph transformation rule. This necessarily raises the question of a threshold to define on the Keys to be taken into account, which can be an unstable process.

On the other hand, standard modelings do not allow representing expansion rules (i.e. node creation). They can represent inflection rules (i.e. node deletion) by shifting the value of a token towards the value of another present category (since the hypergraph merges nodes of the same type). We can of course think of a system of adding intermediate tokens but this risks destabilizing training. This is why we keep tokens with values in high dimension: to compress in the same token different operations (such as the creation of a node); which requires being able to represent many cases in a token therefore having expressive tokens therefore in high dimension. In principle, we should not need values, nor tokens. Nevertheless in the space of hypergraphs, a graph can grow arbitrarily large, which at some point will represent a performance problem to define transformation rules (become very long), identify patterns, and replace them. Thus, the dimension of tokens allows us to represent in a fixed-size space the evolution of the initial graph.

In other words, the relational links between the categories of a transformation rule after $t=T$ transformations can be identical to the relational links of a transformation at step $t=0$ but to represent the reality of the transformation at $t=T$ in the universe of hypergraphs, it would be necessary to unwrap all the categories that contributed to the values of those at $t=T$. For example, in $\{\{1, 2\} \rightarrow \dots\}$ at step $t=T$, the relation $\{1,2\}$ no longer defines the same thing at all as at $t=0$. And at $t=T$ $\{1, 2\}$ could be equivalent to $\{\{1, 2\}, \{4, 3\}, \{4, 2\}\}$. Here, we have a hybrid where the values of categories have importance (unlike CT or HoTT) but that we can if needed unwrap symbolically to correspond to CT or HoTT.

3.2 Input dependencies

What we want to avoid most in this architecture is dependence on data values. In other words, we want to learn relations, not values. For example in diffusion models or flow matching or almost all models, as input we take the inputs and the NN weights are specifically linked to this data, and indirectly to their relations. We want to reverse the process here, make the data (the value of tokens) a second-class citizen to allow lightening the learning of transformations and transposability. We can even see the mechanism that reconstructs a model from scratch from the property as the functor which at a homomorphism is identical to the target model.

If we represent the (continuous) selection process of rules to apply as simply a NN that takes as input the index (not the value) of categories and outputs the index of those to use, then the training mechanism on properties for this NN in particular can be seen as the transformation rules that no matter the value of categories we place, the NN remains the same, and the only thing we must adjust is which category is associated with which index (which can also be done by gradient). Figure 4 below illustrates this functioning but does not represent the actual process used, notably because we want to be able to add or remove categories simply. On the other hand, there will necessarily be an internal mapping of NNs with data values during conditioning, but we want it to remain a simple influence on the path we take.

Figure 4: Illustration of a remapping

To circumvent this dependence on values, we can implement neighbor reconstruction. The idea is to allow defining continuously the model from discrete links as we can do Laplace transformations on a space whose topology is defined on a graph, or neural ODEs on graphs. In other words, we want to define a common continuous space where each point is a transformation as for HoTT (adding the continuity constraint which even if false in places allows defining valid predictions). From the point of view of gradient or backpropagation, the discrete model will appear as a single model. For example, Mixture Of Experts (MoE) can be seen as a discretization of this mechanism.

Each expert has an embedding that represents its position in a common continuous space, at each iteration we choose a direction that we approximate with the points closest to this direction. In detail, as the experts can be reused between each iteration, the positions of transformations are reused, and it is rather the routing mechanism that learns a transformation of the common space. And in reality, generally the routing of experts does not call upon embeddings but directly a softmax on the index of experts.

Nevertheless, if we really wanted to use this common continuous space, it would suffice to replace the routing by a gradient and the embeddings by gradients. The idea is to form a graph where each node represents a transformation, and between these nodes each edge has a relative (or absolute) learned position and a learned gradient around this point. This may seem counterintuitive but it is actually more natural to give each edge a position because in graph transformations each "transition" is a transformation. In this situation, the nodes that we define have no real existence in the theory of hypergraph transformations, they just serve as anchor points that serve to transpose the associated transformation according to the chosen path. The edges are in fact points in the space of hypergraph transformations.

For each node, we take the set of incoming and outgoing edges to assemble them according to their relative positions with respect to this node by favoring continuity between the two parts (see later how) and interpolating the continuous space around these points from the gradient of each of these points. As with MoEs we could be satisfied with positions with associated embeddings nevertheless, we lose a lot of information on local curvature, which must be compensated by more points. There are several possible implementations such as:

- use a specific layer for each entity to produce the gradient that we will follow
- use a layer to build the space whose output is collapsed into a single value of the space on which we take the gradient
- define this layer by edge (defines the gradient of the level line between two nodes, see figure 7) or by node (define the gradient by position see 5). In the case of definition by edge, the further the nodes are, the more approximate the gradient is since we use layers of the same capacity regardless of the case. On the other hand, it will possibly be necessary to normalize at the time of fusion the different views of the space to counter-balance a relative local learning (the locally learned magnitude not corresponding to the global magnitude see figure 6)

Figure 5: Illustration of a continuous by edge graph representation

Figure 6: Illustration of a non normalized continuous graph representation (same space as figure 5)

Figure 7: Illustration of a continuous by node graph representation

At first glance, there is likely to be an explosion of parameters or a risk of overfitting. Nevertheless, these parameters are not independent since they all describe the same local space around a node. On the other hand, for each node, we seek to minimize the number of points necessary to describe the space. In other words, have only a few highly favored paths.

Moreover, the desired effect is to be able to add nodes on the fly without this changing the global structure, in other words to be able to more finely control the addition of new information, which can be contradictory or not, with use the non-relevant paths (not selected) will be gradually erased. This furthermore allows being able to handle rare events since even if during local fusion their weight in the whole will be almost zero, they will remain accessible to the gradient/in memory (for a configurable time at least). At minimum, we can keep a compressed trace of rare instances to allow extending them again when encountered again. With this system, we can indeed assign precision arbitrarily on certain zones, and follow curriculum learning by favoring already well-identified zones and postponing the rest.

The underlying idea is to be able to differentiate learned elements that bring knowledge about a transformation, from elements to know. For example, knowing what a capital is is not of the same order of utility as knowing what is the capital of a particular country. Obviously, sufficiently old and integrated knowledge itself becomes a useful transformation, and often an instance of this

knowledge (a capital name) crystallizes the notion itself. The objective in this case is simply to mitigate the integration of knowledge, to know if we can afford not to learn particular instances for the task in question.

3.3 Input representation

The representation of inputs is a relatively critical step, particularly in this architecture since given that each transition is a graph manipulation, the input must be a graph. In discrete contexts (e.g. a vocabulary), the association is direct between embeddings and vocabulary. Nevertheless, these embeddings cannot simply represent a point in a subspace: they must represent either a transformation on a graph, or a graph. There are several possible implementations:

- Associate with each vocabulary item two layers (Keys, Values) that will serve as first transformation on noised tokens
- Associate with each item a discrete graph directly

The first solution risks proving unstable at training since the model will only have access to input data once. The second solution seems more relevant here but requires redefining the role of embeddings no longer as objects having an intrinsic value that we transform but as transactional objects whose value is exclusively defined by its transformation. In this definition, comparing two embeddings is in fact no longer possible. If each token represents a graph, it is easy to define a difference score between two representations, but this does not take into account the ability to move from one graph to another, some states being impossible. For example, comparing the structure of two molecules with identical representation except for the 3D orientation of a bond, is not possible on the simple basis of this structure since the resulting properties can be radically different. Of course, this is a solvable problem by including properties in each embedding whose role is to define a subspace where different but semantically close elements are close. Nevertheless, this only moves the problem, since ultimately the embedding associated with an element remains a point in space. It is a simple approximation (and generally giving good results) but incorrect.

If we consider an embedding as the continuous representation of a discrete graph, and more specifically as the n -dimensional representation of a graph in which the latter becomes a planar graph, then to compare two tokens with each other, it is necessary to use the entire model to determine if there exists a transformation from one to the other.

A more accurate way to compare embeddings is for each output token to use the output probability of the target token relative to the current tokens. This is exactly what the training of these architectures does by aligning output distributions for example. But does not explicitly formalize the causality of transformations, since the only constraint point is discretized through these embeddings.

Going back to the representation of embeddings as planar graphs, each embedding represents the graph in relative position, as for a complete sequence of tokens they represent in fact several different views of the same final graph. One embedding itself represents a relative view of its associated graph (so no absolute position in a space). At the forward pass, these embeddings are assembled in a correct relative position compare to the other. Only then, the model transforms the input sequence's graph into the response. At the end of the forward pass, the model needs to re-decompose the transformed graph into segmented relative view. And as a matter of fact, in this configuration, some embeddings' role is to help positioning each view together, acting as meta graph, (since an input sequence does not have the whole assembled graph but only individual relative view, the output sequence cannot have absolute view, nor information per embeddings regarding its positioning in the whole graph).

Moreover, one challenge is to correctly size the associated graph and dimension of the embeddings. Higher dimension means a more complex graph as a starting point (so less transformation), but also more parameters. We could have a smaller dimension, but for each embedding we could have multiple views of the underlying graph (thus multiple token per embedding).

Nonetheless, the objective is then to work with these views optimized to capture maximum information without deploying the entire graph. Thus, in such a configuration, tokenization itself is no longer relevant, since it only defines the size and number of available views. In other words, with different tokenization, the final result is the same. Even the output result can be reformulated under this vision, since the output corresponds to finding in a number of tokens to represent the final graph obtained under the most relevant views that allow reconstructing it. We can even express the compression/incompleteness rate of the produced token sequence by estimating the graph reconversion score.

On a small scale in multiple dimensions it is possible to represent a graph in a planar way, but for a whole token sequence, the final graph will probably exceed this property and therefore view choices will have to be made. Although we can envision higher dimensions to cover this case, there will come a time when in this configuration the graph will be too complex.

In this model, to compare different results, we compare their internal representations. Thus, by understanding data in the form of graphs, we align with JEPA [22, 23, 24] models where comparison is not done in the input/output space.

Therefore, there are different ways to implement this graph representation:

- consider embeddings as a planar view of a graph and therefore consider an embedding as a vector field representing attractors (nodes) and currents between attractors (edges)
- consider embeddings as a compressed view of the graph (auto-encoder, token modeling [25], property encoding)

The problem in these cases is the need to compress/decompress at each step, at each node of the model to extract either the transformations (expressed as graphs). It is perfectly possible to maintain a library of these transformations either at the scale of each node, where the key/value transformation is transformed into a retrieve process. In this configuration, the nodes carry the prototype-tokens and the transformation happens with the key/value of conditioning. Nevertheless, at each value update it will be necessary to recalculate the correspondence.

Therefore, we can keep a vocabulary in a vector database of tokens. We can then more quickly find the correspondence between a graph at the input and output of the transformation to deduce the rule in force in it.

As a reminder, we have two ways to represent a transformation, either explicitly with the Key/value layer, or implicitly with relations between classes (for a combination of classes we map the other accessible ones), we can then deduce this transformation. So this method can concern both tokens of classes or layers of transformations.

Moreover, even in training, the entire discrete chain of graph transformation will not be verified but only on reduced portions. And, as we saw previously, we can define a transformation locally or globally: remapping input classes of the transformation (assign to a graph, a simpler graph and do it in a way to preserve relations between initial graphs) or by following a whole chain. In other words, by ensuring locally the validity of the transformation for each node (which can be parallelized) and periodically integrating partial sequences (where we can always do a remapping but which requires more time to calculate) or complete ones, we can envision practical feasibility.

In these configurations, inputs are converted to graphs at the initial step and we follow the trajectory in the space of transformations. Nevertheless, if this method works in discrete input cases, for continuous cases (such as images), the transformation is problematic. Because, we cannot

really simply produce a continuous input-graph representation transformation that will then be used as input to the model. In this configuration for example, we must find initial graphs expressive enough to support in a coherent manner operations such as edge detection kernels, which is a non-trivial operation on a semantic representation of the graph. In this situation, we can employ a small network (300-500 million parameters) outside the model (and not following the architecture of the general model) but trained in the chain that produces the appropriate embeddings and therefore work no longer with raw data. The disadvantage is that we cut ourselves off from access to raw data, which in many cases is not a problem but remains a hindrance for a general architecture.

A solution is then to no longer work with embeddings as input but extract from this input data the representations as we go (making input data accessible to all nodes in the model). We can see this as a byte sequence that we must cast into a class containing subclasses or subtypes. If we have no indication of the class to use or the types present, we can only take the set of available classes and try to cast (assuming a fixed order for example in the order of appearance of class attributes). At the end we measure the fit of data in each class by measuring the number of remaining bytes that we cannot cast. And for each type, we define tests to know if beyond the format a cast element behaves as expected for this type.

This is exactly the principle of HoTT that we organize in several levels and for each type each element is defined with the paths to move from one to another, which forms a topological space where once an element is placed on it, we can evaluate its coherence in this type by doing internal transformations. The continuous space of transformations is in fact the set of all elements of all types, of all levels flattened. This is possible since complex types (integrating subtypes) are not logically reachable before having identified these subtypes. This corresponds to the notion of causality in hypergraph transformations.

Until now, we have defined this undifferentiated space from which we can at best hope for causality but not coherence at the type level. The objective of this model is to learn paths that will be retrospectively grouped into "islands" (set of elements that have internal coherence, namely membership rules and internal topology) which represents only a reorganization of the undifferentiated space. What deviates from HoTT is in fact this approximation of topological spaces into continuous spaces without defining all elements discretely. But keeping discrete elements at first order since the continuous space is only an approximation made on certain points. At the end of training we could very well do without discrete elements, and later re-discretized the space as needed. Just as it is then possible to add new nodes [26]. In this model as training progresses, we should be able to better differentiate point knowledge (what is the capital of a country) which are elements of these islands and transformation knowledge (the island itself which represents capitals). This then offers a possibility to train the network differently where we verify above all that the trajectory follows the right categories without penalizing the model because in the expected responses it does not know an instance of this category (capital of a country).

This island learning corresponds in fact to building a space on the space of transformations where a node of this space represents a trajectory. In other words, we link a set of nodes that form the causal trajectory of transformations for a particular input and we link these nodes to another node that no longer really exists on the same plane as the sub-nodes but which is integrated into training as if everything were on the same plane. The value of this node is either defined by the gradient along this path, or by a transformation on individual gradients to compose them (each level having the same light transformation). And each edge between these types of nodes creates its own space where a point of this space is in fact a whole trajectory. Islands are defined at this level. It is bidirectional hierarchical learning.

This hierarchical learning is a natural inclusion with the formulation in graph and HoTT, notably in the notion of compression of hypergraph representations in continuous space since the

activation state of a lower space can be represented by a single point in the following upper space. In other words, we do a re-mapping of classes, where each the complexity of each point is hidden by the lower levels. Following this idea, it is also possible to reformulate the continuous space of transformations as an ordered space of all hypergraph representations of the same order of magnitude of complexity. In other words, if we return to our continuous space of transformations, we can consider that the number of anchor nodes represents the average number of nodes determining the complexity of hypergraphs at this level. And this continuous space represents the superposition of all these accessible hypergraphs. For example, a graph of which we would have an edge with a certainty of 0.5 between nodes represents a composition of graphs that have this edge at 1 and others at 0.

Thus, at each anchor node, we use the inputs in conditioning to eliminate graphs from this superposition (and therefore close to a diffusion model on graphs where we remove at each iteration edges [27]). On the other hand, as complexity is controlled, we can operate in low dimension (the same for all levels), and therefore directly extract the hypergraph corresponding to the input in question by following the remaining nodes and edges (we then consider the continuous space as a planar view of the graph and therefore the direction defined by the embeddings at each edge indicates those that are connected and in which direction).

We could also consider a model closer to a graph generation model that builds node by node, edge by edge with the same model (so all anchor nodes would share the same base with slight finetuning). This is a possible solution but it has disadvantages: the need for global attention, the non-persistence of nodes (which cannot be directly attached to the node of the following upper space), greater processing slowness.

The advantage of considering a fixed space is to allow defining a causality of decision boundaries, and therefore accelerate processing and reduce dependence on global attention, since each node has direct access to the information useful to it and global information is descended from upper spaces as we progress in the lower space. As for links with the upper space, it is possible to circumvent this problem with floating representations but the interest of these links is the direct synchronization of all dependent elements (at the first order of dependence). Moreover most hierarchical learning does not establish these links and synchronizes by floating representations.

In this configuration, we can in theory do without embeddings and tokenization, but in practice this allows above all to be able to access retrospectively the raw input data. Indeed, the nodes of an upper space are connected to lower nodes and therefore have direct access to the exact set of the representation, but we can also add between each level a floating representation of the whole state of the lower space and train each node to function either with the exact representation, or with the condensed representation. This has the advantage that we can start training the model with embeddings and a tokenization decided in advance, use it as condensed representation at level 0 space, level 1 space, it will naturally provide a segmentation that can at the end be used as optimal tokenization for the network. And also, define a level -1 where we pass as input the values of tokenized embeddings, which are then decomposed, aligned with level 0 representations, and therefore over the course of training do entirely without embeddings and tokenization. We could start by directly each individual value (where at this stage, continuous or discrete, everything becomes discrete), to go up the chain but this risks being too costly in training. The objective is rather to start from an intermediate base to then align the levels below (which should be faster), with the objective of allowing all levels to have access if needed to raw data (for example by querying how many letters in a word, etc).

In this configuration, temporarily no longer exists as an implicit dimension but explicit (as in Wolfram's hypergraph transformations). To simplify, each level processes types of similar complexity, for example: level -1 processes letters, level 1 words, level 2 sentences. So the interaction between each entity of a similar level is captured as trajectory of the direct upper level. In other

words, once a level has determined for a word its graph representation, the following level indicates which transformations to follow to evolve over time (along the causality axis of the sequence).

This has the particularity of being able to process each word in parallel (like the Mamba model using SSMs), which then defines in the continuous space the set of possibilities (a word having several meanings, at this stage the space contains a superposition of discrete possibilities), which we can then combine afterwards to collapse the continuous functions into an element or a few elements. It remains then to ensure that for each final entity this corresponds to a discrete element for each representation.

Moreover, it is necessary to represent the upper layers as global information sharing links (for analogy, inter-layer links in a transformer). Now as they are based on the same space that they represent in a different organization, it is possible to merge all levels into one and therefore perform processing in a single pass. Taking a layer as base, we can infuse this layer with global relations defined by the upper layers by distilling these transformations into the base level, since each transformation and each upper node has a bidirectional link with upper nodes, we know how to diffuse information in the model in 1 layer, either by adding links directly, or by distilling the transformations of upper layers directly into the layers of each anchor node. This layer collapsing is dynamic, in the sense that it does not require training a model in parallel (even if feasible as is and would allow keeping the innovation of the model closed source, and providing a flattened version of the model with similar results but difficult to interpret and re-decompose in open source). Current NN models actually do similar actions, either too isolated for hierarchical learning, or too compacted where a model on the same level of abstraction must learn everything with only the output as constraint; which only greatly complicates the task of the model since it must itself model these different levels without having the resources or architecture for it.

This is also aligned with recent advances in Hierarchical Reasoning models [28, 29] where a supervision link drastically improves performance.

From a transformation space point of view, these links represent in fact jumping from one node to another by bypassing a succession of others to take a shortcut. Which similarly to neural ODEs, also produces coherent results despite being in the transformation space, by integrating for example over the entire path, by making jumps as with Continuous Normalizing Flows [30]. Another way to see it is at the neuron level itself namely that a graph transformation rule can in fact be decomposed into discrete actions (one action at a time) such as (delete edge, add edge, delete node, add node), although the order within a rule itself must be respected (such as not deleting a node before having deleted all its edges). Thus, a single neuron can represent this action to take by segmenting its activation level according to the number of actions. Nevertheless, the pattern matching of the subgraph on which we must apply this action is not decomposable as such (a neuron cannot handle pattern matching entirely). So, we need a group of neurons that identifies the work subgraph, and which sends a single signal shared by a whole other group of neurons which has the task of applying the actions to this subgraph.

3.4 Implicit continuous routing

As mentioned previously, routing between different nodes is no longer explicitly discrete but continuous and corresponds to the path. This continuous space is represented at each anchor node of the space as composition of partial views of the space represented on edges around which we interpolate the space. The path chosen to go from one node to another is defined by the edges contributing most to the path given by the gradient, either in top-k, or in automatic clustering to identify groups. If the chosen path falls mainly on an edge, we follow it to go to the next node, otherwise we follow the path which is the composition of anchors associated with chosen edges (and therefore all their attributes are merged).

In this configuration the edges have either directly a learned gradient (which we then interpolate at the node level), or by a layer that outputs a gradient, or by a layer that outputs a value from which we take the gradient (which has the advantage of being able to potentially model the space by distant zones and not necessarily at the point of the gradient itself but which can pose problems during backpropagation).

There are different ways to use embeddings to guide the gradient, either directly in conditioning, or with algorithmic complexity. In other words, for each transformation at the anchor node we take the matching score of the transformation rule pattern and we use this metric (indirectly combined with the transformation at which we find ourselves), to orient towards the next node. The space is then organized in terms of complexity (in other words the casting score on the current type).

In this configuration, we can follow several paths in parallel (starting at different anchors or splitting different paths at the same anchor), which represents the work of different attention heads in a transformer. We determine in advance the number of paths at all times that we want to follow (the number of heads), and at each anchor we share the current position of each path via a shared attention module (SSM) to force convergence towards common anchors. Technically, each island can function independently and reroute itself towards the right islands (it is moreover designed to be distributed and to be able to apply training algorithms different from backpropagation), but in practice this represents a cost not necessarily justified.

On the other hand, this can solve the problem of merging responses for a model or Winner-take-all, since here each transformation does not estimate its own activation threshold but its own completeness (which has a verifiable correspondence with discretization into hypergraph). The entire role of the model is in fact to estimate the complexity of the steps it takes, in the sense the effort necessary to move from one state to another. There is no longer a notion of certainty estimation because it is no longer the role of the model to produce such a score. Even if the path taken by the input is not the right one because pattern matching is not sufficient we can always merge patterns to find one that corresponds to the input. In other words, we do not force any path and we can directly compare the matching score between each node to take the most propitious without this forcing the model to produce an average result between different possible responses.

3.5 Model learning

The value of being able to extract transformations lies in finding an implicit decomposition of a new problem into islands/modules that we can then test in different combinations to ensure solution validity. For example, a model learning to play Snake should ideally learn a model similar to the Monte Carlo algorithm whose rewards are specific to each game (which we can/must extract from each game as instance nodes, whose links we can then evaluate), a grid creation model (what happens when playing Snake with a diagonal grid), and an action management model (what happens if I design a game with other possible actions/movements for Snake). In other words, from a single problem it can produce a modeling to be tested independently in different contexts to learn a generic solution.

This can be viewed as a form of collective of individuals (the transformations) sharing their knowledge. The value of hypergraph transformations lies in the ability to model entire universes (i.e., entire model systems calibrated on different existence rules). In other words, when a transformation should exist but does not, the transformation is not incorrect, it simply belongs to another universe. Thus learning this transformation's incorrectness in the current universe actually enables refining knowledge about another universe. The advantage here is being able to shift the entire universe to adapt to different new tasks. With the continuous graph structure, we can extend

knowledge about a universe or not, and thus when reporting information as an incorrect transformation, we can decide to develop the adjacent universe or simply update the corresponding node (which will translate to a microscopic modification of the node’s space). The idea is to rapidly discriminate one universe from another, to be able to recreate it from scratch or at least guide its learning from scratch. Obviously it will not be possible to recover the entire model, but by learning any universe according to the data, the discriminating knowledge of the target universe will enable shifting the whole.

Moreover, in this architecture, a ”module” is not reintegrated into the ensemble (regardless of its size) through weight averaging but by finding its relative position with respect to other modules and integrating it according to the state of knowledge of the space: either weak knowledge, preserving only the most discriminating property, or fine knowledge, reintegrating secondary properties.

From a backpropagation (BP) perspective, each pass actually involves a relatively fixed number of nodes, not the entire model. This reduces the number of parameters to modify simultaneously. This assumes good graph connectivity, which can be mitigated by taking different paths approximated in a single hop simply to give BP a more global view of the space. Alternatively, we can update iteratively: on the first pass, detect the necessary deviation, take the nodes along this path (requiring recalculation of transformations but not routing, thus requiring less time), then take the gradient along this path and continue until the deviation is properly covered by the current path.

The model is primarily designed to use methods other than BP, such as predictive coding, since each island can theoretically be pretrained independently and must be able to route data to the correct islands because at cast time it knows what is missing (in other words, to handle its own routing locally), using local synchronization through position exchange to accelerate convergence.

The underlying idea of the learning approach in this architecture is that given infinite time and the set of all possible answers (to all possible questions), one can formally verify whether an answer is valid for a question. Obviously, under time constraints, this is not feasible. Nevertheless, we can preserve this idea to evaluate answer proposals we know and select the one that best matches. This match is either formally valid, or we evaluate the complexity of the missing transformations needed to reposition the answer toward a more suitable one, or to simply use the answer with caution. The model should be viewed as a library of axioms (indeed, the model is closer to a giant retrieval system where the core model is merely the organizational strategy, and facts are stored independently), which we apply successively to obtain the proof we seek. This is the mechanism used by LLM-based proof assistants like Deepseek Prover [31]. They generate proposals in natural language that are translated by a formal assistant like Lean or Coq, and then each link in the natural language reasoning chain is assigned a sparse score depending on whether the proof succeeded or failed in Lean.

In our architecture, we attempt to apply the same logic but within the model itself to structure its learning and reasoning, without depending on an external assistant. The primary objective is not verifiability, but the underlying logic. Thus, algorithmic complexity [32] becomes a better evaluation metric than Euclidean distance, for example (just as the natural gradient with Fisher information is more suitable in a differential geometry context).

This complexity is not trivial in this architecture since it guides the entire chosen path and enables approximations to an intuitionistic logic approach. Since we orient an answer to a question based on this complexity. More concretely, in this architecture, we cannot know what constitutes a good answer; we can only measure the effort required to move from the question to the answer, whether the question and answer share similar complexity, whether the answer uses only part of the question (which we can know since transformation rules apply to subgraphs), etc.

In practice, a question serves to select the subset of axioms considered valid. Either by relying on the model’s library, in other words, by being cast onto types. Or by establishing axioms as true

itself, meaning what failed to be cast into types defines a new type in the space we consider valid. This notably allows us both to know that the context of an answer is potentially false (because the axiom is known to be invalid), while still permitting reasoning on these hypotheses.

In the continuous space of transformations, the question (the input) traces its own graph of what is valid on the fly by dynamically creating paths between things that should not have them. This is essential to avoid forcing the input to take a valid canonical path, thereby distorting the nature of the input, the semantics of the input.

Necessarily, in the continuous routing space, links we know to be false (nonexistent) will have low energy (a hill), unlike valid paths (a valley) that the gradient will naturally follow. But this does not prevent following them; it simply defines the complexity cost of following this false path, which may turn out to be lower than the cumulative complexity cost of successfully casting what cannot be cast from the input (because it assumes something false). What must be understood here is that the invalid transformation exists in this context, whether valid or not; the transformation space contains all transformations, but on top of this space, the model traces boundaries of what it considers valid in the current universe (the universe defined by the typology of all dataset inputs). Therefore, a hypothetical question simply temporarily alters these boundaries, moving from one universe to another and shifting all validity boundaries based on the assumption that a specific transformation must be valid.

In other words, all information (valid or not) is information (useful). During training, we differentiate between modifying the rules themselves and modifying the validity boundaries by ensuring universe segregation. For example, to the question "How does the sun shine?", the answer "By making light" is not incorrect at all; it is even perfectly valid, but it states the obvious. The complexity of the answer does not match what the question supposes in our way of thinking. In other words, what we learn is the complexity preference that guides a question toward its answer.

Therefore, during this training, we do not penalize the answer but update the preference. Nevertheless, if the possible answer(s) (since the model is not limited to a single answer) contradict the target answer (meaning, by defining paths that cannot be deformed from one to the other, or that borrow paths defined as false by the question's axioms), then we have a universe definition problem: the paths involved in the predicted answers belong to another universe, meaning the learned boundaries of our current universe are inconsistent.

3.6 Space modeling

One of the first attempts at this architecture, from a conceptual standpoint, was to associate with each element of a vocabulary a shape that defines its properties (as the shape of a protein's receptors defines what it can do and governs its interactions with other proteins) and to have a substrate in which these shapes could evolve. To do this, we experimented on a very small scale with chemical retrosynthesis software like ASKCOS [33] (developed since 2016). The objective was (and still is) to equip each word of a language with intrinsic computational properties, whose role appears in their interactions. A major obstacle (beyond the obvious training time, execution time, interaction rule complexity, etc.) was the substrate itself: it is very rare to be able to perform a chemical reaction with a few compounds without managing other parameters like stirring, temperature, progressive introduction of other intermediate agents. So many elements that are not defined by the inputs but are specific to the substrate itself.

So we made adjustments to separate from the chemical aspect by defining each token as a surface on an n-sphere (initially 3D spheres so that a point on this surface would be accessible from an infinity of directions, which is not permitted by a circle that has only two possible directions) whose initial deformation defines its interactions, and substrate-specific combination rules. The

fundamental problem remained the same: ultimately all deformations were permitted and there was no self-consistency verification.

This naturally leads toward differential geometry on manifolds (notably sub-Riemannian ones that can model interactions in parts of the cerebral cortex [34]), whose structure defines the substrate rules and where some rules allow the invariance of these properties throughout the entire space. We can then compose shapes together and measure these properties to define the transformation’s stability (and consequently its correctness).

In this sense, the geometry of the very space used to model transformations defines the possible transformations. Yet even with topological constraints, provided they are expressive enough, one can end up producing anything and everything. The advantage chemical transformations had was their stability: an unstable compound will decompose on its own. This stability can be defined by the length of paths taken on the manifold, compared to similar ones to define what is natural as a transformation from what is not, etc.

But all this remains an ad hoc method; the very choice of manifold is architectural and not learned. As we have seen, we can learn a local parametrization that extends to the entire manifold via transition functions, thus capturing the underlying geometric structure. We can even learn a model that explicitly defines the trajectory (geodesic, rectilinear, etc.). But the very method of detecting anomalies, instabilities, naturalness is not direct; they require grouping, defining metrics, comparing. Which is absolutely not a problem in itself. Simply, the substrate (the geometry of the space) continues to play a more important role than the input elements. And what we end up doing is training a model to create a projection that sends the most common input elements (elements defined as natural via the dataset) onto a correct form (geodesic, rectilinear). So when an exotic element appears, its trajectory/shape will be atypical and detectable but will not necessarily preserve consistency among exotic elements since we are outside the domain of application. This is inherent to the very nature of NN training and its approximation nature. Ultimately, for an invalid, exotic input, it is very unlikely that the projection onto the space produces an impossible geometry (e.g., a path that crosses through the sphere). We will rather have a path making zigzags or crossing itself on the sphere.

There are models that project data into a product space (Euclidean \times Hyperbolic \times Spherical), thus forming a decomposition into geometric components to better capture mixed data structures (hierarchies, cycles, similarities) [35]. Nevertheless, this remains primarily to improve representation and not to identify which geometric component is most natural for a given datum, thereby revealing inadequacies, inconsistencies.

However, this raises the question of whether there exists a model that for an exotic element is capable of defining a system in which this element would be considered natural. This is the principle of meta-learning, but where we ask: the continuous space that the model has approximated and which is supposed to contain an approximation of all models, in what space is this model itself included? How can I reconstruct this model if I no longer have this model? Hence HoTT, which is by definition a Self-founding theory.

In other words, we seek a way not to penalize the model when it produces representations that do not respect the geometry but rather to push the model to identify the geometry that makes this representation correct (e.g., in what geometry is a path that crosses through the sphere valid?). And dynamically: for each datum, without assuming it belongs to a new task.

Universes under this architecture are meant to solve this problem by allowing movement from one universe to another with very little information by identifying from a few exotic transformations which universe they belong to, then shifting all learned transformations in this universe toward another. Like a geometric form under constraints, where modifying a single parameter can completely change the form by recalculating dependencies and constraints with this simple new value.

In this sense, detecting an anomaly amounts only to finding the universe (the manifold) in which this trajectory is natural/optimal. Thus, by this account, all trajectories have their own universe; only certain universes are so close to each other and have such negligible influence on axioms that we can approximate them as being the same.

All this therefore raises the question of manifold topology and the use of differential geometry compared to HoTT or CT. From a practical standpoint, all three theories have evolved to enable the same things (differential geometry also has its discrete version with simplices, a hierarchical version by layers), are all relatively computable (for example, Lean supports all three), and all allow defining unifying frameworks. So the question is not really which theory to use, but the architecture that can replace one theory with another. We oriented ourselves toward HoTT thanks to hypergraph transformations that offer a fundamentally discrete framework, which for verification and manipulation is simpler. But discrete differential geometry also allows this, simply with potentially more effort.

The blocks of this architecture do not change according to the theory used, but their content does.

Moreover, it is probably not necessary to resort to HoTT to define cortical operations that already seem to use differential geometry. However, HoTT allows us to discretely define a topology on which we can define differential geometry (with some guarantees). In other words, to a differential geometry on a manifold defined by some invariants, we can associate a correspondence with a space that would require far more discrete points to define. Thus, even if we do not resort to HoTT in the levels close to inputs, such as for continuous image input processing, in higher levels, we can use HoTT by approximating the invariants of the lower space as being an HoTT space. This is an excessive simplification, but bridges exist between HoTT and differential geometry like Synthetic Differential Geometry. Nevertheless, this remains a possible and useful approximation, at the expense of formality.

Starting from differential geometry, we could also have defined something conceptually similar (Jet Bundle, Lie groupoids and ∞ -groupoids, Cartan-Ehresmann Hierarchy).

Particular attention must be paid with HoTT to the Law of Excluded Middle (LEM), which it does not support natively, although this can be extended.

What is practical with HoTT in this architecture is that it allows explicitly encoding impossibilities via negation proofs, rather than relying solely on an energy landscape where certain paths are simply costly.

In type theory, proving $\neg A$ amounts to showing that assuming A leads to a contradiction. In our architecture, this can also translate into the ability to mark certain paths as formally impossible in the current universe, not simply improbable.

For example, learning that there is a theoretical limit to compression (Kolmogorov incompressibility) does not translate into a simple high energy barrier between "compression" and "infinitely small," but by the structural absence of a valid path in the transformation graph. This can be shortened in this architecture by a path specifically marked as impossible, whose role is then to synthesize this topological hole.

Concretely, rather than depending solely on an optimization landscape where a gradient would naturally avoid certain regions (purely energetic), the model can explicitly know that certain transformations violate axioms of the current universe. This becomes particularly useful for hypothetical reasoning: we can distinguish "costly but possible" from "logically impossible in this context," which is facilitated by the architecture's graph structure.

3.7 POC

3.7.1 Graph based

To test this architecture (see figure 8), we propose a first simplification in two steps:

- The encoder (diffusion model) that produces the hypergraph of the input (embeddings) in the form of a graphon [36] and an intensity function that will allow the sampling of nodes.
- The decoder (same diffusion model) that produces the output hypergraph by relying on the graphon of the input.

Figure 8: Illustration of continuous hypergraph

In this POC, we represent the transformation space in the form of a continuous graph (see figure 9). In other words, we preserve the bottom-top flow of a standard model but to produce a usable graph as output.

Initially, we can preserve the standard attention mechanism by considering a step in the transformation space, noted T_t , constant (and representing the layers). The diffusion time step is noted T_d . But ultimately, the attention module will also be part of the space parameters and will therefore be equally combined with other points. The underlying idea is to be able to avoid full attention, by constraining each node to take only a part of the tokens, and by exchanging information between nodes at each time step T_t .

Note that, in this setup, each node is conditioned on the inputs.

Figure 9: Illustration of internal working of the diffusion model

At the moment of backpropagation (BP), we add nodes to this transformation graph to correspond to those imposed by BP. In other words, we do not directly modify the nodes in place, but we update the space. Because as a reminder, the continuous space is formed by discrete elements, and when navigating in this space, we locally gather the different edges to construct the continuation of the space. This is actually similar to a database where the interpolation between the different local elements amounts to retrieving the right elements that best represent the space. Navigation therefore amounts to selecting the right transformation for the inputs in question.

Note here that at each node, we do not directly transform the input, which for continuous data such as images can pose problems since there is a need for recurrent processing on this data, and the graph data that the diffusion model probably cannot carry this load. To mitigate this effect, for each node we can construct a residual flow by subtracting from the inputs the values that were used in the attention for this transformation. We can also envision a companion model that at each node also transforms the inputs. Or another MLP at the node to convert each graphon into embeddings specific to the inputs from prototype values and applies attention with the embeddings of the inputs to perform a transformation. The idea here remains to be able to extract the "essence" of the embedding in the form of a graph.

On the other hand, the intensity function to choose the right number of nodes and their proper sampling, can also be constructed in parallel at each node, as each node locally knows its interest in sampling here or not.

In this POC, we therefore go from a noisy graphon (which we can consider as representing a graph with all possible edges), to a sparse graphon by constraint. From this output graphon, we can sample a discrete graph, then go back up the flow. Here, each transformation is a graph transformation, so each transformation (each node of the continuous space) also manipulates a sub-graphon, and therefore for each transformation we can deduce the discrete graph transformation made, as well as the position of the pattern to match (thanks to attention). This allows us to simply verify the discrete equivalent, without having to search and match the patterns of hypergraph transformation rules.

Even close to the initial noise, the transformation represents a graphon that is simply not sparse. These transformations close to noise nevertheless pose some questions, namely whether the initial noise does not represent the empty type of HoTT from which one can prove anything and everything. Which for evaluating reasoning can be relevant by detecting reasoning that needs to get closer to noise to start again in another direction.

Nevertheless, these transformations close to noise remain an edge deletion, however minimal it

may be. We can then consider considering non-normalized local versions to sparsify the graphon relative to the previous state.

Or, we can consider a discrete version of the diffusion model, closer to a perceiver that would start on source values, which could represent a family of learned graphons to express all the others. Semantically, since we can start from this point to create anything, this potentially remains an empty type, but potentially simpler to sparsify the graphons of transformations close to the source.

Then, we do the same thing for the output graphon, and for each transformation we locally compare the input and output graphons to also extract a transformation. Indeed, the transformation space also includes the temporal axis as an explicit dimension. So each transformation once in a state (in this case once the input representation is found) must know towards what to evolve (the output representation) and this transformation represents temporality.

Note that the graphon of the input is in reality constrained to no form, and therefore could represent anything. To this effect, we impose a progressive sparsification of the graphon through diffusion, and a similar degree of complexity between classes (which are clustered initially, then will become an integral part of the architecture once the hierarchical layers are put in place).

This POC architecture allows to simply extract a discrete graph representation, while combining validation at the level of the model transformations themselves. Here, the embeddings here have a different value from that of the final architecture. But the objective of the architecture is to learn a geometry of the space on which the input data moves. In other words, when we consider the inputs as graphs, the continuous space of transformations then forms a space with its own geometry, and we can then interpret the role of transformations as what allows the movement of these inputs on this space.

The geometry of the transformation space can be given by an external analysis, but ultimately it will be carried by the hierarchical layers. This means that the network can directly take embeddings as input, and perform transformations on them. In other words, for each transformation we will have the equivalent of a metric or a particular displacement. As for the pattern matching score of the graphs, there will be the equivalent by the local measurement of the metric.

Each layer can then exist in its own manifold (it is not a different resolution of the same space at each layer, but a reorganization of the space. When the layers are all merged this will give only one large space perfectly organized for the current universe), which can be predefined in cases where we have information, or learned. In the case of predefinition, we then construct the equivalent of the continuous space of graphs to have the same geometry as the imposed manifold. In all cases, the model itself will seek to compress this space with a minimum of parameters to approximate it, but keeping the possibility to change the manifold along the way. The updates of the space will simply no longer be done transformation by transformation but at a more global scale (like doing a grouped visual rendering rather than individually).

This means that one of the hierarchical layers will represent all possible manifolds and all possible metrics. By knowing a few manifolds (Riemannian, Euclidean, etc.) or a few models (via their properties represented by a graph), we can orient the reconstruction from scratch by triangulating the position from known references. It is not said that from one training from scratch to another, we have the same positions, but we will most likely preserve the same relationships between these elements. Thus, we can imagine creating a unique model that represents all possible choices [37].

This model remains a simplification that notably does not include hierarchical layers, parallel processing, agentification of trajectories to test different environments and combinations, addition of neural memory (short, medium, long term) to prune the graph of the continuous space, graph j - j manifold conversion, universe shift for meta learning, reconstruction from scratch without

data, execution variability (here we make a constant T_t step), fusion of all layers into one, topos verification, multiway hypergraph, etc.

3.7.2 Manifold based

A more direct application to test is to abstract the graph representation to jump directly to the geometric space it creates. In this configuration, the transformations directly process the input values, and the continuous space is the implicit projection of the transformations onto a low-dimensional manifold (see figure 10). We can represent the space as a continuous grid discretized at certain points that carry the representation of the space at that point and its surroundings, and which is associated with a transformation (FFN). The transitions between each node carry both the relative position to each other, and the gradient over that portion of space. We then assemble all incoming and outgoing transitions at a node, merging them according to their relative positions to obtain an interpolation of the geometry at that node/point and its surroundings.

Figure 10: Illustration of internal working of the diffusion model

We could use a black-box model that takes as input an FFN and projects it onto the manifold with coordinates, or even directly the input and produces a position on the manifold on which we take the gradient to directly calculate the modifications to make to the input (making the transformation implicit). Nevertheless, this opposes the vision of this architecture which attempts to make the processes as explicit as possible. For example, obscuring the update of the geometry or transformations during an update since it becomes difficult to know which portion is impacted and what is propagated. On the other hand, it is more complicated to be able to allocate more precision to a part of the manifold, although we can imagine representing this black-box NN as a continuous map of its activation states, but which would therefore reproduce what we are trying to do. And finally, most importantly, this would limit our capacity to maintain locally parallel/different geometries and the ability to add information on the fly even at inference.

Regarding the forward pass, we pass the tokens through a standard embedding layer, and for all

starting nodes, we pass the token through the associated FFN. We can also choose the calculation resolution by selecting only certain input nodes. The underlying idea of this forward pass is to calculate all valid paths to create a probability distribution on the manifold.

This reflects the very nature of HoTT which allows searching for equivalent paths. And this allows defining the very notion of validity for a path, by simple self-consistency. Indeed, if in the space of hypergraph transformations, the input can be represented in a static geometry that is the same for all (i.e. a graphon is a continuous grid that represents the adjacency matrix where each node of the hypergraph has a position on this grid), when we abstract this notion of graph to focus on the geometry created by these transformations, we end up with embeddings representing real values that do not share this property (e.g. an image can be rotated in different directions and yet represent the same thing). In a graph, this problem transposes to the nature of the representation, since what we are interested in is the relationships between graphs, but with a graphon we can have multiple selections of positioned nodes that represent the same graph. This nevertheless remains partially solvable by considering the space of graphons as a spatial organization of all graph representations. This is not the case in the space of values, except to consider an upstream NN that abstracts this dependence on position, or to find equivariant transformations according to certain properties, which although feasible complicates the task.

Consequently, we cannot store a value/representation to compare during the current transformation to measure how much this transformation does what it does, how valid it is. This is an essential metric since it is the correspondence of how much a hypergraph transformation matches the pattern. The solution is therefore to consider simultaneously all paths and eliminate those that are inconsistent. After all, the manifold is composed of a set of fibers/individual paths, and a specific input only represents a slice of this manifold: each token carries within it multiple semantics that is embodied by the set of paths it can take.

To calculate this validity, at each node we consider that the transformation made is entirely valid, that it does 100% what it is supposed to do. Therefore, we have a reference point to determine the validity of other transformations. Either by extracting a representation (by shared projection) of this transformation by comparing the input and output of this transformation, then comparing this transformation with others. Or, starting from the position of the node, navigating to the position of another node, which defines a transformation path, and it is then sufficient to compare the result obtained at the end of this path (the transformed input token) with the actual value at that node. We thus obtain a validity score.

By repeating the operation for all possible paths to the same node, and independently considering each node having a valid transformation, we can establish a map of paths that are consistent with each other (that lead to similar results throughout), and eliminate those that lead to contradictions (results that are too different). This elimination is a simple weighting of the path by the score. We do not actually decide to eliminate paths.

And therefore, from this cross-interaction between all nodes, we obtain the slice of possible transformations, from which we can sample a path to deduce an input (which in reality translates to taking the output of the last node of the space according to its probability).

It will happen that in the first steps in this space we cannot immediately discriminate paths. And in reality, some of these paths represent the equivalent of multi-head attention in a transformer. In other words, the central path (what the token should actually represent), needs these other paths that represent information it did not have access to. It is therefore a dependent path. This is not a problem in this architecture, since at all steps we know where the current point of the different paths is and we can connect these different points, when taking a next step which is done by gradient in an implicitly projected space of transformations, we will have access to all these values. In other words, two distant nodes make synchronized decisions. From a hypergraph point of view, this corresponds to a pattern to match distributed over different distant portions of the graphon. The two nodes will have access to part of the same pattern to match, and by propagation via

the gradient, we actually force a common path where the first node can apply its part of the transformation, and the second node its other part of the same transformation rule. There is no explicit exchange of information, or attention between the two nodes, strictly speaking. Their simple position on the manifold, and their matching score makes this exchange implicit.

Obviously, calculating all equivalent paths is too costly, particularly paths by continuous deformation. In this sense, we can provide each node with multi-scale view space, which allows tracing shortcuts between distant nodes to allow saving calculations during the forward pass. Moreover, at any moment, we sample the paths we test with a maximum. As the space is continuous and supposedly consistent (consistency learned progressively), we can extrapolate any other point in the space and the value of the associated input.

For a single token, this is an operation that can in fact be performed by Monte Carlo exploration. But this architecture has an interest for multi-token inputs (which are the standard), since we can, like in Mamba or similar RNN architectures [38], pass each token in parallel in the continuous space of transformations and then recombine while preserving causality. Hence the importance of this distribution of all possible paths (of possible meanings). In detail, for two tokens processed independently, the fusion follows the same method as before: self-consistency. For the two slices of the same manifold, it is a matter of agreeing locally for each transformation on a valid representation. In other words, the representation of the transformation we choose locally at a node for token 1, must be the same as for token 2 (and if locally the nodes are not the same, it is sufficient to trace a transformation path between the two). We then repeat the operation for other tokens. We can then train the SSM to accelerate this mechanism. At the end of the sequence we end up with a collapsed representation (more or less depending on the ambiguity of the semantics of the sequence).

Concerning embeddings, they often represent a point/position when in reality they should represent a path or the properties that this path possesses which therefore gives a set of possible paths. And we can use this metric to guide and avoid projecting back to the input space permanently. In a sense this is not wrong, because at the hierarchical level above, a trajectory is a point, and we follow a probable trajectory from this point. But it still only represents probable trajectories with the cleanest possible curvature. And therefore at some point we must compare to something else to determine what is valid from what is not (which is very different from what is probable from what is not). In this sense we reproduce the flaws of transformer architectures that only combine probabilities, we simply reformulate these probabilities in a space that has geometric properties. Which remains better but insufficient. We cannot be content with curvature alone.

A winding path can be entirely valid. So we cannot be content with mapping the input to a position on the manifold, we actually lose a lot of information which is the friction with other possible representations/other possible positions. Because even at the higher hierarchical level, it is never a point but a distribution on the manifold, since ultimately the mapping of a trajectory to a point is complicated since it is position-based, so we learn the properties of this trajectory, its topology for example, and therefore we no longer obtain a single point. And using a higher dimensional manifold to map the entirety of the input or inputs does not correct this fundamental problem which is the semantics of what the input represents relative to the manifold. If the embedding represented a position, this means that at the end of the trajectory, the entire sequence would be infused with elements specific to this position. However, the embeddings that do the mapping are themselves always relative. It's like thinking that by reading a sentence from a text, we can write another that represents the way we processed that sentence. In other words, that the word in the second position interacts in such a way with another word and that this can mean this. We do it naturally of course, but with the same number of words, we must use other words that inflect the meaning and that have (relatively) the same definition for everyone. We cannot take a sentence of specific size, take a word by assigning it another meaning, which

would be influenced by the other words of the sentence, give this sentence back to a person and expect them to understand the new meaning. Because this representation of the sentence only exists in the context that produced it. Thinking of embedding in terms of position in a manifold actually amounts to doing that. We can argue that we train the manifold to just bring close concepts together so that the position has an intrinsic semantic value, but it doesn't change the fundamental problem which translates into embeddings that are fragmented and have different representations for the same things depending on the context. It only works up to a certain point (in addition to requiring high-dimensional manifolds which slows down and complicates training and rapid learning of new tasks).

The self-consistency approach (which is that of multiple positions or representation of embeddings by description of properties) partially solves this, since a winding path can be the only valid path, because the other preferential paths with smoother geometry may have a lower score between them despite their more advantageous curvature, than the winding path which will aggregate more consistency despite its curvature. In other words, if the preferential path due to its curvature is considered valid but it makes average scores with respect to other paths, it can be eliminated in favor of the winding path which also makes an average score on the others, but not necessarily worse, except that locally does better. We can argue that the very principle of learning geometry is to be able to define a topology that allows each of these valid paths to express itself with an advantageous curvature yet there is an advantage to self-consistency which is that of being able to adapt more quickly and dynamically since what we compare is no longer the curvature which is an intrinsic property of the manifold under construction, but the paths between them which form their own manifold, regardless of the real manifold shared between them.

In this configuration, the manifold only serves to: shorten paths (and therefore reduce the number of possible transformations) and define the topology that allows knowing the preferential paths (paths with advantageous curvature, the shortest, etc. determined at training and which represent natural paths). This topology furthermore allows defining a natural information loss score. For example in HoTT, a type can be composed of other types. Nevertheless, this conversion can be lossless or not. And in the second case, a point in space that represents a valley can be understood as a type where there will be information loss. This means that when comparing paths to each other via their result, we can quantify the amount of information we expect to lose, and take it into account in the comparison.

Indirectly, this is related to the curvature of space, but which we can exploit here differently. This also has a partial link (but not totally covering) with the empty type of HoTT. We can consider that if in a space we can go from any other direction it means the reasoning is invalid. But this also represents the equivalence between types and/or a forgetting of formal structure (homotopic levels). In this configuration, we can even envision reverse paths and therefore have locally inverse transformations (which aligns with the Forward-Forward algorithm) but we could quantify the information loss and decide whether it is relevant to use them. In reality, in the forward pass, it is more relevant and efficient to calculate alternative paths and then compare the result (which rather aligns with predictive coding).

On the other hand, what we want to avoid is manifolds of too high dimension. The dimension of the embedding space associated with the node directly conditions the fineness of trajectories, since it implicitly represents a projection of a transformation of given size to a space of smaller dimension. We can mitigate this either by emitting sub-tokens for each token (which raises the question of how they are linked in the geometric space), or with paths that each process different parts of the same token.

As said previously, most operations have an equivalence between HoTT, differential geometry and CT. There are also possible additions to guide the trajectory in differential geometry that can work in the latent space by estimating certain properties but which requires another NN to encode these features. Or even to go back and forth in the manifold space and the input space. The only

question is rather how to have a unifying framework to allow a compositional system where we can move from one to the other fluidly.

However, this is why conditioning is actually problematic:

- If we consider that they are a position, then we map the inputs directly in the continuous space. So we increase its dimension.
- If we consider that they are an encoding of properties then how to influence the trajectory on this basis because they cannot be locally compared with the paths
- If we consider that the embedding represents properties of the path, then an additional NN is needed to encode them because it is already supposed to be an internal representation that the model uses itself between layers. And a simple projection cannot suffice because in the case of tokens from continuous sources, we must be able to make transformations (such as edge detection), which is no longer compatible with the nature of the internal representation which has no computational role, but just guidance and therefore is never transformed.

This is why in this setup, we did not choose diffusion, nor conditioning but we simply consider that we synchronize all tokens together (regardless of the source). So the conditioning tokens are considered as the input space. They can then exist or not in the same manifold, but at some point, there will exist a manifold that allows synchronizing all these sources. Moreover it is during this synchronization that in differential geometry the curve plays a real role since the synchronization can be seen as several spaces aligned next to each other with needles on a point of each space and connected together by a rod. We then look for paths that allow following the geometry of each surface as well as possible. And if we consider that we can only stay on the surface then a poor alignment produces zigzag trajectories on one of the surfaces for example and therefore indicates an invalid trajectory. This situation arises less if we consider that the projected point can be off the manifold and that the role of the model is to bring it back to the manifold. In any case, this property of curvature allowing to induce validity emerges from comparison with other trajectories and not from the curvature of a single trajectory alone.

As said previously, for certain tasks this is amply sufficient, just as for certain tasks the pure probabilistic approach of transformers is valid. But this only captures different and incomplete degrees of the same underlying thing. We can even argue that most tasks related to intelligence do not need more.

However, the spirit behind this architecture is to address problems so radically novel that relying on previously learned transformations would not apply. This is partially solved by meta-models, but that is not the de facto approach integrated into the model for learning during either training or inference. This architecture offers a unified approach that is inherently constructivist, intrinsically learning to build itself for any task, and potentially reducing the amount of data needed for training.

We can argue that given enough data and training pressure, a model can learn the underlying meta-algorithm that emerges from the training data, which is directly infused with our way of thinking. However, architectural decisions often lead to better performance on domain-specific tasks, which tends to be false when applied to generalized tasks. We believe this is because domain-specific architectures are not applied at a large enough scale and remain too isolated. Our architecture attempts to mitigate this by creating highly interconnected domains with highly specialized tasks, all embedded within the same continuous space where all transformations exist.

We can argue that meta-models also mitigate this issue. However, having a dedicated meta-model is already too isolated. Methods that use the same model to modify itself are more promising,

even if their information scope is limited by the output bottleneck. Even methods that use gradient information from backpropagation to edit weights remain too isolated. What we seek is a model that can locally modify itself within its own language, a language shared by every unit. Gradients provide local information but are not expressed within the model’s language itself; they are an overlay. For example, an output message and a weight modification message should be indistinguishable at first glance, only becoming determined at the end of the modification process (which can correspond to short-term synaptic plasticity). In this sense, message passing in graph networks is more aligned with these principles.

Moreover, we can argue that massive amounts of data allow a model to learn the underlying learning process, which can then be distilled into a smaller, task-agnostic model (without the entire knowledge base). In some sense, natural evolution is a form of massive distributed training over vast timescales, allowing the accumulation of massive amounts of cumulative data. However, biological neurons appear to have built-in learning algorithms that can be immediately deployed. Regardless of the path taken to train such unit-level behavior, the result is not an entire model that learns something and then teaches other models capacities distributed across compute units. Instead, it is a way of processing information that is learned at the unit level, resulting in a model capable of performing tasks as a secondary objective—a byproduct of that first unit-level learning algorithm. With our architecture, we attempt to elaborate something similar, where units have their own primary learning objective that is not related to the data itself, but rather to the structure of the network formed (which is indirectly influenced by the data).

Aligned methods such as [39] and [40] treat the model within a continuous embedding space. What we aim to achieve is to embed the modules themselves, such as MoEs, within a unified continuous space that self-validates according to trajectory coherence. This can be viewed as ensemble learning or voting, but extended toward HoTT to more formally capture types, paths as proofs, and hierarchical/universe perspectives. In this setup, the whole model itself is embedded into a continuous space and represented by composition of such spaces. Doing that, allow to have no difference between modules and the whole model, updating the model or outputting something, since all is trajectory-based representation (only the hierarchical level used changes). The learning only comes from the exposure frequencies, but at first all is considered short term knowledge/memorized knowledge. At first glance, trajectory-based validation resembles ensemble voting. However, by seeking to formalize trajectories as subspaces with language-agnostic properties that can be extracted and isolated when needed for testing, we move closer to CT and type-theoretic representations. In this framework, the types emerge from equivalence classes of trajectories : trajectories that exhibit similar behavior within subspaces are identified as instances of the same type. These can then be composed into higher-order types (which can be seen as classes). Which can then be treated as equivalence of a raw binary data (input data) that need to be cast into the best available/complete type. The input data is then both used to defined the type structure itself and the instance value associated. The next step is then to find the associated class from the input one, that will be used for the answer and which represent a transformation between class. This choice is guided by the type complexity preference association that is learn throughout the whole dataset (e.g. complex question need complex answer, certain subjects have small complexity question but high complexity answer). We can map for a specific input/question, all the possibles outputs that formally match the question. The choice into the desired output is then learning a preference mapping.

Concerning the learning of the model, it reduces to finding the reference transformation(s) for a token, which allow validating the whole by self-consistency. We could envision using an NN that from the activations of a transformation outputs a signature (like a spectral signature) or property-base signature [41], and compare with others, or learn a distribution locally by a (multi) Gaussian, or consider that the activations of the transformation are the weights of a transformation and map it in the continuous space, or use an inverse transformation, or even consider the space of

transformations as a space of activations where each transformation shares its own mini manifold in which we can compare curvature. But this is not ideal and goes against the idea of this architecture.

Ultimately, the objective is to have a signature for each transformation, which we want to express in graph form but currently, we must think of these transformations similarly to what modern Hopfield networks represent for attention [42]: the attention mechanism of transformers is actually a retrieval problem where Keys and Queries form a dynamic memory where keys represent the latent space of this memory and queries allow fetching information from this memory. This actually partially solves the problem of invariants since a token representing an oriented feature, will logically be oriented similarly in memory. Of course the network must still be trained by data augmentation to handle these cases, and in the end the network learns invariants rather than orienting in the same direction, but the underlying idea remains.

Here the transformations form the fixed memory on which we come to search for information. This information is not a value to compare directly but the transformation directly. And the input allows retrieving the right transformation. This has a deep connection with the notion of library of axioms, of hypergraph transformations, and that generalization can be formulated as a retrieval problem on known and correctly memorized facts. We can even push the reflection further and say that the only thing that is generalized is the capacity to correctly retrieve learned information. What we optimize is what allows retrieval and the organization of memorized information. The organization of space furthermore allows passage from one type to another which requires truncating the latter. It is in this that the generalization of experiences occurs: being able to extract decontextualized information from the initial experience.

In other words, even if counter-intuitive, in our architecture memorization is favored, desired and determining. We must be able at any time to find the initial experience that allowed generalizing knowledge because it is this experience and how they are arranged with respect to others that has all the importance of generalization. We push for generalization to crystallize in key memorizations. Obviously, the role of nodes is to compress this information progressively, but from the point of view of the architecture we can mix information from a local latent space or from a discrete point since for the architecture both are the same thing.

Still, learning can be optimized afterwards (which is normally the role of hierarchical layers) to define upstream the optimal position of nodes and links between these nodes (direct and indirect links) to minimize the number of operations necessary for the discrimination of paths. In other words, optimize the location of reference transformations that we consider valid for the token. In this way we can pre-calculate the compositions of transformations on paths (the integral on the path in question), calculate them in parallel, then take a node use it as reference, recalculate the links between nodes, and so on but the space is organized such that the number of iterations is minimal.

What must also be taken into account is that the first calculation phase is the same regardless of tokens, and that the only thing to recalculate is the tokens at the junctions that we can also sample with the composition of transformations on this path approximated by a single transformation upstream.

In general for inference, we can optimize the space afterwards to minimize the number of operations to do and therefore be able to match the number of operations done in a transformer.

During training, the paradigm is different, because we already have access to the valid path. What we are trying to do is create links between paths and the target path, with periodically a real run to determine the predicted path and compare it to the target.

3.7.3 Intra token relations

As previously discussed, the transformation space represents the superposition of all manifolds associated with each type and their transitions from one to another. Fundamentally, what we

want to achieve is a graph where each node has its own latent space representing the manifold associated with types. Then, between each type, we attempt to find transformations to transition from one to another. However, this approach is complex to implement since it is not the data that takes the form of a graph but the model itself. Moreover, this assumes a hard selection when adding or removing nodes. Additionally, since the objective is also to exhaustively search for relations, we end up with a geometric space dictated by these transformations.

Furthermore, each type, which can be represented by a simple projection layer onto its local manifold, can also be decomposed into elements that are themselves interconnected and form the latent space of the type.

Therefore, it is simpler to directly associate each node with a position in a latent space, and it is also easier to represent everything in the same space, albeit with important nuances.

Here, we can view the transformation space, where each node has a position in the manifold, as the absolute position of each type relative to others. This space represents the set of all types and all transitions between types, localized in a manifold of maximum dimension d . However, each part of this space can be softly segmented into types that locally have their own structure, their own manifold. Therefore, ensuring that an element belongs to a type means projecting it onto this local manifold and observing its trajectory/curvature. With an important subtlety here: we project the data onto all the basic elements of the type in question. Indeed, we can decompose each type into several central points, several central regions, within which we can navigate freely to move from one element to another, but not necessarily from one region to another. We can certainly learn a projection that will determine the best region likely to correspond to the data, but fundamentally what we do is test multiple positions and, based on whether their trajectories are smooth or not, we determine that the data, or at least a portion of it, can be cast into this type.

We repeat this process for all types of the same complexity (e.g., in programming, this amounts to taking an input sequence in bytes and attempting to cast each basic type boolean, integer, long onto this sequence by searching for potential positions). For the same input, we then choose types of the same complexity having the smoothest local trajectories before moving on to types of greater complexity, composed of these subtypes.

In other words, even if we project (either the data or the activation values of the transformation as the data passes through), this does not result in a unique projection.

However, working in high dimensions to study trajectories remains a problem. This is why what we study is not the trajectory in the transformation space, but the trajectories in the local spaces of each type, which are forced into low dimensions. In other words, for an input token, the manifold on which we track the input's trajectory is dynamically created to represent only the manifold of that input, which is forced into low dimensions. To illustrate, the transformation space can be compared to a 2D holographic material capturing a 3D image, which, under the impulse of a laser and depending on the given direction, projects this 3D image in a simpler, more usable form as it represents only a single view.

There are different ways to formalize this:

- Consider the transformation space as the global manifold
- Use pre-weighting on transformations to determine the low-dimensional sub-direction to follow in the transformation space, ensuring that along the chosen path we remain on the same subspace
- Define on-the-fly a projection on the output of transformations while ensuring the creation of smooth trajectories

Regardless of the chosen method, this relies on the fact that once we choose a path, we define a certain projection in which, by construction, this trajectory is optimal. We then compare it with

other trajectories to see if this projection also allows smooth trajectories for other transformation paths. Paths with smooth trajectories in this projection belong to the same manifold or region of the manifold, while those with rough trajectories belong to another manifold or region of the manifold, for which we can find a projection that makes them smooth, thereby defining another local manifold.

Next, we must determine whether a transformation exists between the found manifolds to evaluate the cost of this transformation/deformation.

The idea remains to compare trajectories with each other to project only the differences, which should be expressible in low dimensions for those sharing the same manifold, and in other (low) dimensions for those that cannot be expressed as such.

In other words, we never compare the trajectory in its absolute/global dimension. This has the advantage of being feasible at inference time. During training, we also do not need to manipulate the absolute space, but only modify it relative to a subspace at all times. The absolute space itself emerges implicitly.

However, the question of the dimension of this space remains. There are three possibilities:

- Either we define a maximum dimension representing a hard limit on the organizational capacity of the space, which for each forward pass will only be exploited in pieces
- Or we define the space directly in low dimensions using trilateration to emulate a higher-dimensional space. This has the advantage of being able to "simply" extend the space horizontally to add dimensions to the implicit absolute space
- Or we define hierarchical layers that will serve to localize manifolds relative to each other in a low-dimensional space, since they rely on the layer below representing only the superposition of local manifolds, and the upper layer can map each manifold to a low-dimensional point to define a new manifold that represents the relative positions of local manifolds to each other

Each possibility is actually a trade-off on information sharing. In the initial transformation space, there are all possible transformations on the continuous space, but we choose which trajectories to compute. For two disjoint and distant trajectories, it is possible to synchronize via their position in the absolute space and thereby share information between them, not directly, but by influencing the path chosen at the next step, and thus the transformation to be performed.

More concretely, the chosen path depends on the chosen transformation, which in turn depends in one way or another on the data. On the other hand, in the standard attention of transformers, each head is concatenated and then passed through an FFN whose output size is the size of a single token. In our space, transformations map a token of size p to an output token of identical size. And from any input token of size p , we can find a transformation that produces the same result as an FFN that would have k tokens of size d as input. Therefore, if two distinct trajectories corresponding to 2 transformations (to 2 attention heads) produce smooth trajectories on the shared projection, then the choice of the next transformation for both paths will be the one that is in the mutual continuity of these smooth trajectories. In other words, the two trajectories mutually influence each other to select the next transformation via their position in the absolute space, which is indirectly linked to the token values and accessible because we locally take the gradient on this space to compute the next step. This transformation can then be learned to correspond to the output value of an FFN with these two attention heads as input and produce a mixing of these two tokens.

This mechanism is therefore directly dependent on the dimension of this space: a space in too low a dimension will create a bottleneck for information transmitted between two tokens, and thus will constrain the mixing. But a space in too high a dimension is more complex to manage.

Each of the previous possibilities trades off either the complexity of managing trajectories in high dimensions or the amount of transmissible information and thus the quality of token mixing.

In this architecture, attention is implicitly formulated and executed by the geometry of the space itself. We can also resort to SSM-type attention locally for intra-token, but this remains more difficult to integrate into the continuous space, since attention itself and its functioning must be formulated in the same format as transformations and paths.

An architecture exclusively in low dimensions is possible; simply the mechanism for communicating positions must be adapted via trilateration, where each local manifold can express distant coordinates in another manifold via trilateration. We lose the manifold’s curvature but gain a notion of absolute position, to which we can add a notion of complexity score for each position. In sum, we locally construct for each node a compressed representation of the regions of interest of other accessible nodes, more aligned with predictive coding. This local representation of the absolute space can also translate into direct links between nodes that compress into a transformation the global curvature of the represented path.

These remain additional architectural choices that are more complex to implement.

At this stage, it is legitimate to use the transformation space rather than the value space directly, since in any case we end up doing a projection. Nevertheless, the transformation space is more suitable for what follows: correspondence with hypergraph transformations.

This dynamic geometry is far from trivial, as it has an intrinsic relationship with how data is processed: via hypergraph transformations. The trajectory taken by the input data on the manifold should be seen as the identification of successive transformation rules. The topology and geometry formed by the causality of these transformation rules constitute the very surface of the manifold on which the data navigates. A non-locally optimal trajectory represents the matching score of hypergraph transformation rules. The length of the transformation sequence has no effect in itself; only that a longer sequence is more likely to accumulate small local matching errors that will ultimately produce too high a mismatch score.

As for the projection of input data onto this manifold, it must be treated with particular attention. Indeed, a token that would be directly projected onto the manifold (after embeddings) is immediately associated with a complete graph. This is conceptually problematic since it means that among all types of similar complexity, we choose only one from the outset. In principle, the entire input is directly projected and the manifold compensates for this choice through high dimensionality. This is equivalent to the trajectory of transformations taken by an input in an MLP. From an expressivity and computability standpoint, fully projecting the input onto the manifold in high dimension is not a problem. Nevertheless, from a structural standpoint, we lose their explicit definition.

In themselves, types are merely sections of the manifold that have their own local geometry, which is therefore approximable by a high-dimensional manifold. However, this makes it more complex to determine the topology of the space, the hypergraph rules, the attention for pattern matching of hypergraph transformation rules, and the local modification of the manifold, the ability to shift from one manifold to another for meta-learning, and the ability to isolate modules/types to explicitly determine their functioning.

The advantage of this architecture is being able to project tokens in very low dimension (lower than the embeddings of an input token). Because a token represents a data sequence that we seek to cast onto types to determine which type best represents this data. In other words, for the same token it can be decomposed into several simple types that do not overlap (the same portion of the input cannot be several types at once). In other words, for an input token, we use only a sparse representation of this token at each transformation, enabling projection in very low dimensions.

Note that the complexity of a type can also be determined by its topology+geometry (the more holes there are, and the more deformed the geometry, the more complex the type).

The synchronization of these different representations/facets of the same token occurs through implicit common agreement. This means that given a token, we have several possible starting points (at minimum one per type of equivalent complexity, and within the same type there can also be several starting points, on sections of the manifold that do not necessarily communicate, or too little).

In other words, this projection cannot be unique and one-shot at the beginning of the forward pass. What comes closest to what we seek are models that perform diffusion processes on the latent token to bring the noised token back onto the manifold; since in a way, at the start, the token's position is random and we adjust progressively as if testing all positions at once.

We seek here a similar functioning where we don't know the correct projection of the input, nor the correct manifold (the correct type) on which the trajectory integrates. In other words, at the start, we begin with all possible manifolds as well as all possible projections. At the end of the diffusion process, we will have determined the correct projection to use as well as the correct manifold to use, along with the trajectory.

This diffusion process is possible because it adopts a similar functioning to one where we have a discrete family of manifolds, with their associated projections. By projecting the input token onto each manifold and studying the curvature of the trajectory, we can then determine on which manifolds the input projects best and use this as decomposition for the rest.

In this configuration, between each type we also know the transformation between them in order to verify the validity of the projection: since we know how to go from one to another, we can perform this transformation and verify either the obtained trajectories which should be the same, or the values in projection in the input space.

Our architecture adopts this principle but extends it to a continuous space. This continuous space allows, among other things, to choose the direction in which to go to minimize curvature on the types. In other words, for a given input, we seek the family of manifolds that will perfectly represent the input (define a geodesic on the relevant types).

Then, when we move to types of higher complexity, we will be constrained by the manifold defining the passage to these types since the types used at the next "layer" may be locally optimal but by accumulating layers this will no longer be the case because we should consider the transformation trajectory from one manifold to another according to the direction of complexity.

This gives an optimization objective decomposable by complexity but also the possibility of defining each "layer" as an optimal solution and using the passage trajectory between "layers" as defining a geodesic. From this information, we can ask what global space would be needed for this trajectory to be correct.

These are two possible interpretations that demonstrate the philosophy of this architecture: in the current data universe, we have a defined manifold that dictates valid transformations through its geometry, but we can temporarily break free from it to entirely change the universe.

Moreover, this test-everything for the projection of the input token is closely related to the probabilist view point. The trajectory itself is not probabilistic, but the projection of the input token into the manifold is, since we try to determine the start position within the whole manifold. Though probabilities are tied to the coherence validation process. This implies that we can in principle apply the Fisher natural gradient to align trajectories, even if not mandatory.

We can then define the architecture as a slightly modified graphon to represent an extended Morse diagram (not only at critical points but to represent a discretization of the manifold) [43] [44] where each node has an index K , and on each edge, the gradient or tangent plane between these two points. We can also include a distance on each edge.

This representation has the advantage of being able to identify and define the topology as well as the geometry. Even though to recover the entirety of the geometry, we must define the gluing points in the dimension of the manifold.

But this representation aligns with hypergraph transformation which abstracts from positions in space, and in this way, the very geometry of space defines the possible hypergraph transformations. On the other hand, this lends itself well to diffusion where for a given input, we can test all manifolds at once via this diffusion process. What should be adjoined to the graphon is an FFN that represents the projection function. Each graphon is associated with an input- \mathcal{L} -position projection layer on the manifold. But this projection is not explicitly defined. Indeed, the diffusion process tests all positions, on all possible manifolds. Therefore the projection is naturally defined by gradient. And as seen previously, once a projection is defined, we can deduce the others, at least in part.

This projection will also allow us to implicitly define the metric of the associated manifold (via a pullback metric) [45], which saves us from having to define it explicitly. This metric can then emerge from the geometry of the manifold, notably because we define the manifold in an ambient Euclidean space of higher dimension. Thus, we can also calculate the Riemannian distance since we have access to the gradient at each point of the manifold, hence to the tangent planes (which is subject to the quality of approximation and discretization). Or approximate it with the chordal distance.

In all cases, the geometry of the manifold remains defined in an ambient Euclidean space. We could directly generate the geometry in the space of the manifold with the intrinsic metric, but this is problematic for information compression (which nevertheless has the advantage of storing everything explicitly), and for adding/removing nodes. In our architecture, since each node has an assigned position in the ambient space, adding/removing a node only amounts to adding a new transition between nodes, for the same position but with different/conflicting gradients (hence geometry). During training, the weight attributed to one of the two will be progressively decreased and we can prune it without impacting the system (which de facto functions on discrete elements that together form a continuity). On the other hand, over time, locally, we can penalize conflicting representations by analyzing the geometry at this point to determine contradictory gradients, and thus accelerate pruning.

We could have explicitly defined this geometry via a Vietoris-Rips complex mesh determined by the data, then by simplicial wavelets (multi-scale) [46] as representation of this geometry instead of hypergraphs. This is also valid for training a model from scratch to respect a geometry from its properties via wavelets. However, this makes the link with hypergraph transformations more unstable and complex, since we add an intermediary between geometry and hypergraphs that only perceive geometry through this wavelet/processed properties prism. Instead of directly defining the geometry.

On the other hand, in intrinsic geometry, adding/removing nodes would be more complex and unstable because we no longer define the geometry from the outside which offered this flexibility.

Note that in this configuration, the FFNs linked to each node process the graphons, and as denoising progresses, the input token that passes through the projection FFN actually undergoes cumulative transformations (due to the fact that at each diffusion step the FFN changes). In other words, at the end of denoising, we will have obtained the manifold associated with the input feature (as if the input had passed through an encoder).

What remains to be determined is the exact gluing of the graphon nodes in their (recall, low) dimension. But in fact, this is the whole point of this representation. First, to be able to use it to have an approximate view where we can choose the discretization, and if we want to focus on geometry or topology to isolate this graphon, and train a small model on it to study it under different conditions. In sum, this graphon can be considered as the functor from which in few-shot we can determine the exact geometry. This is because a data point will represent a complete trajectory, so we seek the representation of this manifold that minimizes fine-tuning regardless of the values. Which we can augment by simulating a few trajectories on the true manifold and

replacing these values with other random ones while simply ensuring we respect the same path equivalence.

And secondly, we can train the model to function and navigate on this representation, internally interpreting the gluings through the trajectory of the input token that it will generate and the common agreement with path equivalence. This is also why we don't simply project the token onto the manifold at the beginning but have access to it at each step via the projection FFN (which corresponds to an implicit back and forth mapping). Without this, by projecting and only following the path on the Morse diagram, we would lose information that we could no longer exploit afterwards.

This equivalence that seems profound to us between hypergraph transformation and manifold is both intended to attempt to replace the calculation of curvature by a matching score on transformation rules. And because in hierarchical layers what we want to see emerge is a graphon representing a flat manifold corresponding then to a simple discrete hypergraph close to CT where we only compose pseudo-discretely categories among themselves. While being able to progressively evolve as knowledge grows by simply evolving the geometry between these nodes (which simply corresponds to changing the gradient on the edges, and the index of nodes). This allows a progressive/continuous transition between discrete hypergraph and manifold.

3.7.4 Inter token relations

Theoretically, from the very first token, there exists a path whose transformation includes all the necessary transformations to produce an output that takes into account all input tokens. It is then a matter of finding which path, applying the same principle as for intra-token: each token has its own associated type and we look for another type that allows the combination of all these types. On the same transformation space, we end up with a number of trajectories equal to: the number of tokens times the number of heads (which are trajectories).

In principle, this means that each token has access to all the heads of other tokens.

A simplified version of this process can be to decompose each path we explore by projecting it into a very low-dimensional manifold, with simple "curvatures" such as, for example, onto a hyperplane on which we try to accumulate as many successive points of the path as possible. Ensuring that the hyperplane contains more than $d-1$ points where d is the dimension of the space containing the hyperplane. When too many points deviate from the hyperplane, we define another one on the following segment and so on. Then, for each intersection, we calculate the deformation from one plane to another (here the angle between the two planes). We define the probabilities on the paths as those with the least cost defined by the length of each segment cumulated with the deformation cost.

We can then either consider that we only choose a path that already contains the desired final transformation, or that at each step the token we take as input is the linear combination of the sequence's tokens weighted by their scores along this segment.

3.7.5 Implementation

The notion of fiber over paths (path bundle/foliation structure) allows us here to map the trajectories that we consider as reference (and which de facto become geodesic) via a fiber onto the higher plane (itself a manifold). In other words, the manifolds are divided into a few reference paths which alone are mapped onto the higher plane, but the rest of the manifold is not. Nevertheless, we still consider the entirety of the manifold at our disposal. This manifold then serves as a reference to construct other manifolds by composition/shifting.

Indeed, for each plane representing manifolds of similar complexity (complex shape, numerous critical points, etc.), we project the input onto these reference manifolds, we follow the trajectory from the projected point given by the geometry of the manifold, then we project this trajectory via a fiber onto the higher plane. We can then observe a point similar (or almost) to that of the reference manifold, or a distant point indicating a divergence. In this case, the path (on the higher plane manifold where the fibers are projected) between the two points gives us the way to compose the reference manifolds of the lower plane with each other.

In other words, even if we only project a few critical trajectories onto the higher plane, having preserved the entire manifold allows us to know how to modify it by observing the modification of critical trajectories and composition with other manifolds.

This composition is then continuous, and the gradient along the path of the higher plane indicates how to compose the reference manifolds which are in finite/discrete number.

The manifold itself can be represented in two ways: either via its critical points and the curvature between them, or via its simplicial complex. In the second case, each node has a gradient that defines what the lengths of each edge are, as well as a scalar that defines the scale to apply to this gradient. The transitions between nodes then represent local links (orientation, distance, etc.). But we can also associate an absolute position in the ambient Euclidean space via an embedding. In all cases, the gluing is done dynamically, considering locally the gluing from links and lengths.

This solution allows nodes to be added or removed on the fly, since we can then maintain different concurrent representations of the manifold/of different manifolds. When considering the input, each transition has an associated weight that evolves dynamically according to the input and allows certain nodes/simplices to be included or not.

Nevertheless, this last approach can prove costly in computation for a still uncertain gain. Indeed, it is generally more expensive to maintain a simplicial complex representation of a manifold than to simply consider the underlying point cloud (cleaning duplicate points/points that do not provide useful information for reconstruction) and then reconstruct the simplicial complex. This is therefore the approach we will follow for now, which integrates more easily with the hypergraph representation. Because in the other case, the simplicial complex must be passed through an intermediate layer that extracts the critical points and allows construction of the manifold graph.

In principle, we should be able to do without the definition of geodesic curve, since each trajectory of the inputs serves as a reference. And what we will require in training is that the number of transformations/steps in the trajectory be minimal for the reference trajectories (so that their computation is as fast as possible). Defining a trajectory with a minimal number of steps means discretizing this trajectory and therefore assuming that it behaves simply between each point. To allow this phenomenon, we can discretize at different locations each time. We then end up with smooth trajectories defined implicitly.

On the other hand, the projection via fibers onto the higher plane implicitly includes this notion of difference in curvature between two trajectories. And, since the reference trajectories are by construction the geodesics (whatever their current length and curvature), calculating the curvature of another trajectory is simpler because it suffices to calculate the deviation from the geodesic, which we can also approximate piecewise and therefore calculate in parallel.

The representation of the manifold as a graph of critical points also has the advantage of simplifying the exploration and guidance of an input's trajectory, since we no longer need to estimate the distance between two points or what it would cost to take such or such trajectory—it is given by the graph where each transition gives the distance and/or the gradient/tangent vector. Each plane being a manifold, each plane has its own graph representation, and since each plane represents increasingly complex types, we can from any plane estimate and have a short/medium/long term view of each trajectory from the start. In other words, the estimation of space is included in the very representation of this space by construction. This allows us not to define a separate model that will estimate the cost of each trajectory to take.

Regarding the different planes, there are different possible approaches. Either we define that each plane includes a loss of information (projection being a loss of information), in which case, the higher we go in the planes, the more the projection stabilizes on a single point representing the universe. This defines the coherence point of the entire universe. Indeed, since each plane depends on the next to define its coherence—namely which trajectory to follow in the manifold once different projected trajectories forming the beginning of this trajectory—there must come a moment when all trajectories stabilize in a single projection, which allows solving the circularity problem of this definition of coherence.

But this stable state can be defined in different ways. Another possibility is to consider that each plane must define an increasingly simple geometry (which is not necessarily induced by information loss). In other words, fewer critical points, geometries with central trajectories that allow few deviations, or even only trajectories in the form of straight lines in Euclidean space, etc.

But we can also consider that at the plane we define as the universe plane, we no longer project trajectories but only the points of the manifold. In this case, as long as the trajectory remains on the manifold, whatever its curvature, whatever it does, it remains on the universe point. This assumes that the lower planes define sufficiently constraining geometries to not allow anything.

In all cases, we are not constrained to remain on the universe point; the input can from the first plane project onto a different universe. Indeed, if the trajectory is sufficiently different, the combination of manifolds that we will create so that this trajectory is considered geodesic in a manifold by projection onto the higher plane, can lead by cascade effect to paths on the higher planes of the same kind, which will in turn propagate until the final point/final trajectory is not projectable onto the universe point, and therefore we must shift the entire universe.

It should also be noted that each plane defines a probability distribution over possible paths, whose role of the lower planes is to collapse by using the details of the inputs at their disposal to constrain these probabilities. In other words, we can not finish a calculation and be content with a zone (defining several paths) probable enough to use it to define a response without ensuring that the details of the lower planes match. In this case, in the lower planes, we work with superpositions of paths or averages trying to take the path that corresponds best/the most without leaving the manifold. In other words, this corresponds to having a vague idea that infuses a sentence, but this sentence remains grammatically correct, despite the fact that the idea is vague. Here it is similar, since we must respect the geometry of the manifold in the lower planes, but simply more trajectories meet the criteria of the higher plane. We therefore relax the collapse on distributions.

In practice, we can begin this implementation with a GNN where each node has its own sequence, and which is connected to its neighbors or more with features on each transition. This initial (fixed) graph actually represents the set of all possible manifolds of all collapsed planes. The role of the GNN transformer conditioned on the embedding of the input will be to perform this mechanism of manifold separation. For each transition, we evolve its feature (which will represent the gradient of the Morse graph), weight of this transition to determine whether we take it into account or not, as well as the node features (which will represent the information of the Morse graph). We can consider the initial state as the noisy state but where we have all possible transformations, and the diffusion process will be to select the right ones, but therefore at each noise level (even one timestep after noise), this actually represents the different layers of complexity of the types we apply. At the end of the process, we obtain not simply the manifolds of simple types that correspond to the input but the final result directly.

A simplified architecture is to decompose the hierarchical diffusion process into different layers. At each layer, we have N manifolds with their own projection FFN. Each manifold has an embedding that corresponds to an embedding manifold of this layer. This embedding manifold allows

establishing relations between different types, how to pass from one to another/how to deform one into another.

Each embedding associated with a manifold corresponds to the projection of geodesics in the fibration (path bundle) and the embedding manifold therefore corresponds to this fibration.

The objective with this fragmented representation is to be able to keep the dimension of each embedding in very low dimension (around 10) regardless of the dimension of the input token. In practice, each token is projected into this low dimension on each type; in other words, each type corresponds only to a subspace of the total space/to a section of this space.

Indeed, if we represent the total space, comprising all types, their relations, universes, etc. as described in hypergraph transformations, what we actually learn is the slices of this hypergraph which projection after projection gives rise to the input space in very low dimension. Here, we cheat by directly representing each as a low-dimensional subspace, and the fibration allows defining an order between these different subspaces.

If we represent a manifold/type as being a node of a graph, with different transitions representing links, these same transitions will be aligned with the subspace, thus will represent a slice of the total dimension. This poses a problem for the trajectory, because it becomes difficult to know which path to follow, since this implies passing from one section to another, on different dimensions. Which in itself is not problematic if the transition is continuous, but in practice poses a problem for learning with transitions spreading with a small remainder over several dimensions.

In the hypergraph transformation theory, what we learn is the universe, but according to the perspective of the observer who is themselves in this universe but perceives it only through these universe slices/projections.

Each layer in this architecture represents a more complex type, composed of subtypes. From a HoTT/cohesive HoTT point of view, this is the attempt to learn a geometry of the space of types 0. Which we can then extend to types 1, etc. But if we only consider type 0 to begin, the current observer's universe is a point in type 1.

Thus, for a given token, we project it onto the N manifolds of layer N, we project via fibration the path of the token projected onto a manifold that we follow for a few timesteps, this gives a point on the embedding manifold, in principle the same if the trajectory is geodesic, otherwise different, which indicates a mismatch. However, if we use embeddings and not a real transformation attached to each manifold, this projection is implicit, since we already know the geodesics of the manifold by construction and its static projection via the embedding. From then on, any deviation allows calculating the projection from that of the embedding.

By doing this on enough manifolds, we can triangulate the manifold where the input token's trajectory is geodesic.

Among these N manifolds, we select k projected points on the embedding manifold that form the most geodesic trajectory possible and which represents the "voting"/agreement on projections and types. This trajectory then forms a point on the embedding manifold of layer N+1, and we can geometrically mix tokens with each other from their proximity/order in the trajectory.

Regarding token sequences, we process each layer N in parallel and mixing is done via the embedding manifold as well.

What must be understood is the projection process which is in fact absolutely central since it determines in a deterministic manner the entire continuation of the transformation until the final result. In other words, the initial step plays a far too important role.

First, the projected point will not be on the manifold except to calculate on which tangent plane the point in the ambient space is located so that this projection is directly on the manifold without using a denoiser at this stage. What we can do here, but a projection that is not on the manifold is fundamentally biased, even if we find its closest point on the manifold, it remains a guess.

The only manifold whose projection is guaranteed is that of embeddings at each layer by the very construction of the manifold.

For other manifolds, their projection is actually free, and is only a probability distribution on its position on each manifold. The only thing we must respect is once we determine that the token projects to this point on a manifold, to ensure the coherence of projection on other manifolds via the transformations provided by the embedding manifold. Indeed, without constraint each manifold can always project to the ideal point, and follow this same trajectory. Here, there must be an agreement via the inter-manifold structure.

We will not be able to constrain all projections from a single one, otherwise this means that all types of the layer are equivalent, which is not of interest. We will have clusters where inside we can guarantee projection but not with respect to other type clusters. This verification will be done in the types of the next layer which encodes relations between these types.

In practice, if we represent a type as a class, layer 0 ensures casting the right part of inputs onto the right potential base types, layer 1 takes care of casting onto types where each attribute (a type from layer 0) has a specific relation with others, and so on. The path represents the relation. And we can have several disjoint paths, which will be assembled on the higher space.

In this interpretation, inter-token and intra-token attention actually simply corresponds to fetching the information that each type needs to match the structure of the type in question. In other words, each type can be a linear combination of tokens with dynamic weights that evolve during forward pass within the same layer according to agreement between types via their transformation paths. And at each layer, we then have the information already used to cast types, and the information not yet used to cast them—this would be the equivalent of the residual stream.

On the other hand, this means that regardless of the attention mechanism, this does not exclude the geometric interpretation, and this is not done outside the geometric structure either.

In fact, without this representation via projection (which is an organization of the total space), we have a total space in high dimension where each token has its own trajectory and attention amounts to determining on which subspace/which section of this space the trajectory evolves. Because the trajectory does not evolve on all dimensions at the same time. Then once this section/this plane is determined, we can assign coefficients according to the deviation. For the same token, multi-head attention represents at each timestep the different accessible sections.

In other words, in the case of a total space, it is the planes that are dynamic and no longer fixed.

This organization into types seems important to us for the many properties mentioned earlier. And allows focusing locally on the structure of manifolds. For example, in simple types of type 0, we can have monoids, fields, rings, which using several Cayley representations for example gives us a geometric structure by extension. In other words, roughly, we can use the same structure for discrete types, and at the limit for continuous types via Cayley and Morse which represent the structure of the type, its generators, and their links.

Moreover, in the case of Cayley graphs, we can use k -simplices (via classifying space BG) to represent relations between discrete elements, just as we can use these simplices to represent hyperedges of hypergraphs. The only drawback here is that a k -simplex by definition defines all faces, whereas in a hyperedge, defining a relation between three vertices does not mean that binary representations exist. What we then observe is simply the hypergraph with binarized edges which at the limit is valid.

This is one of the challenges with simplex representation, particularly for discrete cases with Cayley, since one simplex too many can define a relation that changes the entire structure of the group and therefore its properties.

What we can then do from this graph is determine the atomic simplices and transformation rules that allow constructing this space. Moreover, the trajectory of a token on a manifold is not

the movement of this token, but the movement of the persistent hypergraph pattern. This means that a token trajectory, and a fortiori a geodesic, already allows identifying hypergraph rules in this space.

What is more delicate are the manifolds of function types of type 0 ($f : A \times B \rightarrow C$). Because the structure of the manifold does not inform about the computation that the function performs. For example, $f_1 : (a, b) \mapsto a^2 + b \in C$ and $f_2 : (a, b) \mapsto a + b \in C$ will be two points of the type of f but actually represent very different transformations. Yet these function types are what constitutes the core of the model's transformations.

To address this problem, for each point we can associate an FFN that represents the function's computation and is therefore usable, and the links between points indicate how to pass from one function to another of the same type. We can also consider the manifold where transformations are an integral part of the space, but this may drown the information of relations, since formerly a single point is replaced by hundreds of others and "intra-point" relations that do not necessarily need to exist. Obviously, associating with each point an FFN and transitions between points as transformations amounts essentially to the same thing, but can allow offering a dissociation between topology and geometry.

Indeed, in this architecture, geometry/distances between points/curvature of space is very secondary. It actually represents optimal paths in cohesive HoTT, and in our model represents preferences for one proof rather than another. In other words, preference in possible responses. But at no point should this geometry be used to define the validity of a trajectory. The only thing that must define the validity of a path is the topology of the space (the number of holes, the number of connected components, etc.). The number of connected components allows defining an impossibility of equality between elements of a type, and between types. And the number of holes indirectly allows invalidating paths by contradiction (via homotopic paths/that can be deformed from one to another).

What we primarily seek to define is therefore this topology, and it is this same topology that actually allows defining the function of a NN and retraining it from scratch without data, simply by pre-training it to form this topology, whose real data in fine-tuning allow defining the associated geometry. We can also include in this topology some information about geometry to facilitate fine-tuning and minimize necessary examples, or determine critical examples (those that allow deciding between several geometries).

If we return to the example of the type of f , what we can construct without geometry is ultimately the graph of all possible transformations. And by computability, certain functions will naturally be distant because too different to be transformed in one transition. For example, passing from $x \mapsto 2x$ to $x \mapsto \exp(x)$ requires several FFNs. In other words, in this type, we naturally have a notion of distance, and if we use simplices we actually realize the combination of different FFNs instead of doing it sequentially where information can become unusable/gradient vanishing.

We can then almost on this basis establish generators of the function space, and a topology.

What geometry brings at that point is the choice of generators because certain transformations are preferred/more common than others and must therefore be faster.

Implicitly, geometry has an effect on the organization of these transformations because by indicating what should be most accessible, this redefines the way of storing. But topology, regardless of the choice of generators, does not change the topology.

We can also define this function type f in the form of a Laplace transform which then gives us the generators and transitions between different points are the coefficients to reconstruct the function (its asymptotic behavior).

Topology is essential because in reality it forces the model to learn by self-coherence only. In the end, regardless of the $(input, output)$ value pair, the internal topology establishes equalities between different values and therefore a multitude of possible paths. For an $(input, output)$ pair,

what we can deduce is on the internal manifold the a priori shortest path. From this path, and others that we think equivalent according to the internal model, we must find paths that create incoherences in the system, contradictions.

However, separating topology and geometry in an incremental and continuous learning context proves challenging. First because if we start with a presumed continuous space, the curvature of space at certain places can indicate a hole or a connected component when this curvature becomes infinite/the gradient magnitude at this level becomes too large and must be clipped. Which in itself in our architecture only represents a coefficient between nodes close to 0. We do not actually do hard removal; even connected components preserve this link in the idea that in case of evolution it is simply enough to increase the coefficient.

On the other hand, input data also gives an indication of a priori valid frequent paths that we can use as reference to construct contradictions. And, we can observe trajectories avoiding certain region in the internal model which could reveal holes. The idea is to use statistical information to build a possible topology that the model try to confirms though testing. If adding a hole does not seem to forbid the known value to be right, and with new data neither (because we find alternative paths), then it might be valid.

Combining both, we can develop a strategy to construct this topology, assuming different topologies that we maintain in parallel and whose effects we observe on very frequent paths. This is the idea behind this notion of universe, which for example can in a vector define the low-frequency modes of the Laplacian that estimates the topology without having seen it entirely. In this way, we can actually change the topology as we go by observation without locally changing geometries (high frequencies will remain roughly the same). Values will change but these changes will remain coherent with each other (we simply change generator representation), and these generators are already present in the old geometry; we simply choose a new node as reference, which through forward passes will naturally adapt local geometry to this new storage organization.

In practice, this is similar to defining a neural memory with N vectors. Then defining a new layer with N new vectors that are linear combinations of the layer below. The transition between the two layers is immediate.

The space of functions (the types of functions on elements of type 0, themselves elements of type 0) are in reality the core of transformations: they are the ones that represent most of the transformations necessary for learning. This space presents itself in the form of disconnected clusters where each represents a linear combination of asymptotic modes (functions described by their asymptotic behavior via tetration, fast-growing hierarchy, etc.). In this way, one can define upstream the maximum number of modes (the modes represented in the form of FFN). Then these clusters represent a subspace of these modes (a set of coefficients, different from one cluster to another) and which all present at minimum a hole at the central point (e.g. (0, 0)). Since this represents the boundary between different clusters (e.g. $a^2 \in \{a^2\}$ but also $a^2 = a^2 + 0 \times a^3 \in \{a^2, a^3\}$). These regions of space are disjoint but there exists a path at the limit.

In a global space where all types exist at the same level, we find ourselves in a configuration similar to Kolmogorov network. The functions represent the modes that define the topology and the coefficients represent the geometry of space.

To this must be locally added the exclusions of certain elements/regions which also change the topology.

What is missing here is the configuration in types of this space. But in reality each type of function will share the same space of functions, we simply limit their fields of action, and change the generators (as a combination of already present modes) to respect the relations between types. It is in fact these types that allow to naturally include geometric attention in the system, since they are what create the necessary friction to constrain the system. In this situation, each space of types is shaped so that a few typologies of trajectories are considered coherent. In other words, at the entrance of each type, the type itself seeks the right combination of input variables so that

the trajectories are stable within it. Indirectly, self attention in the global space serves the same function.

Fundamentally, what is missing from current NNs are the constraints of the system itself, namely that when we update the landscape to favor a trajectory, we indirectly adjust others that were perhaps correlated. This justifies in fact the important quantity of data necessary and the number of epochs, since we replace this lack of constraint by repetition and small successive adjustments.

Regularization (of weights/replay learning/etc.), momentum, batches, are all techniques that attempt to locally reintegrate constraints to compensate for the lack of local constraint.

And in fact, learning a manifold by pairs of points that describe the starting point and arrival point on the real manifold, still unknown, does exactly the same thing.

The idea of this architecture is to reintegrate global constraints by supposing different possible architectures and linking them to know that if the update of a path by learning requires decreasing the score of another and increasing that of a third, we can know that these last two paths are linked and treat them accordingly. There is naturally an explosion of information available, but the hypothesis is that the added constraints will allow to eliminate simultaneously several manifold architectures sufficiently to compensate for this explosion, and thus potentially allow learning with less data.

In itself, what the model learns is a structure at the limit, which allows limit links that only exist at the limit and which allows creating a hyperconnectivity of the network, where everything is globally connected. For a pair of data it is in fact the information that can be extracted from it at best, it is up to the model to segment this information afterwards and see if the architecture is compatible with the limit.

This is for example the case of discrete types that can be represented with atomic simplexes, but which by passing to the limit each face exists independently.

This limit representation is in fact advantageous because it allows the superposition of different architectures. And for example if locally a manifold explodes in gradient, this allows indicating a potential hole, but does not condemn the model to no longer being able to exit this configuration where information is saturated since it suffices to add a link at the same position with a different gradient and simply adjust the weights of the two architectures, to select the most advantageous and locally coherent one. This is moreover the first mode of learning, not to modify existing weights but to add some and to prune/compress afterwards.

In this architecture, we can represent each type (whether discrete groups, fields, functions, etc.) as a topological graph where each node represents the modes of this topology (e.g., generating element of the group, asymptotic mode of a function-type, etc.). To do this, we create upstream a basis of orthogonal modes (which can be represented by FNNs, polynomial functions like Legendre, B-splines in the case of univariate functions). Then each node of the graph uses a subset of these modes, which then defines the topology of this node, which we consider without connected components.

In practice, the type $f : A \times B \rightarrow C$ has an element for example in the form $(a, b) \mapsto a^2 + b^3 \in C$. But this function has the same internal topology as the function $(a, b) \mapsto (a + b)^2 + b^3$, yet the results outside asymptotic behavior are largely different. In other words, the type of f has many non-connected components, not counting the subtypes like $f : (A \setminus \{a1\}) \times B \rightarrow C$ which also have holes.

Thus, the simplest approach is to consider each non-connected component (and without holes, with flat topology) individually and to make the connection between subtypes a posteriori. This amounts to defining each node as a k -simplex with k being the number of modes of the defined space (see Figure 11). The lengths of the edges define the geometry of the space. This allows each type, even if theoretically part of the same type, to focus on a part of its parent type's space. And

this definition also allows directly comparing topologies with each other to identify contradictions on paths.

Figure 11: Schema of the modes simplex representation using simplex and flow lines

In reality, this architecture is very similar to that of transformers (see Figure 12), since we have two types of layers: those of types, those of functions that perform mappings between types (which is also a type but with a different meaning, even though the behavior with respect to other types is the same).

When we construct types as being defined by their modes, processing an input amounts to projecting the input onto the simplex, or using an FFN to extract the coefficients specific to each mode of the type in question. This then corresponds to the self-attention of transformers that decomposes each input into dynamic types. And the function layer actually represents the non-linear transformation, which performs a non-trivial mapping between product types.

From a geometric point of view, we could make an analogy with each type representing a chart and the functions being the coordinate change between charts, or the transport function.

Figure 12: Schema simple type and function types layer architecture

To go into more detail about this architecture (see Figure 13), we associate (ad-hoc) to each node a combination of at most k modes. Once the topology of a node is defined, it can no longer change. Only its geometry can. This corresponds to learning for each mode of the node's topology, coefficients (e.g., edge lengths of the simplex) to define a precise and restricted zone of the parent type that includes all nodes having the same modes. We do not perform mode combination (e.g., a vertex of the simplex becomes a linear combination of other modes). We could do this, and it's an option considered to facilitate the construction of more complex types, but this risks complicating the learning of the global topology.

Indeed, the dimension of the space is no longer governed by the dimension of the inputs, which can become arbitrarily large, but by the total number of modes of the global manifold. Given that we consider each node as a subset, the transport between 2 nodes must already take into account this torsion to navigate between different subspaces. Allowing each node to be a combination of other modes is practical in terms of computation and limits the number of edges to establish, but it complicates transport. On the other hand, a priori, we do not lose expressivity since functions take products of types (which will moreover be one of the mechanisms to allow grouping the non-connected components of the same type together via a hypernode).

The idea of this architecture is that we use triangulation to define new nodes with different topologies. Indeed, each node allows us to approximate the local behavior that we can use to interpolate the behavior in uncovered zones. When a path passes through one of these zones, we interpolate the transport function which does not simply average between nodes, but selects which modes to combine and which geometries to adopt.

This is why we can afford at initialization to fix the modes for each node, because the very principle of this architecture is interpolation to create new nodes with mixed topologies.

Figure 13: Illustration of the topological hypergraph network

We have two ways to implement transport: either by defining for each edge a transport function (an FFN) that will express each point of the path on the manifold between the two points. This is a valid solution but requires defining each point in the ambient space (thus with a vector of dimension equal to the total number of modes). This is feasible, provided we can maintain the total number of modes in low dimension (≤ 100). This would work for any dimension, but the principle of this architecture is to try to limit dimensions to facilitate interpretation, interpolation, and learning. In essence, what we're trying to do here is to flatten dimensions, replacing dimensional complexity with combinatorial complexity (with 15 nodes we can make $2^{20} \approx 10^6$ combinations per pair).

What must also be taken into account is that we want to avoid constructing degenerate nodes (which admit a mode with a coefficient of 0). We seek to construct a mixed complex, but where each k -simplex is atomic.

The other possible method to define transport is actually to only consider for each edge the intrinsic distance and the gradient at the vertices of the simplices. This allows defining a relation between two nodes with no nodes in common (thus that we cannot glue together), but which still have a link. We then consider the distance on this edge as being the shortest distance, and we define via the gradient all possible directions having this node as starting point, and the defined distance.

In other words, we don't really define the transformation between the two nodes, but we can describe the curvature. Indeed, as we abstract simplices by nodes, what is missing is their orientations and their gluing, yet it is at the level of gluing that we can establish curvature. Because if several nodes have the same distance, within a single node, the journey toward one or the other does not necessarily have the same curvature. At the scale of a node it's negligible, but by accumulating with all nodes, we are no longer able to define reliable distances, and thus to

orient the path search.

This problem is not limited simply to curvature, but to the impossibility for a non-trivial manifold to be represented in absolute coordinates in an ambient space that is too small (although we could consider a hyperbolic ambient space). For example, wormholes in 3D space are bridges between two distant points in space, which amounts to identifying two parts of space as being the same. But this link itself is topological. The choice of distance and gradient translates an attempt to reproduce this functioning where we simply observe the non-trivial manifold in restricted space, having the extrinsic knowledge of how regions of space are connected. This forms the topology of said space.

Regarding inputs, we project them individually into the type space, considering, as for a Fourier decomposition, that the token represents a temporal sequence. Thus, this allows aligning with the representation of Kolmogorov networks where mixing is done after functions. And this also aligns with Fnets [47] (Transformers using the Fourier transform instead of self-attention). In fact, by constructing the space in terms of modes, which can have different meanings for each typology of type (group, field, function, etc.), this allows us to distinguish two elements: the topology of inputs via modes, and the geometry via coefficients (as well as high frequencies on which we can be more flexible because they only have local behavior).

In other words, as the objective of this architecture is for a learned path to verify its internal coherence through topology, we can verify that the modes are the same. This also aligns with JEPA which seeks to obtain the same representation for different parts of the input. Here, we can penalize paths that have a different output in terms of topology (modes).

Moreover, as each node has a clearly identifiable topology, and via hypernodes that associate non-connected components, for the same path $(input, output)$, we can study the different paths that lead to the same result to ensure they are equivalent (in terms of being able to deform one into the other), and thus adjust the links between nodes, and therefore the topology of the space.

Transport between two nodes is an important aspect. Either we consider that each layer/FNN associated with each node is simply an extractor of the modes specific to this node, and thus simply a projection. In this case, the links between nodes indicate that there exists a possible transformation between the two, but do not specify it (the layer of the output node also only performs a projection according to its modes, thus not necessarily compatible with the other node at the end of the path).

The distance on each link, as well as the gradient on the vertices of the simplex, are only present to give a notion of density/distance function to find the most optimal/preferred path. The distance between nodes gives the distance globally, the gradient at nodes gives the distance locally.

Thus, the only way to reconstruct the transformation is to use the topology (topological neighbors), and to construct the transformation by mutual agreement between nodes and links.

This has the advantage of having to store much less information but requires dynamic reconstruction. Even though we can facilitate this reconstruction by including in the topology the resolution of ambiguous cases where it would be necessary to explore too large a part of the space to reconstruct the local topology (e.g., cycles).

The other approach is to explicitly define this transformation which then describes the path on the manifold. We insist that this transformation not be a simple jump between nodes, but that it indeed describe a landscape with points all along the path on the manifold.

The major disadvantage is that it is then necessary to synchronize each edge together so that they share a coherent view of trajectories: if two paths are supposed to intersect on the manifold, each transformation on the two edges (for which we don't automatically know that they intersect, see Figure 14) must be coherent and thus synchronized.

As raised previously, explicit transport between nodes is an additional aid but does not automatically make the geometry coherent; it simply allows expressing in terms of coordinates in the

ambient space the trajectory, which we can then more easily compare with other non-connected edges to estimate their links and synchronize them.

The disadvantage of synchronization is also the advantage of distributed and redundant information.

In practice, a transformation that only makes a jump between two nodes is closer to a coordinate change between charts. Which alone is difficult to use, but which when combined with topological links can be exploited. The same goes for a transformation whose transport is expressed as a path in ambient coordinates; without knowing the topological links, there are intersections or geometric contradictions. In other words, through knowledge of hyperedges that represent the topology of space, we are able to correctly interpret the non-trivial local geometry.

In fact, only with links and gradient at nodes, we can offline (without data) iterate on the topology to create and refine these transformations by exploring the topological space more and more. The idea is moreover to learn the topology that allows in a minimum of iterations to be able to find these transformations. The geometry should only intervene in a finetuning phase with data. What matters is the equivalence between paths, and the distance between two nodes can sometimes be interpreted as geometric distance or expressed in number of turns that allows identifying topological holes.

Figure 14: Illustration of node transport with an intersection

Moreover, as said previously, curvature is not an indicator of the validity of a path, but has an indirect influence. Indeed, naturally an edge with a high distance can represent a very chaotic curvature that a single transport FFN between the two nodes would not be able to correctly represent/memorize. Even if this chaotic path can a priori be valid, in practice it will probably be unusable. Although a large distance on a slightly curved path can be perfectly captured by the transformation. In other words, we can correlate curvature to the memorization capacity of the transformation.

Nevertheless, the topology itself can include information loss, for example with non-bijective functions, crushing the information. In other words, a very chaotic trajectory can be invalid because by passing several times through certain points, the model progressively loses information about the initial values until it can derive anything from them. This is the equivalent of passing back through the initial noise to find another trajectory in a diffusion model: we can obtain anything from anything.

A priori solution is to make transformations bijective/invertible, as in normalizing flow models. In reality, in our configuration, even a non-bijective transformation can be compatible with invertibility. Since one of the objectives of this architecture is ultimately to use a diffusion/flow model whose process represents the simultaneous exploration of all paths in parallel (via exploration by probability distribution). Thus, whether the application is bijective or not, for the same arrival point on the output set, we can individually explore each path that could have been mapped to this point. And we can maintain this exploration until the collapse of information where we end up choosing a unique path according to its probabilities which allows retroactively determining each step of the path.

In this first implementation, to simplify the architecture, we associate a coefficient linked to the information loss of transport (which represents the collapse rate of the transformation). Thus, we will compare each path with similar collapse rate.

To estimate it we can use light methods like volume preservation (Jacobian determinant). What we want is to avoid having to calculate the singular values of the matrix, or more costly operations. Of course, by considering for all paths passing through the same transformation that there is a uniform collapse for these, this will probably force the model to use different transformations for each zone, and thus indirectly participate in a segmentation similar to if we wanted them bijective. But here this will be done in a simpler and less costly way for a first implementation.

Curvature is above all revealing of the organization of storage, which is supposed to organize itself around the most common transformations that we want to represent/reconstruct as faithfully as possible. A chaotic trajectory then reveals poor storage organization, and thus indirectly uncertainty about retrieved information. We can nevertheless rely on the topology of space to validate the topology of the response (e.g., not knowing Paris, but knowing that it's a capital). The path, whether it is a chaotic geometric trajectory or not, will still pass through nodes whose topology is known. The projection onto these nodes may be poor, uncertain, but its passage on the node is not. From uncertainty to uncertainty, we can choose a path that deviates from the expected topology, because at each node, we follow the most relevant path (short/with low curvature here) as in Monte-Carlo or A-star.

Nevertheless, the objective is to learn a topology that limits this drift. However, the network should not be penalized for information that was corrupted, too indistinguishable.

In the case where we don't use transformation for transport, the topology itself can give us an indication of the fonctionnal collapse rate. As in a 3D space with a "wormhole". In principle, 3D space already has space filled, but we glue two zones together, which in the restricted dimension that is 3D space, a zone concentrates several points with the same coordinates but whose paths in this space are not equivalent. In terms of homology, we can consider that a path that makes additional turns loses in some way information, since with a direction at a point, I can perform several turns to arrive at this same point with a different direction.

Moreover, in this case of situation, as each projection extracts information according to the modes of the node, we split the input token in two: what contains the same modes as the node, the rest. In other words, we can average a coefficient on the quantity of information extracted for each projection and use it to evaluate the information collapse at this node.

To return to the notion of local modes, on the same node, the associated modes will not necessarily be in low frequency, but rather in high frequency. The low frequencies that represent the topology require the observation of cycles at different scales. This is the case, for example, for product functions, which will create groupings of local nodes, and which by hyperedge, represented as a node, will create the associated product type that will have the low frequencies associated with this topology.

By repeating the process on these product nodes, we manage to represent within a single hypernode the entire topology of the space, which also has its own low frequency modes, which this time will represent the total topology.

The advantage of this formulation is that we can dissociate the different levels and make them evolve independently. Synchronization will of course be necessary, but we can adjust the topology at the same time as a local high frequency mode. Identifying a product type allows the grouping of these sub-nodes, but then we can experiment with different topologies for this super-type (in coherence with the other super-types). The objective was to unify all nodes into hierarchical structures with hyperedges so that ultimately all elements of the same universe are represented under the same hypernode (indirectly). The model cannot simply leave independent nodes, and must constantly seek links to assemble these nodes together. Hence the fact that gradually, with a node representing a functional space, the different other nodes representing types and passing through this node for a transformation are grouped under the same supernode.

As mentioned previously, the idea behind this architecture is that the path taken by the input token to reach the desired final output point allows us to identify a path giving an a priori correct result. And from this path, search for all others leading to this same result (from a topological point of view, therefore according to the same low frequency modes up to the cycle). And we also search for paths that do not lead to this topology. Then we compare the paths with each other, the links they are supposed to create by passing from one node to another. And for each node, since we know the topology a priori, a path between these nodes (which represent transformations) gives an equivalence between these topologies that define the types. From there, given these equivalences, we try to see if for all paths leading to this result we have similar equivalences. If not, then we have paths that are a priori non-homotopic but are nevertheless supposed to be by definition since they lead to the same topological result. And in this case, we can seek to create equivalences so that they are homotopic, or else seek to be able to prove anything and everything by finding derived equivalences with paths that do not lead to the same topological results. The apparent contradictions then serve to know which equivalences create inconsistency, which can a priori be considered false.

The objective then is to crystallize these inconsistencies into a few equivalences that can be linked together in a hyperedge, to serve as a reference later on the inconsistency choices we have made. All the "decisions" that the model makes on its topology, on why we choose one path rather than another, are crystallized into a few nodes created on the fly that serve as memory. This crystallization is simply the process of finding the equivalences that allow, on the paths of this specific input, to arrive at the same conclusions with minimal search for alternative paths, and taking into account the current geometry, which represents the capacity to memorize these paths (in other words, we prefer to record an equivalence close to established knowledge, and therefore reconstructible with a high rate, rather than choosing a poorly explored equivalence, although exploration is also rewarded).

There are therefore several things at play here. First, just like the topology of the universe, we must wait for a sufficiently complete token sequence to obtain the real low frequency modes that

form the basis for comparing topological paths. Then, the result obtained at the output is a priori not exploitable as such since it is already contextualized: at the output we do not get directly exploitable embeddings. We must then search for the sequence of non-contextualized embeddings that best capture the output "signal" up to the cycle. This contextualization can be assimilated to different but equivalent modes, and a shift specific to the cycle of these modes. The output vocabulary itself contains only certain modes and is frozen at cycle 0.

There is therefore a real search operation that corresponds to the gluing together of different views of a hypergraph as we had made the connection previously.

Which brings us to point number two: the network primarily performs retrieval operations. The network itself is searchable where we can both search for similar paths via equivalences, but also paths that do not use these equivalences. Moreover, as training progresses, the nodes created on the fly to represent constraints are pruned and integrated into a sparse memory: for each portion of the total graph, for each zone of the manifold, we associate a hypernode that manages the memory of all these sub-nodes. When pruning specific nodes, we update the associated memory. This memory node does not have a very different functioning from other nodes, since it is itself composed of modes that represent the memory keys, and a projection layer that represents the retrieval layer from a noisy input. Which is fundamentally what each node does. This memorization, initially discrete and contextualized (specific to the input), is then generalized by mnemonic absorption where we do not encode the information as is but find topological equivalents closer to the active modes of memory.

And this memorization aims to constrain the system by remembering the fundamental model evolution choices made: since if an equivalence is suspected to be inconsistent with respect to the rest of the system, we must be able to remember the conditions that made it inconsistent, because an equivalence is not intrinsically inconsistent/invalid, only within a defined system. Now, since our model does not limit itself to one universe, but seeks the most appropriate universe for the given input, an equivalence that is inconsistent in one universe may be consistent in another. Therefore, we must remember the context of this choice.

Which brings us to the temporal question: how is temporal evolution encoded in the model?
There are different types of temporality:

- That of the evolution of inputs/a specific situation that must be encoded within the universe, the manifold. And which corresponds to the continuation of a trajectory
- That of the model itself which must be capable of anticipating its own evolution, its own changes and being able to reason about them
- That which retroactively modifies the universe: hypotheses/imagining scenarios.

The evolution of the model itself, of a universe (and not the evolution of an event in this universe, even though in hypergraph rewrite theory, it is the evolution of the universe itself that generates the evolution of an event by transposing its pattern in a stable manner within the universe), can be modeled in the same way as the rest of the model: via hypergraphs.

Indeed, if we consider the hypernode representing the universe (its manifold), then we can embed this node in a hypergraph where each node represents a possible evolution of this universe (of its topology via learning). Some of these nodes will have high frequency modes and probably be very close geometrically to the universe node, because they represent geometric modifications, while others more distant will represent deeper modifications, which will change the topology of the universe.

And as we did for the universe, we can construct hypernodes that represent all possible evolutions, and these nodes represent the temporal node of the universe, the true universe node that

contains all these possible evolutions. From this node, we can then construct other universes that have other creation rules.

The temporal evolution of the universe, this manifold that represents the future of a universe, can be mapped to the multiway space of hypergraph transformation, which represents all possible orders of application of a rule. And the space of the self-contained universe node (with all its possible evolutions) can correspond to the ruliad space where a node defined by its modes can generate by itself the entire universe and its possible evolutions. In practice, we do not generate the entire universe just from this, but we create an initial universe, which can have random modes, random geometry, and which we can use to interpolate the right universe. This is the basic idea: from a known universe defined in its topology and geometry at all levels, we can interpolate another universe by knowing how to modify the modes of nodes and relationships. And without this multi-level knowledge of the universe, if we only have the modes of the universe node, then we can guide and accelerate the search for the right universe/manifold given the input data.

We can even envision reference universes with known topology that we use regardless of the model to triangularize the universe in question, and be able to recreate it from scratch sufficiently correctly to require little data to refine it.

In this configuration, a hypothesis can actually be two things:

- A future that will be realized soon
- A future that has already been realized in another universe

Indeed, a hypothesis primarily can both define a possible future of the current universe, but also describe a valid rule in another universe either from the start, or in a future closer than that of the current universe. In fact, the future of one universe can be the past of another.

Moreover, just as we can create limit paths between types, which represent a possible bridge at the limit, we have the same thing with universes: at the limit, infinitely far in the future, in possible evolutions, two universes can be equivalent because ultimately they are different rules but which can eventually traverse the same equivalences in a different order, and thus become equivalent at the limit. But also, this is when we will see non-connected nodes appear between universes that represent universes where even at the limit of the future, we cannot obtain the same equivalences.

In other words, some hypotheses could not belong to the current universe, and we can use this limit as a criterion to differentiate membership in a distant but accessible future, and an inaccessible future. From a practical point of view, this means that beyond a certain distance, we consider that the hypothesis is not accessible, but we still register it within another universe. This actually means that a universe node cannot be described alone, but always in relation to its observable universe delimited by a temporal barrier. Everything that goes beyond this barrier is defined in another universe, which allows establishing decision boundaries on the current universe, and establishing constraints since if over time we realize that an equivalence was accessible, we must create an equivalence with an entire universe, which allows approaching an over-constraint of the system, facilitating possible update choices.

In other words, the system watches itself evolve according to different prisms, different hypotheses that it maintains in parallel and interpolates its current universe from this. Gradually, the position of the point of our current universe moves (or rather we refine what we believed to be our universe by taking a more appropriate point), which also shifts the multi-level representations of the observable boundary. The system can both define itself by what it is (the details of the universe in question that shift as we move), and what it is not (the details of the observable boundary).

Of course, this multi-level representation is given by the topology, since in terms of graph, everything is at the same level, but because certain nodes are hierarchically nested, this allows

establishing an order. Moreover, the universe node represents the fibration by path bundle since the gradient on this node indicates the geodesic paths which by propagation create an implicit projection where we can differentiate a "valid" path in this universe from a "non-valid" one in this universe, and by observing its trajectory determine by triangularization its adequate universe.

This does not mean that the path is not valid, simply that the path "makes" hypotheses (which are encoded in its trajectory by the path it takes and therefore allows establishing equivalences) that we do not necessarily know yet but which can be perfectly reasonable and which is represented by this decision boundary of universes that defines what we do not know/what we are not. Where the current universe represents what we know. And between the two we can have perfectly true and reasonable things. The more the current universe grows in what it knows, the more the "concentric" boundary recedes.

In practice, this also allows modeling an input sequence, however long, as its own manifold. Where the addition of sequence only allows refining this manifold. In other words, when we read a book, this book creates its own manifold with its own hypotheses, its own equivalences. This allows giving an implicit organization to the input context where information is no longer condensed/compressed from one sequence to another, but it infuses the topological and geometric structure of the manifold in question.

The model does not produce a manifold at the output, it is defined along the network itself with the knowledge of the network itself since it is created by triangularization by limiting itself to shifting on the fly a few nodes that represent the effective part of the knowledge that the input sequence calls upon. We can therefore both reason with the hypotheses that the input imposes on us, while being able to know if this hypothesis is reasonable or not thanks to the rest of the model where we can extrapolate and search for equivalences that would lead to a contradiction. We can relate this to synaptic plasticity where the input temporarily modifies the connections while respecting the pre-established organization.

Todo

Todo 1 - Interpolation continue du rang, filtrer sur les basses fréquences (les éléments les plus importants/fondamentaux doivent rester) - Fonction itérée IFS (dimension fractale, fonction récursive) vs base - On peut créer un autre mode non existant de la base en sélectionnant des nœuds qui orientent la découverte et en trouvant un autre mode qui respecte la contrainte (e.g. ortho) - Rappeler qu'on applique la même structure/même architecture à toutes les échelles (groupe, fonction, univers, temporalité, etc.) et on obtient le modèle complet - Exemple relation temporalité data (élément univers) et temporalité univers : une particule qui se déplace. Elle suit la trajectoire de plus faible courbure/plus court chemin (donné par la géométrie) mais par exemple quand on arrive à un embranchement ou une vallée à haut gradient/haute énergie, on ne sait pas où aller, quel chemin suivre. Et là c'est le relais à l'espace de l'évolution temporelle de l'univers qui explore chaque branche (dans le cas de la vallée par exemple création spontanée de particule ou condition spontanée pour franchir ce seuil énergétique avec un photon à ce moment-là, et on regarde ce que ça crée comme futur pour voir si c'est stable) - à voir

Todo 2 Chaque edge représente le landscape de la courbure locale pour le plus court chemin avec le nœud, la somme de tous les landscapes doit être plate puisque c'est un simplex. Ou alors définir uniquement les sommets, le grad... - à attention à la formulation car entre gradient sur les faces des simplex et au niveau des sommets ce n'est pas la même chose, ni le même résultat, ni les mêmes conditions de validité.

Et l'attention entre séquence paragraphe c'est juste plus de points sur le manifold.

Ce n'est pas compressé dans le sens où on fait un résumé.

On maintient les nœuds actifs/tout le réseau actif et on ajuste pour les nouveaux points.

Le fait d'utiliser des modes ça permet à ce que chaque embedding ait sa propre dimension/taille puisque cela revient à étendre ou raccourcir le "signal". Et la tokenisation ça représente simplement les différentes vues de l'espace que j'ai. Une séquence entière décrit un manifold qui est triangularisé/construit on the fly au sein même du modèle (pas en sortie). La séquence décrit seulement la trajectoire qui permet de discriminer au mieux le manifold d'un autre (de le reconstruire au maximum à partir de ce seul chemin). Une grande tokenisation (e.g. niveau des mots) décrit au mieux une trajectoire plus courte et moins courbe qui doit arriver au même résultat : discriminer le manifold pour le reconstruire. Une tokenisation plus courte (e.g. niveau des voyelles/consonnes) décrit une trajectoire plus longue/plusieurs trajectoires, donc plus d'information pour reconstruire le manifold. Le raisonnement lui se fait sur tout le manifold, autrement dit il peut passer par des zones/chemins qui n'ont pas d'équivalent en token, et donc il faudra un grand nombre de tokens mot qui auront la charge de tourner autour de ces zones du mieux qu'ils peuvent, et de différentes façons pour décrire ce qui n'a pas d'équivalent. Chaque séquence a sa propre topologie et sa propre géométrie qui donne implicitement ce qui est considéré comme une géodésique sur ce manifold (ce qui correspond naturellement au fait que la géodésique est une reconstruction "parfaite" de l'information, or comme la géodésique représente de base la séquence, on a un maximum d'information sur ce chemin). Le modèle lui permet de recontextualiser et apporter les informations manquantes.

La tokenisation dynamique n'est pas une simple recombinaison de signaux dont les tokens hiérarchiques bas (voyelle) doivent une fois recomposés (e.g. moyenner/additionner) former le token plus haut. Cette comparaison faiblement non linéaire n'est pas possible, car même s'ils décrivent la même chose, ils ne le font pas de la même manière et donc sont non comparables sans passer au travers du modèle. Ce qui est souhaité comme design (même si plus cher en ressource). Puisqu'on souhaite que les embeddings décrivent des chemins discriminants du manifold, non contextualisés. Dans les faits, que les inputs soient discrets ou continus ça ne change pas : tout est essentiellement discret. Et lorsqu'on tente de décrire le manifold on le fait selon une quantification définie par des tokens qui donnent les degrés de liberté possibles. Puisque sinon, cela signifierait qu'on peut décrire avec autant de trajectoires voulues le manifold, et donc au plus bas niveau créer des combinaisons de lettres qui n'existent pas. -; pas clair, à reformuler car les combinaisons sont "encodées" dans la topologie mais au final spectralement on peut décomposer un signal comme on veut en autant de parties qu'on veut, et donc cette composition est hautement arbitraire et non communicable hors contextualisation. Il faut donc nécessairement des références fixes partagées par tous les acteurs. La topologie va nous dire que certaines combinaisons de mots sont impossibles mais va laisser passer des combinaisons qui ne violent pas de règles mais qui n'existent pas pour autant. C'est là que la géométrie filtre ce qui a le plus de "chance" d'exister. La topologie permet de créer de nouveaux mots, la géométrie permet d'orienter cette création avec ce qui "sonne" le mieux/le plus "naturel". Ce qui a le plus de chance d'être compris par d'autres acteurs au travers d'habitudes communes. Géométrie = habitudes/normes/... -; à reformuler, trop d'extrapolation sociale

Ce qu'on cherche à faire avec les inputs ce n'est pas de raisonner dessus, mais de les utiliser comme référence pour construire ce sur quoi on va pouvoir raisonner. Au final la représentation en layer, c'est une représentation itérée où pour une séquence on peut commencer à tracer le manifold de différentes manières mais au bout de n itérations on obtient le même manifold (mais pas forcément les mêmes chemins de références finaux). La question pour deux séquences similaires c'est si on obtient le même manifold topologiquement parlant et que les deux chemins sont homotopiques.

Au final la tokenisation est avant tout trouver pour tous les chemins homotopiques le même chemin représentant (la référence). Puis ensuite adapter à la tâche downstream en finetuning pour faire shifter cette représentation selon la géométrie.

Donc dans un premier temps on travaille uniquement sur les inputs, pas les outputs. Et avec ces inputs, bien sûr la représentation topologique apprise peut être valide mais incomplète/trop

simple et pas adaptée à la tâche downstream, ce qui va causer une géométrie où les distances vont tellement éloigner les nœuds qu'on peut considérer qu'elles cassent les liens et donc indirectement changent la topologie par action discrète (un edge qui a une distance trop élevée par rapport à ses voisins, ça crée des problèmes d'instabilité pendant l'entraînement, l'idée c'est de normaliser/sigmoid cette distance et quand on veut la mettre à jour on crée un edge parallèle avec la distance appropriée adéquate, ensuite quand on fait le pruning, on observe le nombre de liens parallèles, la fréquence de changement, etc. pour savoir comment on met à jour la distance, qui pourrait décroître exponentiellement en une update au final, ce qui sort le gradient de sa zone de saturation).

L'idée d'avoir des edges liés même très éloignés c'est pas tant pour la recherche de chemin que pour faciliter la reconstruction de la géométrie en identifiant en amont les cycles, et tous les points charnières qui demanderaient sinon plusieurs itérations. L'idée est en une seule passe d'avoir à chaque étape toutes les contraintes pour ne pas revenir en arrière. Pour le coup ces liens sont des vrais liens topologiques dont la distance a peu d'importance.

Ironiquement, ce que deux acteurs partagent n'est pas forcément la topologie qui représente les connexions personnelles qu'ils font entre domaines, mais la géométrie : ils ne savent pas comment connecter ce qu'on leur partage, mais peuvent savoir quelles sont leurs "distances", leurs liens relatifs. E.g. un étudiant ne sait pas comment deux concepts sont connectés mais il peut "sentir" s'ils sont reliés ou non, sans savoir comment les relier. Et parfois (souvent) cette seule connaissance est superficielle et donne lieu à une mauvaise topologie en interne mais une impression de savoir, car on dispose de nombreux points avec leurs distances mais sans savoir si ces distances sont réellement informatives (permettent de tracer des chemins discriminants pour la topologie).

On a deux choses à prendre en compte : que les réponses qu'on produit soient cohérentes avec soi-même, avec le système qui les a produites (la topologie), et que dans un autre système topologique, la géométrie relative est plutôt conservée : autrement dit, à quel point je dois établir des références avec un autre agent pour tenir une discussion avec lui. Comme deux personnes ne parlant pas la même langue : on établit des liens basiques entre mots, qui établissent des références indépendantes en interne mais mutuellement cohérentes, qui ensuite définissent on the fly les embeddings du discours de l'autre agent. - $\dot{\iota}$ à reformuler trop ésotérique - $\dot{\iota}$ démonstration du propos même donc

Ça veut dire que la sortie on la quantifie avec des embeddings random qui partagent uniquement la même géométrie relative, et la question c'est combien de références je dois ajouter à la séquence pour obtenir la target output. Et on synchronise et cristallise les embeddings de cette façon : à travers le nombre de références en commun. On peut en fait produire des combinaisons de lettres "fausses", si on les utilise telles quelles on ne peut pas produire une output utilisable, mais la question c'est comme un chiffrement par substitution, combien de mots clés je dois aligner entre cette sortie et la target pour qu'on puisse shifter la sortie en conservant la géométrie relative. Ce "combien", ces éléments qu'on rajoute à la séquence ça forme le vocabulaire. Qui est aligné par la tâche downstream. Bien sûr une tâche downstream sémantiquement pauvre va produire une géométrie pauvre, et indirectement limiter la topologie. Mais la question est alors jusqu'à quelle taille de vocabulaire je peux croître avant que je produise une topologie si complexe qu'elle est dans les faits inutilisable (langage abscons, complexité artificielle, créer des problèmes pour les résoudre soi-même = s'hyperadapter aux data, au bruit des données). Il y a une taille maximale de vocabulaire qui permet de réaliser la tâche et d'arriver à la limite de la complexité d'une topologie exploitable par le dataset. - $\dot{\iota}$ entropie, théorie de l'information - $\dot{\iota}$ à l'ouest rien de nouveau

Ce qui est plus intéressant c'est cette notion d'agent/teacher-student/ensemble learning. Chaque univers est une vue différente d'un problème. Autrement dit un agent différent. Une unité d'un tout (- $\dot{\iota}$ reformuler, too much, éventuellement en note...). Des agents dont on peut en réalité connaître les liens topologiques et faire en sorte qu'ils ne maintiennent pas d'équivalence topologique entre eux, pour ainsi avoir des agents réellement différents entre lesquels la topologie est très différente

et dont la seule synchronisation se fait par la géométrie relative des séquences de chacun. Un agent peut avoir une topologie simple, un autre très complexe, un autre intermédiaire, et l'exercice est de voir quelle quantité d'information on est capable de partager en temps raisonnable : à quel point l'agent avec sa topologie complexe réussit à faire identifier à l'agent à la topologie plus simple des liens topologiques similaires. À un moment, cela va dessiner une frontière "stable" qui devrait représenter le vocabulaire maximal. Bien sûr un agent à la topologie très complexe peut être celui qui s'adapte au bruit des données et qui indirectement va pousser les autres à adopter une topologie aussi complexe mais toujours différente qui vont eux aussi s'adapter au bruit. Et c'est l'idée : plus on s'hyperadapte, moins on est capable de communiquer avec d'autres points de vue. Ce n'est pas une spécialisation sur une partie des données. C'est un univers complet sur toutes les données mais qui adopte une méthode de raisonnement spécifique (une topologie spécifique) pour résoudre les mêmes problèmes. Et ce ne sont pas des modèles séparés. C'est le même modèle global qu'on shift selon les cas. L'équivalent serait de développer des personnalités différentes par agent, mais ce n'est pas vraiment juste utiliser une séquence qu'on adjoint aux entrées pour modifier le calcul, c'est plutôt qu'on finetune le modèle pour produire le comportement attendu à partir de quelques exemples. Mais avec un contrôle plus vaste, puisqu'on peut éliminer des biais (sans forcément savoir quels rôles ont ces biais, juste que ce sont des biais indépendants et qu'on peut créer des personas à partir d'eux en s'assurant qu'il n'y ait pas d'équivalence au fil du temps entre eux). Et ici ce finetuning est implicite puisqu'il s'agit d'un déplacement dans l'espace. -; mieux définir cette histoire de shift qui est très concret mais expliqué de manière trop floue overall

Et donc comme on maintient ces univers à une distance "topologique" pour s'assurer d'une différence notable et non trivialement équivalente, chaque agent va s'hyperadapter à un "bruit différent" sur les données, et donc ils seront de moins en moins capables de communiquer entre eux, car le vocabulaire commun va exploser en taille. On va donc chercher à le réduire pour retrouver une communication. Ce qui va pousser le modèle à collapse sur une représentation simpliste, et ainsi de suite. Ce qui est censé créer un cycle dans l'espace de la temporalité d'évolution de l'univers, un cycle qu'on veut identifier pour connaître le vocabulaire idéal. Bien sûr l'idée n'est pas de cycler sur tout le dataset mais de le faire avec quelques data en extrapolant/simulant les modifications, les drifts des données, et un cycle complet.

Un modèle trop complexe crée des contradictions locales incohérentes entre elles, et insolubles globalement. La géométrie permet de créer ces contradictions locales. Mais pour les résoudre globalement on se retrouve avec un système qui doit créer toujours plus de structure topologique pour résoudre la géométrie (i.e. résoudre une contradiction en crée n autres, et ainsi de suite sans sembler se stabiliser/converger dans les types, ou dans un cycle trop long pour être considéré).

L'idée n'est pas de bloquer ce cycle, au contraire, c'est simplement de l'identifier pour savoir à tout moment où on se trouve sur ce cycle pour estimer sa propre incertitude. Ce cycle c'est la "garantie" qu'on peut laisser s'entraîner le modèle indéfiniment et qu'il peut savoir quand passer à autre chose (apprentissage progressif) ou s'assurer que même si on collapse on sera capable de recover dans le temps. L'idée c'est de laisser le collapse et l'expansion se produire pour observer comment ils se produisent et s'assurer que c'est conforme à la prédiction. Comme ça on peut essayer de stabiliser/moyenner le cycle par correction a posteriori. Et cela permet de s'assurer qu'en driftant au fil du temps, le modèle sera capable à partir de l'observation de son propre collapse de savoir comment se réajuster même si on dévie de ses prédictions de collapse. Car dans ce cas, il devra laisser se produire un collapse pour se resituer. En système clos un drift est inévitable, la question n'est pas ici, mais de pouvoir récupérer du drift très rapidement avec quelques données externes nouvelles. Bien sûr, plus on va "avancer" loin dans ce drift, plus on va se perdre, et prendre plus de temps à recontextualiser tout le parcours qu'on a fait pour se retrouver là.

Ce qu'on cherche à faire c'est réduire le plus possible ce drift en système clos (sur le dataset sans validation), que le modèle s'auto-arrête sans avoir recours au dataset de validation pour étudier sa

courbe de loss. $-z$ existe déjà sous certaines formes, l'idée est de tout unifier.

Le cycle est statique dans le sens où c'est un cycle sur un hypergraphe qui représente la temporalité de l'évolution. Il n'y a aucune dimension implicite dans ce modèle, tout doit exister au travers d'hypergraphes manipulables, et donc self-reflecting.

Todo 3 Définir une topologie en même temps que les data est un exercice plutôt délicat, notamment car la définition des hypothèses suppose leur existence sur une autre topologie qu'il faut définir suffisamment au moment de la génération de l'hypothèse, chaque hypothèse pouvant être abritée sous différentes topologies, la conciliation de toutes les topologies va s'avérer laborieuse. Ainsi, il est plus simple de présupposer de topologies à utiliser comme point de référence et de les ajuster par la suite ; produisant une forme de raisonnement par contradiction. En effet, pour un chemin de raisonnement particulier, il est plus simple de complexifier la topologie (augmenter le nombre de trous) jusqu'à ce que le chemin ne soit plus permis. Autrement dit, si un chemin en ligne droite sur une topologie donnée résout le problème, on peut se demander si en ajoutant un trou, on peut toujours résoudre ce même problème, et ainsi de suite.

On définit alors trois nœuds univers construits avec leurs modes associés représentant la topologie du manifold décrit. On choisit ces trois topologies (ces trois ensembles de modes) pour être différentes en permanence afin de produire des topologies avec peu de similarité. Ces trois manifolds vont servir de référence pour la construction de l'univers cible (dictée par les inputs). Chaque manifold selon la complexité de sa topologie dispose d'un vocabulaire discret intrinsèque. Ce vocabulaire sert à décrire le parcours du graphe (représentant le manifold) d'un chemin. Autrement dit, un token du vocabulaire a une position sur le manifold et décrit dans son immédiat voisinage le chemin qu'il suit. En théorie, une fois qu'on définit le point de projection sur le manifold, le chemin est entièrement déterminé en suivant le chemin de plus faible courbure, cependant d'un point de vue pratique, si on ne fractionne pas ce chemin en plus petites unités au moindre update du manifold, le vocabulaire devra être modifié intégralement.

Dans ce contexte, un chemin partant d'un même point A sur le manifold mais empruntant une trajectoire différente de la géodésique menant à B , pour finalement mener à C . Il n'existe a priori pas de token dans le vocabulaire permettant de décrire le chemin $A-C$. Pour ce faire, il faut combiner d'autres tokens ayant des points de départ différents de A et des points d'arrivée non forcément égaux à C mais qui lorsque mis ensemble permettent d'interpoler le chemin $A-C$. C'est le rôle des séquences de tokens (du multi-token) dans ce modèle. La séquence de tokens permet de redéfinir dynamiquement le vocabulaire où un token de ce nouveau vocabulaire est une combinaison linéaire du vocabulaire de base. Autrement dit, on reparamètre le vocabulaire de base, la géométrie locale de base du manifold pour correctement décrire le chemin non géodésique $A-C$.

L'usage d'un vocabulaire est important ici car il permet de créer un bottleneck d'information lors de l'échange d'information entre univers. C'est un bottleneck artificiel qui ne compresse pas l'information puisqu'on a accès en détail à chaque chemin continu sur chaque manifold et qu'on peut les comparer directement. Mais cette comparaison, ce parcours de graphe, nécessite des points de référence, et de la quantification dans la pratique. D'autre part, il y a une réelle volonté dans cette architecture de discrétiser pour représenter une limite fondamentale sur le partage d'information avec l'extérieur et avec n'importe quelle tâche downstream : le langage fourni par les inputs ne peut pas représenter toute la complexité de la structure sous-jacente. Mais on doit tout de même être capable de connaître cette structure en détail, simplement de ne pas la définir par le langage associé à la tâche downstream. Ce faisant : on est capable de clairement identifier un chemin de manière continue sur le manifold, mais l'effort réside dans la capacité à le décrire aux autres manifolds avec leur vocabulaire (e.g. avoir besoin d'une longue séquence de tokens pour décrire $A-C$ alors qu'un seul token suffit pour $A-B$).

Dans ce schéma, ce qu'apprend le modèle c'est à combiner les manifolds de référence pour produire le manifold associé aux inputs. Pour une input donnée (discrète ou continue), elle a son vocabulaire associé que l'on synchronise avec les autres univers en cherchant la combinaison linéaire des tokens des vocabulaires respectifs qui permettent de décrire l'attendu. De cette manière, puisque chaque univers a une topologie différente et de complexité différente, on peut au fur et à mesure interpoler la topologie correcte associée aux inputs. Dans les faits, cela s'apparente à un path bundle puisqu'on projette un chemin (une séquence de tokens) sur un point (un token dans un autre vocabulaire).

Ce passage est très important selon nous, car nous souhaitons ne pas dépendre des valeurs et des mises à jours des valeurs sur les tâches discrètes (nécessitant un hard mapping entre les inputs et le vocabulaire d'entrée dont il faut également apprendre la valeur). Nous pensons qu'en définissant un vocabulaire intraséque à chaque manifold, pré-task, on déplace ce problème d'apprentissage des valeurs à un problème d'apprentissage des relations. Les valeurs d'entrées ne servent ici que de raccourci, de dictionnaire sur les bonnes combinaisons. Concrètement, l'unique chose qui compte c'est la cohérence des "projections" des inputs sur les manifolds de référence, pas les points de projection, ni le chemin en lui-même, puisqu'un autre chemin peut décrire la même chose s'il est équivalent et cet autre chemin aura un point de départ différent et des séquences de tokens différentes. Cette équivalence est celle des chemins topologique, qui n'est pas forcément relié à une équivalence sémantique, mais le but de training est de faire correspondre les deux.

L'idée sous-jacente est que même sans vocabulaire attribuée aux inputs, on puisse tout de même en extraire une information sur les relations avec un choix pseudo arbitraire de valeur. C'est implicitement ce que font les NN modernes où les embeddings appris représente des starting point optimisés. Ici on souhaite faire la distinction explicite entre les deux. Et une manière de faire cela est en considérant un vocabulaire comme un dictionnaire dynamique (comme ce qu'on peut trouver dans les algortimes de compression) : l'univers entier des possibilités se restreint à l'input actuel sur laquelle on crée un vocabulaire pour représenter au mieux l'input lors de la reconstruction. Autrement dit, on tokenise l'input de manière à contraindre au mieux le système (e.g. un symbole qui ne revient qu'une fois dans la séquence peut prendre n'importe quelle valeur, donc n'est pas contraint). Concrètement, pour chaque symbole discret on associe une combinaison linéaire des vocabulaires associées aux manifold. Ce mapping est d'autant plus contraint que le choix d'une combinaison pour un manifold doit être cohérent avec les autres qui sont reliés par certaines équivalences. Le rôle du modèle est alors de trouver la combinaison qui maximise les équivalences entre les chemins des manifolds de manière itérative. Ce qui est la fonction première de ce modèle : trouver à partir d'un chemin le manifold sous-jacent que le chemin décrit au mieux. Autrement dit, une séquence peut être représentée en ligne droite, mais aussi courbe, faisant plusieurs tours, etc. Et arrivera soit une limite d'indécidabilité (e.g. il y a trop de choix possibles équivalents, ce qui peut indiquer que le contenu de la séquence est non représentatif), soit on arrivera à une limite de complexité topologique au-delà de laquelle on ne peut plus encoder cette séquence.

Comme indiqué, certaines séquences ne pourront pas être représentées car trop peu contraintes, et c'est à ce moment-là qu'entre en jeu les valeurs apprises : étendre le dictionnaire à d'autres symboles non présents dans la séquence et qui aiderait à contraindre le système.

Tout l'enjeu du modèle est de performer dans cette recombinaison dynamique. D'ailleurs le manifold ainsi créé qui se limite au dictionnaire des symboles présents représente les transformations entre manifolds : les combinaisons linéaires. En effet, il faut visualiser le système comme plusieurs entités qui partagent une expérience similaire mais dans des langues différentes. Alors la traduction d'une langue à l'autre ne peut pas être une simple combinaison linéaire des mots, il faut des transformations non linéaires qui donnent à la fin une combinaison du vocabulaire. Cette transformation non linéaire est le manifold créé. Un chemin dans ce manifold a une équivalence dans un autre manifold et donc à partir de celle-là on peut trouver une combinaison des tokens du vocabulaire.

Évidemment, au fur et à mesure du training, la géométrie des manifolds de référence va changer à mesure des équivalences entre manifolds, impactée par les inputs. Et si la géométrie change, alors les valeurs du vocabulaire intrinsèque changent puisqu'elles représentent les parcours optimaux du graphe pour décrire ce graphe (qui représente le manifold). Et au fur et à mesure on va également changer la topologie des manifolds selon ces mêmes équivalences pour représenter au mieux les relations du dataset d'input (dans le sens où sur certaines zones des manifolds on arrive mal à représenter les inputs, ce qui signifie une topologie trop différente, et donc qu'il faut l'ajuster comme supprimer ou ajouter un trou). Tout en s'assurant que la topologie des manifolds de référence reste différente tant sur le plan de la complexité topologique que de la topologie en elle-même. Comme le rôle du modèle est de trouver des équivalences entre chemins de manifolds, alors on peut monitorer ce taux d'équivalence pour ajuster la topologie en permanence pour qu'elle reste différente.

Mais malgré cette adaptation, et même si la géométrie ou la topologie évolue pour mieux s'adapter aux données d'entrée, la tâche première du modèle est d'extraire des relations peu importe les valeurs, peu importe les manifolds utilisés. Évidemment, certaines topologies seront très éloignées d'un dataset différent, ce qui va conduire à une moins bonne approximation, et c'est pourquoi le layer au-dessus des univers qui monitor leurs évolutions sert de meta learning pour accélérer le bon positionnement dans le layer des univers. Tout au long du training, on choisit de manière arbitraire de changer les topologies temporairement, de projeter les inputs dessus et de minimiser le nombre de données nécessaires à revenir vers les manifolds de référence actuels qui représentent l'état des connaissances actuelles du dataset. C'est le shifting d'univers.

Ce qu'il faut comprendre dans ce shifting d'univers, c'est que si on représente les univers par une séquence de modes comme point dans un manifold où chaque point représente un univers et un chemin représentant une transformation non linéaire pour y parvenir, on ne peut pas reconstruire un univers sur cette seule base. Lorsqu'on dit qu'il n'y a pas d'information bottleneck à proprement parler, c'est que le bottleneck se construit avant tout pour le monitoring entre strates mais les équivalences entre univers sont construites localement d'un univers à l'autre, puis compressées et remontées à la strate suivante. Autrement dit, lorsqu'on shift d'un univers à un autre, on ne le fait pas sur la base seule du chemin entre univers dans le layer des univers. Ce chemin nous donne une transformation globale que l'on applique ensuite à toutes les équivalences de l'univers de départ avec les autres de référence pour les modifier individuellement afin d'interpoler l'univers d'arrivée.

Toutefois, on n'est pas obligé de shifter tout un univers pour déterminer le chemin sur un autre univers. On peut simplement l'approximer en considérant les équivalences locales qui concernent le chemin. Ou bien seulement identifier les coefficients des modes topologiques de l'univers propres à ce chemin et faire le shift approximatif uniquement sur cette base, ce qui est drastiquement moins coûteux.

Pour récapituler, on ne cherche pas à faire exister toutes les inputs sur le même manifold, mais plutôt à déterminer celui le plus adapté au chemin décrit par la séquence. Le manifold construit au fur et à mesure du training à l'aide des manifolds de référence, eux ne servent que de point d'ancrage qui ont également toute leur utilité. Par exemple, avec un seul mot comme input, ou un seul morphème, il n'est pas possible de construire un dictionnaire dynamique, pourtant on doit quand même être capable de l'associer à des faits appris. C'est le rôle du manifold associé aux inputs. En faisant un mapping entre les manifolds de référence, on externalise la mémoire à ces manifolds et un seul mot peut alors se mapper sur plusieurs zones des manifolds représentant plusieurs faits/expériences/souvenirs. Si l'on fait la comparaison avec une neural memory, les vecteurs bases de notre système sont les manifolds de référence et le manifold des inputs qui encode le mapping entre eux sert d'interface pour le retrieval (le layer des Query dans lequel l'input passe). La généralisation elle vient de la capacité à construire des manifolds on the fly représentant au mieux les inputs (comme la self attention où les bases de la mémoire sont dynamiquement générées [42]).

D'autre part, le manifold de la tâche downstream et le manifold des inputs sont distincts des autres : ce qu'on apprend c'est le mapping des chemins d'un manifold sur un autre mais les manifolds de référence existent en soi indépendamment. Autrement dit, le collapse de l'information dans une tâche de classification n'impacte a priori pas la topologie des manifolds de référence. Évidemment, la tâche downstream va définir le niveau de collapse de l'information et les mappings appris pour les chemins entre univers seront spécifiques à cette tâche donc moins voire peu généralisables. On doit d'abord entraîner le modèle en auto-régressif avant de le finetuner sur la tâche downstream.

Le signal de training qui correspond à la reconstruction de l'input, la bonne prédiction de la suite, ou l'alignement sur les valeurs de représentation, est un signal utile mais insuffisant. La capacité à prévoir la suite que ce soit dans l'espace des inputs, l'espace latent ou l'espace des représentations, est une conséquence d'un autre processus avant tout puisqu'il limite la capacité à faire des hypothèses, à produire quelque chose de peu probable mais valide. Concrètement dans la séquence "Il était une fois, un petit garçon qui entra dans une forêt terrifiante et mourut", la chute est valide mais va à l'encontre de l'attendu supposé par la première partie. Prédire la représentation de cette phrase c'est être surpris par cette représentation, et ensuite la reconnaître comme valide. Ce qui correspond avant tout à des chemins équivalents dont la géométrie aurait fait qu'on en a choisi un plutôt qu'un autre représentant le plus probable.

Autrement dit, ce qu'on cherche avant tout c'est l'équivalence entre chemins : à maximiser les équivalences entre les chemins des manifolds de référence. C'est cette partie du processus itératif où on cherche à stabiliser les représentations entre manifolds pour une même input en choisissant un vocabulaire dynamique. Ce qui signifie qu'on peut disposer de la séquence entière dès le début et ce qu'on s'assure c'est des équivalences entre les manifolds. On ne prédit donc pas en soi la suite d'une séquence car on dispose de toute la séquence dès le départ, mais chaque choix de représentation pour cet input génère une hypothèse, et au sein de ces hypothèses on s'assure de l'équivalence entre manifolds. Au fil des séquences, le but du training est d'éliminer certaines de ces hypothèses, et donc de rendre impossibles certaines équivalences en modifiant la topologie respective des manifolds. Vient ensuite l'ajustement de la géométrie qui elle correspond à la bonne prédiction de la représentation de la suite de la séquence.

Pour récapituler, lorsqu'on dispose de la phrase "Il était une fois, un petit garçon qui entra dans une forêt terrifiante" on n'a pas de moyen de vérifier que la suite est "et il mourut" ou "et il vécut une aventure extraordinaire". Implicitement les NN actuels font les connexions entre ces deux fins possibles au fur et à mesure des exemples en trouvant des phrases avec des structures sémantiques similaires qui lient les deux. En d'autres termes, il fait le même processus que ce modèle mais avec un vocabulaire unique sur un manifold unique qu'on fait évoluer au cours du temps. Et la capacité de ces modèles à prévoir d'autres séquences et les lier entre elles est assez faible. Ici, le modèle est pénalisé s'il voit une donnée nouvelle sur laquelle il n'existe aucune hypothèse, et lorsqu'il rencontre une donnée qui valide une hypothèse, il est pénalisé si la structure prédite ne correspond pas. Autrement dit, on encourage le réseau à imaginer ce qu'il va rencontrer à un moment ou un autre, non forcément dans une temporalité continue comme souvent dans un dataset d'un batch à l'autre. Cette pénalité nécessite intrinsèquement de la mémoire pour savoir quelles étaient les conditions de création de cette hypothèse pour pouvoir les modifier. D'où la formulation de l'architecture du modèle entier sous forme de graphe puisqu'il suffit ensuite d'ajouter un noeud pour encoder une nouvelle information. Et sur chaque noeud on peut associer une fréquence de parcours, un taux de changement, encoder les différentes ranges de valeurs qu'on lui a attribuées, ect. Et le pruning lui se charge de contenir ces stockages individuels sous un certain seuil, en compressant ensuite l'information pour la reconstruire localement plus tard. La structure même du modèle en graphe permet à la fois de représenter au sein même du modèle le knowledge graph et de représenter sa structure géométrique, rendant la limite entre les deux floues. Ce graphe modélise les interactions au sein même du réseau puisqu'il s'agit du réseau. Pour faire le parallèle avec nos explorations

précédentes, on peut considérer que ce modèle est un réseau virtuel qui n'est pas généré on the fly comme un GNN, mais qui est le modèle même. Et le NN chargé de faire l'interaction à chaque nœud peut alors être réduit en taille.

D'ailleurs, une trop bonne prédiction des hypothèses doit donner lieu à un score de fatigue/score de surprise [48] [49] élevé/faible et générer la production d'autres hypothèses moins probables. L'idée est qu'à un moment le système va se stabiliser entre des hypothèses trop farfelues qui ne peuvent pas être soutenues par le dataset, et des hypothèses trop proches de la tâche downstream ou de la tâche de prédiction.

À noter :

- Dans cette architecture, à la fois le manifold associé aux inputs et à la tâche downstream sont distincts, puisque ce sont en soi deux langages différents, ou plutôt deux objectifs différents.
- On peut considérer au sein d'un même manifold/univers chaque nœud comme un mini univers (même deux nœuds avec les mêmes modes ne représentent pas nécessairement la même topologie puisqu'un nœud peut exclure certaines zones/points en affinant les coefficients de ces modes, même si le manifold est plat au sein de chaque nœud). Et le processus décrit précédemment s'applique tout autant. Mais on choisit dans un premier temps de ne pas l'appliquer à ce niveau de granularité car il est alors plus difficile d'attribuer un nœud à une topologie entière, là où avec des univers de référence prédéfinis, on conserve la même cohérence interne entre chemins.
- La temporalité dans un dataset étant arbitraire d'un batch à l'autre, la capacité du modèle à prédire ces évolutions internes s'en voit impactée. Mais alors le modèle devrait prédire l'évolution de sa propre complexité interne. Autrement dit, en termes de temporalité toutes les évolutions ont la même longueur de temps unité (puisque pas d'ordre dans le dataset), mais on peut les organiser selon le chemin d'apprentissage que le modèle va prendre selon la complexité des découvertes qu'il fait. Le modèle prédit qu'il va rencontrer un élément trop complexe pour lui, et va pouvoir dire quelles sont les étapes pour le comprendre. En soi, au moment où il rencontre cet élément trop complexe, le modèle ne sait pas qu'il est trop complexe puisque justement il n'a pas les outils nécessaires pour ne serait-ce que percevoir cette complexité. Mais il peut prédire son chemin d'apprentissage et ce qu'il pense être capable de faire le long de ce chemin. Puis à une étape de ce chemin, les éléments qu'on croise (dans un ordre toujours arbitraire) si on n'est pas capable d'en tirer davantage de complexité que précédemment, alors c'est que le modèle s'est trompé sur la prédiction de sa propre évolution. D'autre part, être capable d'en tirer davantage de complexité qu'avant ce n'est pas une comparaison avec ce que le modèle était lorsqu'il a rencontré cet élément la dernière fois, mais qu'il jalonne ces hypothèses (les associe à une étape de l'apprentissage) et qu'on compare quelles hypothèses cet élément "active".

Bien entendu, le modèle ne peut pas prédire ce qu'il ne sait pas puisqu'il lui manque justement ce qui est nécessaire pour le prédire. Il ne va pas prédire le contenu de l'hypothèse associée à l'élément complexe, mais plutôt qu'on peut en tirer quelque chose de plus ou non et comment. Pour illustration, savoir qu'il existe des objets plus petits comme des fourmis et faire l'hypothèse qu'on peut appliquer les mêmes règles d'échelle à l'Homme et la Terre. Notre hypothèse sous-jacente est que toutes (ou du moins en grande partie) les idées peuvent être formulées par association simple. Ce qui ne l'est hautement pas est le comment implémenter ces idées (e.g. l'invention d'un avion est une idée simple qui peut être l'association d'un oiseau sur lequel on peut monter comme on monte des chevaux, le comment on parvient à faire ça est très complexe). Ce que le modèle doit donc prédire c'est la hiérarchie de complexité d'implémentation des idées. De prédire que pour réaliser l'idée d'un avion, il faut réaliser

l'idée A, puis B, puis C, etc. Le comment lui n'est pas prédictible a priori sans a minima les étapes précédentes déjà implémentées.

- Le savoir transversal, ou la capacité de généralisation représente exactement la manière dont le modèle apprend : entre deux manifolds/deux domaines on cherche des chemins de référence sur la base desquels on peut explorer l'autre manifold de manière cohérente. Et le modèle doit trouver ces chemins de référence. D'autre part, la distinction qu'on a faite avec le shift d'univers s'applique ici aussi puisqu'il y a une différence entre avoir des points de référence qui donnent une idée générale de comment solutionner le problème en s'appuyant sur un autre problème et construire l'équivalence locale exacte. Pour illustration, comprendre ce qu'est une rotation en 3D ne garantit pas de savoir en faire une en 4D. Mais cela permet de savoir à quoi doit répondre la rotation en 4D en s'appuyant sur les résultats de celle en 3D.
- Concernant la "personnalité", même si nous pensons qu'il est possible de réduire une personnalité à quelques séquences hautement idiosyncratiques, le processus inverse d'appliquer une personnalité a posteriori nous semble compromis puisque le savoir est intentionnel. Premièrement, il faut faire la différence entre le savoir factuel, la capacité de généralisation et les liens entre savoirs. Le savoir factuel au sein d'un même domaine est contenu dans un même manifold. La généralisation est comme décrit plus haut la capacité à faire un mapping à partir de références, les liens entre savoirs eux sont la construction des équivalences. Et cette construction est nécessairement intentionnelle car l'espace des combinaisons possibles de liens entre savoirs est combinatoirement explosif. Il y a la construction de liens transverses par nécessité : on ne connaît pas la réponse et on doit en extrapoler une, mais il y a également les liens non sollicités qui sont vrais mais qui n'apportent a priori rien, si ce n'est en définissant la personnalité même. La personnalité nous semble décrite par deux choses : les données vues, incluant leur ordre, et les liens entre données faits. Il nous semble à ce stade peu probable que l'on puisse définir une personnalité lorsque tous les savoirs sont accessibles et intégrés. Puisque si le parcours d'apprentissage résulte en partie d'un choix par intérêt, ces intérêts sont liés en partie à la personnalité, et le reste au cadre entourant. Autrement dit, on peut comprendre la personnalité comme un filtre qui restreint l'accès au savoir afin de limiter la dispersion lors de l'apprentissage et de systématiser la manière d'apprendre afin de l'éliminer des variables à prendre en compte.

Mais dans un système où la marche à l'apprentissage est forcée, l'ordre est aléatoire, et où on ne se limite pas à un domaine, cette partie de la personnalité est compromise. Reste alors les liens transverses entre savoirs faits non par nécessité. Et à ce stade, on peut juger qu'un lien transverse est aussi un savoir et donc qu'il n'induit pas de choix spécifique. D'autant plus que le modèle est encouragé à explorer des hypothèses diverses et variées et des liens en tout genre. Pour autant, il arrive un moment où la retenue de ces liens est jugée par leur pertinence/leur nécessité même s'ils sont valides.

Autrement dit, même si on programme une persona après coup pour le modèle, il ne pourra pas effacer certains liens dont l'existence même compromet cette persona, et il ne pourra pas résoudre au cas par cas l'équivalence des chemins. Car adopter une persona dès le début d'entraînement et l'adopter après coup est plus qu'une simple question de finetuning, puisque la présence même de certains liens transverses contredit la persona définie après coup et ce même lien a été utilisé et diffusé dans le reste du modèle pour définir le parcours d'apprentissage. En d'autres mots, le simple fait qu'on ait le savoir d'une chose étend le champ de ce qui est possible et donc indirectement de ce qui est permis. Même si a posteriori on supprime ce lien, ce qui reste aujourd'hui difficile dans l'alignement [50], il reste une différence fondamentale avec un apprentissage qui n'aurait pas eu un parcours d'apprentissage avec ce savoir. Et comme dit précédemment, ce n'est pas simplement la connaissance de l'idée en elle-même le problème mais bien l'équivalence locale créée qui rend la possibilité d'utiliser

ce savoir bien plus grande et probable. Pour illustration, savoir comment construire une bombe dans les détails, simplement savoir que les bombes existent, ne pas savoir que les bombes existent, sont trois états bien distincts qui rendent le passage à l'acte sous certaines conditions plus ou moins probable car plus ou moins faisable.

Évidemment, la personnalité contribue à bloquer l'accès à certaines capacités apprises, mais il nous semble que cela n'est pas une simple histoire d'ajout post hoc et qu'il ne s'agit pas non plus d'une simple reparamétrisation. Mais d'une ré-exploration extensive des liens pour créer des points de référence en lien avec la persona en question. L'idée étant de pouvoir résoudre on the fly des conflits d'équivalence entre la persona choisie et le savoir en ayant le plus de points de référence possible.

Il faut également faire une différence entre la persona et la personnalité. La persona est une tranche de la personnalité exprimée avec le vocabulaire du manifold. La personnalité elle n'est pas nécessairement exprimée dans ce vocabulaire mais directement comme chemin du manifold (puisque le vocabulaire du manifold est intrinsèque au parcours du manifold, il n'est pas exclusif). D'où une possible dissonance entre ce qu'on interprète comme la personnalité avec le langage des inputs et ce qu'est réellement la personnalité.

Pour nous, la personnalité représente une séquence extrêmement réduite pour réduire les effets de bord. Et la complexité ne vient pas de ces éléments totems, mais de leurs interactions avec le reste de l'univers. C'est pour cela qu'il nous semble préférable à terme de réduire les données d'entraînement pour d'abord forger une personnalité, pour ensuite laisser le modèle avoir accès à cette quantité astronomique de données. Cela va nécessairement biaiser les données puisqu'on renverse le paradigme en cherchant d'abord à créer l'interface pour ensuite créer la base de données derrière dont l'organisation va alors dépendre de cela.

C'est pourquoi on a souhaité maintenir au plus proche notre modèle de cette structure d'entités distinctes mais évoluant dans le même espace pour maintenir plusieurs personnalités en parallèle. L'idée est d'exposer la même information à plusieurs entités ayant chacune leur propre intentionnalité et donc créant des liens transverses spécifiques. Chaque entité a ses propres objectifs, ses propres conditions, etc. Et l'espace collectif est construit à partir de ces expériences individuelles et conflictuelles. Ou comment créer un système qui inclut ses propres contradictions et construit dessus.

- Le modèle en tant que tel nécessite de nombreux paramètres, ce qui nous semble contrebalancé par l'explosion des combinaisons. Autrement dit, le nombre de paramètres ici devrait être compensé par la vaste quantité de combinaisons de chemins possibles même pour un petit dataset. Il est par exemple possible d'apprendre une équivalence locale qui ne correspond qu'à une input, et donc faire de l'overfit, mais de par l'équivalence entre chemins apprendre par cœur devient bien plus coûteux puisqu'on doit également apprendre par cœur tous les autres chemins censés être équivalents. Le nombre de paramètres du modèle ou la taille du dataset nous semble compensé par cette explosion des combinaisons. Pour rappel, on encourage le modèle à cristalliser les généralisations sur certaines données, mais il y a une différence entre apprendre un savoir par cœur, propre à une donnée et l'intégrer avec le reste du modèle, que les équivalences entre d'autres données soient valides.
- En principe dans le path bundle, qui correspond à la combinaison des tokens d'un vocabulaire, on ne peut pas encoder un chemin qui n'existe pas (e.g. entre deux composantes non connexes). Or comme les tokens sont associés à certaines régions, une combinaison pourrait conduire à un chemin artificiel entre deux zones non connexes, ce qui n'est pas permis en path bundle. Il y a alors deux manières de le résoudre : soit le considérer comme une manière de contraindre le système en limitant les combinaisons possibles, mais la vérification de la

discontinuité pourrait s'avérer coûteuse. Soit relaxer le problème et considérer qu'on fait une transformation de la topologie.

3.8 Notes

The choice of HoTT instead of CT or differential geometry comes from the hypergraph transformation which offers a discrete framework for modeling, and which depends only on pure graph transformations without properties on nodes or edges. This makes it a good candidate for manipulation from scratch. One of the initial questions was how can we make a network appear from nothing, and have it organize itself without information (without data), other than what it generates by self-stimulation (as the nervous system of a fetus can do for example). This therefore amounts to encoding somewhere the structure of the network itself, or an objective function that constrains the network to structure itself in this way. From then on, what format is necessary to encode this information. It is entirely possible that we can encode it according to the specificities of each model (for example, storing parameters for a Riemannian geometry, and storing the necessary properties to verify the geometry). Although biologically plausible over the course of evolution, the possibility of encoding this information in a graph simply composed of nodes and edges, is more neutral and more universal.

On the other hand, this notion of trajectory developed throughout our explorations, corresponds to an object that carries a computable load in itself, and which assembles according to rules of self-coherence. In this sense, HoTT offers an expression framework for this idea, since paths are computable proofs and validity comes from the construction as we go along of a topos.

Obviously, whether in CT or HoTT, a topos is not simple to implement but the exploratory nature, of continuous verification while exploring the space is aligned with meta learning and hypothesis creation.

The initial objective of Paththinker with these different previous papers was to stay as close as possible to existing architectures to facilitate comparison. But it turns out that they are too constraining. Attempting to implement each component separately was too unstable. On the other hand, each idea was expressed in its own language, with its own particularities and too disparate. HoTT therefore has a very conducive unifying framework. We would probably not strictly implement HoTT, but the framework of reflection it offers interesting conceptual bridges, which we can then approximate.

The construction of this architecture is also made to align with the notion of "collectivity" where a whole network organizes itself by allowing relative autonomy while contributing to the whole. This is moreover the principle of distributed computation of NNs, but the interest of this collectivity is that in fact we can agentify it to produce agents of completely different sizes. In this architecture, we attempt to implement this mechanism, since universes in this architecture represent entire models. In other words, a space where each point is a model, and therefore we can deploy several models and reintegrate the learned information not directly by aggregating/averaging the models; since the collectivity (the space of all models) is infinitely larger and does not have the architecture of the models. This fusion actually operates by triangulating the position of the different models relative to the current universe. And this reintegration can be done at different levels: we do not reintegrate the whole model but only 1 element that differentiates it from the others, its specific property. This could for example translate to a universe whose property is a reversed arrow of time.

At the scale of a universe, this notion of collectivity also applies since by extracting a trajectory we actually make an autonomous model, which has its own properties. We can then assemble different trajectory-models to test their interactions in an isolated manner in parallel and reintegrate them by recalculating their position in space.

Moreover, this reintegration/fusion is entirely conditioned on the amount of information in the zone of this space: a poorly explored zone can be developed or simply updated with the same level of information, and conversely another zone can become more disparate in information because less relevant for the current universe. The graph representation of the model itself allows this natural extension and this sparsification.

From a philosophical point of view, collectivity deliberately aligns with Jung's notion of *Unus mundus*. As for the discrete aspect of graph manipulations, this can align with Wheeler's *It from Bit* theory.

In other words, this architecture attempts to answer how we create information from nothing (discrete graphs, although excessive simplification of the theory) or how we explain "nothing", and how we can have modules that are both autonomous and included in a collectivity that seeks answers to all possible questions (reintegration is no longer simply possible). We can even push the reflection further by arguing that in reality the model seeks to explain randomness, the only thing it does not control. Indeed, the model attempts to explore all possibilities, and ultimately it will do so deterministically (given a threshold of what is enough deterministic). But it can only explain after the fact the interaction between different modules. This encounter can be considered random at the local scale and as long as the model has not explored all possibilities for this encounter, it remains random at the global scale. In other words, the model does not locally control the randomness but can only constrain it globally. Randomness remains as an independent and irreducible variable.

The entire space evolves around randomness, which determines the possible relationships that are then used to extrapolate other parts of the space. The model can explore different as-yet-unmet interactions, but these explorations will always be relative to the interactions already encountered. Eventually, the model accumulates enough interactions to dynamically create a map for each interaction. At this point, the model can influence randomness through diffuse modular interaction causality, but it cannot directly control randomness itself or establish direct causal interactions. For example, the model could influence the trajectory of a person becoming wealthy through interactions with others or through people discovering their work (many macro-level interactions). However, it could not make them win a lottery, as that would require determining the specific winning numbers values that emerge directly from randomness itself. (At this scale, one could argue that the interactions between the numbers themselves might be influenced, but this example illustrates that beyond a certain threshold, the model cannot influence the actual values.) The distinction is critical: influencing outcomes requires only small perturbations around a random point, whereas direct control would require creating the random point itself. The model can architect what happens under certain circumstances, but it cannot determine which real circumstances will enable that path. For instance, diffusion processes or stochastic calculus can influence the trajectory of randomness, shaping where it tends to go, but they cannot alter the fundamental nature of randomness itself.

The model here does not seek to reduce noise or prediction error, but rather to reduce the lack of intrinsic information, specifically the relationships that have not yet been modeled. Noise associated with input data is considered merely as micro-adjustments at interaction points. The goal is not to denoise the variables, but simply to present the full set of possible interactions given the information available in the input data. The reduction or collapse of this information onto a specific path is not actually the concern of prediction itself, but rather of the preferences inherent to the dataset. In this architecture, we explicitly differentiate between these two layers: the interaction layer is not penalized by the collapse of preferences, while the preference layer represents only a reorganization of this space that operates on top of it in a decoupled manner. This aligns with world models but extends the conceptualization further.

Wolfram's results on the representation of physical laws via this structure also bring a possible link with physics (although still currently discussed). But here, it is not so much the link with our

physical universe that matters, but rather the ability to model different universes with their own rules each. Of course, any Turing complete system offers this possibility, simply the modeling in hypergraph offers a universal language. Where for example, a modeling in mathematical symbols (entirely feasible), would add an additional and possibly unstable layer.

4 Theoretical foundations

The central principle of PathThinker is to model information flow through internal trajectories across the network’s hidden states. By doing so, the network is no longer treated as a black box but as a system capable of self-reflection, allowing explicit internal adjustments to emerge naturally from changes in information flow rather than from opaque parameter updates.

The hypothesis is as follows: if a model can reflect upon its own internal pathways, adding new information or transformations becomes structurally manageable, as the network learns where and how to incorporate new elements without disrupting existing knowledge. This mechanism has the potential to bypass catastrophic forgetting and mimic the flexibility of adding an edge in a graph to encode a new relation or concept.

Although self-conditioning has been proposed as a related mechanism, used notably in diffusion models and large language models (LLMs) to preserve intermediate states across computational steps, it typically serves as a memory aid rather than a tool for self-organization. In essence, the network gains access to tools traditionally used post-training, such as trajectory visualization or attention-based diagnostics, but in real-time, during both learning and inference.

One might argue that models such as diffusion networks inherently learn a trajectory toward a target state, and that even LLMs progressively construct sequences of internal states to reach a coherent output. Indeed, techniques such as attention map analysis between layers already attempt to interpret shifts that could indicate uncertainty or semantic drift. However, these approaches do not solve fundamental issues like data efficiency, hallucination, or slow adaptation.

The distinction between PathThinker and existing approaches, such as self-conditioning or Mixture-of-Experts (MoE), which also dynamically adapt their internal structure based on the input, may appear subtle at first glance and could be interpreted as a reformulation of existing principles. However, we argue that this difference, while nuanced now, may lead to long-term benefits. PathThinker aims to understand and organize itself by explicitly modeling and externalizing its internal computation processes. The key idea is not merely to perform the computation, but to construct a virtual, introspectable model of the computation one that can be observed, analyzed, and altered.

Whether this constitutes a genuine methodological innovation or a novel perspective on existing paradigms remains an open question. Ultimately, empirical investigation is required to determine whether the conceptual distinctions introduced by PathThinker yield measurable advantages in learning efficiency, generalization, or adaptability.

PathThinker proposes to explicitly prioritize internal consistency and leverage this to construct meaningful trajectories. For instance, a single datapoint could be expanded into multiple hypothetical trajectories, each leading to the same outcome but differing in internal reasoning paths. By learning to group trajectories, assess state validity domains, and reject implausible hypotheses early, the network could become more effective at generalization and faster at discriminating incorrect inferences. This would reduce both the amount of training data required and the time to adapt to new information, as the model actively anticipates what should exist, before encountering it, rather than waiting to passively absorb examples.

This mechanism parallels classical model generalization, where training data shapes a loss landscape that enables interpolation. However, traditional models require extensive data to build such

landscapes. In contrast, recent approaches such as reinforcement learning in LLMs (e.g., DeepSeek [51]) and inference-time space exploration using Monte Carlo sampling in diffusion models [52] have shown that letting models make assumptions improves generalization. These methods allow the model to explore and validate multiple hypotheses instead of waiting for the solution.

Ultimately, most of the mechanisms PathThinker proposes already exist in modern architectures, but are either implicit (emerging from large-scale data exposure) or externalized at analysis. The novelty here lies in making these mechanisms explicit and internal, centered on strong assumptions validated when possible, rather than relying solely on data-driven discovery. This follows the paradigm of continuous meta-learning, where the model constantly evaluates without task segmentation [53] [54].

Given these principles, diffusion models emerge as a natural foundation for PathThinker. Their design inherently involves trajectory learning, and their slow, iterative nature makes them less prone to catastrophic forgetting, provided that the distributional shift between data instances is not extreme. Moreover, their training objective always, focused on recovering a trajectory, aligns with the core objective of PathThinker.

5 Architecture overview

5.1 Dual-Flow design

Building upon our initial concept of PathThinker [3], we propose a refined architectural formulation based on a dual-flow design, wherein computation is explicitly separated into two distinct but interacting flows :

- Execution flow : this flow is responsible for describing the outcome of the reasoning process in a form that is interpretable with respect to the input and/or output space. It encodes what the model is doing at each state, semantically, without driving the internal computation itself.
- Reasoning flow: this flow handles the trajectory of the internal computation. Its objective is not to produce the final result, but to achieve internal consistency across states, a self-referential logic independent of the target objective.

The core idea of this design is to decouple the final result (execution) from the underlying computational trace (reasoning). In this formulation, the execution flow becomes a passive structure, one that only describes what is happening internally. In a multimodal setup, the external semantic representations will be aligned with the internal trajectories, while preserving their integrity across the different contexts.

To implement this, we introduce a companion model to manage the execution flow, and a trajectory-based model to manage the reasoning flow. We identify two architectural strategies for coordinating these flows (see figure 15):

- Direct data access : this approach gives the trajectory model full access to raw input through conditioning, enabling high-resolution reasoning. However, it poses challenges for multimodal scalability, as introducing new modalities may destabilize previously learned representations.
- Indirect data access : in this setup, the trajectory model receives input indirectly, through the semantic representations produced by the companion model. While this improves stability across modalities, it may limit the model’s access to fine-grained data features.

Figure 15: Architecture overview of dual flow design

5.2 Companion model

For the companion model, we adopt the Perceiver architecture [55], which uses a latent array iteratively updated based on conditioned input. This structure can be interpreted as a discrete analogue to a diffusion process. Its key advantage lies in its robustness to distributional shifts across inference steps, making it suitable for recursive application similar to how diffusion models evolve over time.

Indeed, on early diffusion steps diffusion models heavily rely on the conditioned data and with it occurs distinct attention patterns over the conditioned input [56, 57, 58]. Capturing and interpreting these patterns meaningfully, which rely on the input semantic, demands to begin from a semantically meaningful state instead of purely noise.

While direct access to input data could bypass the need for such a companion model, the purpose here is to enable out-of-context hypothesis exploration. For this, we require a mechanism that interprets each intermediate state and allows reconditioning of the diffusion model in altered contexts. However, it is critical to note that this mechanism remains passive : the companion model does not govern the reasoning flow, it only describes it.

As with many architectures inspired by Perceiver, this setup encounters challenges with causality masking. However, in PathThinker, the trajectory model is not intended to handle token-level details. Instead, it operates at the sentence or concept level, delegating fine-grained processing to the companion model. This approach echoes the design philosophy behind the Large Concept Model (LCM) [59], which uses the SONAR architecture (an encoder–decoder that maps multi-lingual sentences into a shared, fixed-size representation) to encode and decode concepts tokens. LCM then applies diffusion in this concept space to predict future sentence-level concepts.

However, PathThinker introduces a deeper integration : unlike LCM, which uses SONAR as a frozen transformer, our architecture entangles the reasoning and execution flows directly from token level. The resulting structure is closer to the two-tower architecture of LCM, where both towers (companion and trajectory models) operate in parallel, with the trajectory model guiding

reasoning and the companion model generating descriptive semantic representations in the input or output space.

Moreover, the training of the companion model is tied to that of the trajectory model, which provides the global gradient update direction. The companion model can then refine this direction locally based on its current state, as long as the deviation remains within a predefined threshold.

6 Training strategies

6.1 Downstream training

In the PathThinker framework, the companion model is never trained across its full temporal axis. Propagating gradients from the target back to the initial input of the companion model would violate the core design principle: that the trajectory model governs the internal flow, while the companion model describes it. Maintaining this separation is crucial to preserving the architectural and functional distinction between reasoning and execution flows. We identify two possible modes for training :

- Diffusion model output : in this mode, the target is applied directly to the final state of the diffusion-based reasoning model, just before a projection layer. Standard diffusion training procedures can then be used to generate the intermediate steps.
- Companion model output : this mode aligns more naturally with the architecture’s intended semantics, where the companion model generates the output. However, it presents a significant challenge : how to train without backpropagating through the full temporal unrolling of the companion model, which would contradict the decoupling principle and impose prohibitive computational costs.

In the first case, training is straightforward: we apply gradient descent on the final state of the diffusion model (the last latent), and standard diffusion training is used to generate the intermediate steps as usual.

In the second case, training becomes more challenging because we want to avoid backpropagation through the entire sequence of steps in the companion model. To address this, we propose a multi-scale prediction strategy, where the diffusion model is trained to skip intermediate steps. Especially, we want to train to model to perform single-step generation. This allows us to perform gradient descent only on that single step. The companion model will describe this single step by taking the initial latent array and produce the output, which will allow us to take gradient on the whole single step to find the appropriate output state the diffusion model need to be in order to produce the desired output. We then can resume standard diffusion training to refine the full multi-step reasoning process.

We also train the model to skip varying numbers of steps, which enables gradient propagation on only a subset of intermediate states and ensure continuity between portion of the full step process. This should improves training stability while still maintaining coherence in the full trajectory.

6.2 Continuity training

6.2.1 Landscape continuity

A central component of the PathThinker architecture lies in the way trajectories are trained to induce structured reasoning and measure internal consistency. Continuity is a natural subset of consistency in trajectory-based reasoning. We seek not only smooth transitions between steps within a diffusion process but also semantic continuity across contexts, as such links reflect the underlying structure between concepts.

However, achieving context-independent continuity is inherently challenging. It requires modeling unconditional structure in the latent space and the ability to locate an input’s position in that space on an absolute rather than purely relative basis. Score-based diffusion models approximate the gradient of the log of the conditional distribution, offering a partial ability to navigate this distributional space, but this alone is insufficient for rich, globally consistent reasoning.

We consider the following strategies for achieving usable trajectory continuity :

- **Explicit landscape** : in this approach, at each timestep, the model outputs an explicit representation of a local probability landscape within a predefined perimeter of latent space. Manual gradients are then computed on this landscape to guide diffusion, resuming standard score-based optimization. This method forces the output representation to be both navigable and interpretable, essentially loading a "local map" of the distribution at each step, which we then can enforce geometric consistency through movement across the map.
- **Recursive landscape** : this approach leverages a discrete set of learnable directions (e.g., left, right, center), with recursive capabilities. At each timestep, the model selects a direction and can recursively dive into sub-directions within that region. This structure resembles fractal geometry, where a compact set of recursive rules can generate complex patterns. The recursive landscape thus encodes rich internal structure while maintaining a compact directional framework. It’s for example use to organize elements [60] or for procedural generation of map through recursive navigation. Each timestep can thus use a variable number of iterations, and the discretization of the latent space around predefined waypoints improves trajectory predictability. When new information is introduced, it follows a descending spiral-like update, enabling localized modifications without disrupting the global structure, a step toward more stable and non-destructive learning.
- **Virtual landscape** : this approach models the space as a graph where nodes are attractor. Each node defines its own local region, effectively a "patch" of the latent landscape, and determines the reachable neighboring nodes based on continuous transition scores. This hybrid structure combines the global control of graphs with the local smoothness of continuous landscapes. Conceptually, this virtual landscape provides a bridge between trajectory-based reasoning and graph-structured knowledge representation. This approach is more of a conceptual reformulation than a strictly technical implementation, but it provides a basis for establishing, through formal proof yet to be made, an equivalence between landscape-based and graph-based representations.

We adopt the virtual landscape model for its simplicity and flexibility, especially its natural ability to support asynchronous updates between nodes, since each node can maintain its own view of the graph. This is crucial in decentralized systems, where parts of the model may update independently or propagate changes at different rates.

In practice, for a given input, the model generates a trajectory to reach the desired output state. This trajectory, or sub-trajectory in a multi-scale setup, becomes a node in the reasoning graph. From this node, surrounding nodes can be generated, allowing to switch between contexts, free from the actual conditioning on the input. By exploring the neighborhood of nodes within the virtual landscape, we can enforce a form of continuity through various mechanisms, which will be detailed in subsequent sections of this paper.

Also, by training the model to skip steps, not only does it learn to interpolate missing information in the trajectory space, but it also gains the ability to reconstruct, recognize, and connect different parts of the sequence. Nodes may thus represent different granularities, complete trajectories, sub-sequences, or individual steps, providing a flexible unit for hypothesis modeling.

This node-based continuity framework forms the foundation for hypothesis generation and reasoning in PathThinker.

6.2.2 Continuity measure

Measuring the continuity of a trajectory in a high-dimensional representation space remains a challenging problem. Existing methods typically approach this issue from the perspective of hallucination detection, identifying semantic or structural inconsistencies in model outputs, often by observing internal states rather than solely relying on output tokens. Notable approaches include:

- EigenScore [61], which evaluates semantic consistency in dense embedding spaces by analyzing the eigenvalues of response covariance matrices.
- MIND [62], a model that trains a hallucination detector on Wikipedia articles by using partial context to predict remaining content, not through output tokens, but via the contextualized hidden states.
- Hidden state analysis [63], showing that models can exhibit measurable uncertainty patterns between known and unknown queries, detectable prior to output generation.
- Spectral attention analysis [64], where attention maps are interpreted as weighted adjacency matrices, and their Laplacian eigenvalues are used to detect semantic drift or hallucination.
- Entropy-based estimators [65, 66], designed to assess semantic uncertainty in generated outputs, focusing on the underlying meaning rather than surface text coherence.

These methods collectively demonstrate that hallucinations, seen as semantic discontinuities, can be detected in real time by analyzing the behavior of internal states against known patterns. This observation supports the hypothesis that trajectory continuity can also be measured relatively using techniques analogous to regularization via prototype matching or validation against neighboring query, in addition to scoring method on attention map.

This aligns with mechanisms already implemented in PathThinker, particularly through the use of unnormalized attention scores within trajectory groups, a technique that we will expand upon in subsequent sections of this paper. Indeed, distortions or irregularities in these scores can indicate attempts to force a trajectory to conform to a group to which it does not naturally belong. These distortions could also be captured more robustly by training a dedicated policy to detect them in an integrated manner.

Furthermore, if hallucinations, or more generally discontinuities, can be identified from hidden states, then they can also be conceptualized as trajectories themselves. In this formulation, it becomes a policy that the model can learn to recognize, much like MIND, but extended to support continuous learning without accessing to reference dataset but by using each real data seen.

Ultimately, all internal behaviors of the model, whether regular or aberrant, can be conceptualized as trajectories. This perspective enables the model to track, detect, and respond to its own reasoning dynamics in real time. Additionally, this framework can be further strengthened by analyzing shifts in attention maps, where sudden or erratic changes may reveal points of discontinuity, complementing the detection of semantic drift at the trajectory level.

6.3 Trajectory training

6.3.1 Grouping

While step-skipping and trajectory building provide important components for reasoning, they are not sufficient to induce robust reasoning strategies. To achieve structured generalization, we require a stateful approach, in which the trajectory at a given timestep depends not only on the current input but also on the entire sequence of prior steps.

However, this breaks the Markov assumption that underlies diffusion processes and is computationally prohibitive in most settings. Traditional architectures circumvent this limitation by

maintaining contextual memory, using RNNs or attention mechanisms to propagate prior state information.

In PathThinker, we retain contextual information using hierarchical representations, as in predictive coding frameworks, U-Net architectures, or recent Kolmogorov-inspired models [67]. These architectures act as implicit memory systems, and serve as viable alternatives to full backpropagation through time.

We propose trajectory grouping, which serves a dual role: (1) as a hierarchical representation, and (2) as a contextualized replay learning. The quality of this mechanism depends directly on the richness and diversity of the grouping strategy. We propose learning a grouping policy that clusters trajectories based on the variability among relative sub-trajectories within a group. The underlying objective is to enable the model to discover structural and semantic similarity between trajectories representing distinct objects.

6.3.2 Single-step trajectory grouping

To simplify the explanation, we first consider the 1-step trajectory case. In this setup :

- A group representation of a trajectory s_0 is defined as the output of the companion model when conditioned on itself, on s_0 .
- The group representation is then used to condition again the model and generate diverse sub-trajectories, which theoretically include s_0 but in practice exhaustive sampling will not be possible.
- The sub-trajectories :
 - Share high attention score similarity with the group representation.
 - Maintain high variability among themselves.

The goal of the grouping policy is to maximize attention alignment between sub-trajectories and the group representation, while also preserving intra-group diversity. We can see group as restricted subspace/axis where the trajectories appears relatively the same. Importantly, we do not aim to align all sub-trajectory representations, as this would collapse the space and destroy diversity. Optionally, a decreasing variability factor over time may be introduced to account for embedding space convergence.

6.3.3 Formal definition

Let :

- M : Trajectory model
- C : Companion model
- π_c : Grouping policy
- s_0 : Base trajectory
- G : Group representation
- $S = \{s_0, s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$: Sub-trajectories generated from G
- A : Attention score function (e.g., dot product)
- V : Variability measure over S (e.g., KL divergence)

We define:

$$s_G = C|(M|(s_0, \epsilon_i))$$

$$S = \{s_i | s_i = M(s_G, \epsilon_i), i \in [1, n]\}$$

with $\epsilon_i \approx N(0, 1)$ to handle variability.

Our training objective is to maximize:

$$\alpha \times A(S, G) + \beta \times V(S)$$

subject to :

$$\begin{aligned} \forall i, j, |A(s_i, s_g) - A(s_j, s_g)| &\leq \delta \\ V(S) &\geq \tau \\ \forall i \neq j, \|s_i - s_j\| &\geq d \end{aligned}$$

To reduce computational cost, pairwise comparisons are approximated by computing averages and ensuring distributional regularity (i.e., avoiding dominant outliers). The grouping mechanism resembles Variance-Invariance-Covariance (VIC) Regularization [68], but adapted to use attention as the core alignment metric.

Note that the same set of trajectories S may belong to multiple groups, with some groupings being more probable due to frequency or consistency of use.

Moreover, we can replace standard sampling from $N(0, 1)$ with classifier-free guidance, where the model is encouraged not to produce a trajectory from the same direction (distributional region) to encourage exploration of diverse regions of the group space. This is a form of guided negative sampling, grounded in diffusion dynamics.

6.3.4 Multi-step trajectory grouping

The challenge of multi-step grouping lies in the alignment of trajectories with different lengths steps and semantic resolutions.

If a group encodes a high-level concept (e.g., faces), intermediate steps may correspond to subconcepts (e.g., eyes, mouth, nose). However, these may not align temporally across different trajectories-step i in one trajectory may correspond to step j in another.

To resolve this, we propose using attention mechanisms between long and short trajectories to distribute representation across steps, enabling soft alignment of semantic units despite differing step counts.

6.3.5 Knowledge graph construction from groups

Each group represents a subspace of the embedding space, a point of view where trajectory representations converge. Unlike traditional embedding methods that seek a single unified representation, here each group anchors a local subspace, and explicit relationship between space region. The result is an embedding space that is structurally meaningful, where subspaces are linked by navigable paths, essentially forming a knowledge graph over embedding space.

This is conceptually analogous to self-attention, where tokens are connected based on learned filters. However, in PathThinker, this connectivity is made explicit, and trajectories provide a continuous path between these subspaces.

Unlike static vector operations in conventional embedding spaces, PathThinker models the embedding dynamics, allowing navigation and reasoning even without input or context, via learned internal structure. This makes it possible to visualize and traverse the space much like navigating a knowledge graph.

One could argue that architectures such as Perceiver already offer similar behavior, since they operate over a learned latent array and can express inter-pattern relationships through evolving attention maps. Additionally, shifts in attention direction can reveal trajectory dynamics. However, in PathThinker, these mechanisms serve a dedicated purpose : ensuring continuity, enforcing structure, and enabling post-hoc interpretability through explicit, knowledge-like rules. Whereas attention manipulation in Perceiver to follow different link often requires manual tweaking or gradient-based probing, PathThinker incorporates these operations natively, autonomously switching attention modes and ignoring invalid or distorted patterns without external supervision. PathThinker avoids the combinatorial explosion associated with endlessly tweaking attention maps or manipulating the probability distribution at the classification head by learning which combinations are meaningful, and focusing only on those that contribute to consistent and interpretable reasoning.

6.4 Multi-scale training

As previously discussed, PathThinker operates across multiple scales, not merely by skipping steps, but by implementing hierarchical representations that enable reasoning at varying levels of abstraction. Handling multi-scale trajectories encourages shared representations across intermediate steps, improving generalization and memory efficiency.

6.4.1 Multi-scale approximation

In Monte Carlo-style approaches to diffusion [52], step skipping is used to approximate the outcomes of alternative trajectories. This allows early decisions regarding which trajectories to explore, when to stop, and where to branch, often relying on backpropagation as a selection mechanism. In contrast, PathThinker replaces this with an internal policy, generated and refined by the model itself, enabling autonomous control over trajectory selection and termination without requiring gradient-based inference mechanisms.

6.4.2 Divide-and-Conquer

Under our architecture, trajectories can be distributed across semantic scopes : one trajectory may focus on edges, another on facial features, another on entire scenes. In other words, a whole trajectory can only focus of specific element and not the whole output as in standard diffusion or Monte Carlo approach.

Then entire output can then be produced by combining trajectories, not manually, but by conditioning the model on the global context. Computing a trajectory from scratch is expensive; however, once it has been generated, it can be reused as a "hot start" and simply adjusted [69, 70, 71]. In other words, once a full trajectory has been computed, its final result can be used to condition the model and serve as a seed to produce adjusted behavior with significantly fewer steps. The idea is that by computing a full trajectory we have the global gradient on which we can rely to skip steps, knowing approximately what should be at the start and more heavily rely on last step to adjust.

For example, in simple inpainting method for image, the region to be modified typically restarts from noise, requiring a full trajectory while enforcing no, or minimal, changes to the rest of the image. But if we begin with the complete image, generate the direction for the required adjustment in a single step (which by design in our architecture we will have as discussed in more detail later in this paper, but which aligned with some approach [72, 73]), we can use this information to skip the initial steps and directly refine the affected patch.

Moreover, by adding a learnable parameter, the model can also infer how many steps to skip, starting from the beginning when strong modifications are needed, or closer to the end when only

minor adjustments are required.

By systematically using the exploration method and single-step reasoning during training, we can induce a structural decoupling of the actual early steps of the trajectory handle abstract structure, and later steps refine details, to let any step doing what is needed. This should results in a more flexible, modular, and computationally efficient model.

6.4.3 Early stopping

A remaining challenge is how to determine when to stop exploring a trajectory. The Monte Carlo diffusion methods address this by estimating progress between a current state and the final objective, often by skipping steps and evaluating similarity. One advantage of this approach is that it operates purely at inference time, without requiring architectural modification or additional training. Which mean we can use such method without specific training objective. However, we could also extend this with a learned internal policy which can approximate early stopping decisions based on the dynamics of the reasoning process in progress, in order to halt without the need to perform the actual skipped computation.

This significantly reduces the computational cost of detail-oriented trajectory generation. While the Monte Carlo approach introduces notable overhead due to branching and sampling, we argue that by using a multi-scale approach, being able to compress steps, this overhead becomes manageable and even advantageous in a decentralized, modular system. Moreover, existing techniques already aim to accelerate the Monte Carlo process in diffusion models [74].

6.4.4 Hierarchical decomposition

In diffusion models, early steps typically encode abstract structures, e.g. object placement and composition, while later steps refine fine-grained details. The goal of the multi-scale mechanism in PathThinker is to go further : rather than enforcing a strict top-down abstraction-to-detail sequence, we allow each trajectory to focus on specific elements. This design enables the model to decompose the problem space into parallel, detail-focused reasoning pathways while maintaining a shared global context. In essence, the model evolves from a traditional bottom-up layer architecture to bottom-up network, where the whole network is employ to represent bottom feature, parallelized them as if the input signal exists in wave function, and iterate over the whole network to produce abstracted representation.

This means that the model learns to compute hierarchically, where the single-step method effectively carries the abstracted hierarchical features. Coupled with the exploration policy, it drives the decision to either extend a trajectory, create a new one, or terminate it. In our setup, this mechanism serves as a way to allocate more computational resources to certain details, to merge them when needed, and to decide whether additional reasoning is required.

There should be no need for specific training to induce this behavior, as the model’s roles during both training and inference naturally give rise to such effects.

The single-step method, in particular, is the one that will have access to the global context during the graph exploration and then can decide what to do next, while finer details are processed in parallel, with the same model but focus on their specific trajectory.

Grouping already serves as an abstraction mechanism, since it encodes higher-level concepts, such as the notion of a circle or a face even when their outputs cannot be directly compared due to variations in position, color, or other local features. This is precisely where cross-attention comes in, allowing the model to align representations beyond surface-level variations.

Moreover, the single-step model does not intervene at every stage of computation, but rather operates periodically across trajectories, either to evaluate completed ones or to decide whether a given trajectory can be stopped early.

Therefore, hierarchical abstraction is already an emergent property of the architecture. It’s the same model architecture used across all levels, but its effect varies depending on whether it’s applied in single-step mode, group mode, or full-trajectory mode. The single-step mode is particularly relevant because it is the least expensive to compute and serves as the default strategy for generating an initial global representation of a group, which can later be extended. This makes it both a technical and conceptual design choice.

Additionally, our architecture supports a dual-mode reasoning process akin to fast and slow thinking : producing a quick approximate answer in one or a few steps, and then optionally extending that reasoning for verification. One of the model’s key objectives is to converge as quickly as possible, ideally providing the correct answer immediately in single or few steps.

Finally, the companion model handles the refinement based on the specific characteristics of the input and output spaces, effectively offloading it from the trajectory model, which can then focus on structural reasoning.

This paradigm aligns with approaches proposed in recent works on hierarchical and modular reasoning architectures [75, 76, 77, 78, 79, 80].

6.4.5 Layer-wise

While the original design of PathThinker was focused on hidden states of standard models, we found that testing these ideas was more tractable in stable models like diffusion, where intermediate steps are explicit and interpretable. Nonetheless, the principles generalize to hidden state in model. For instance, model layers can be treated as trajectory steps, either through: single-layer recurrence, where a single layer is applied multiple times [81, 82]. Or through dedicated layers, with the ability to skip or dynamically select layers [83, 84, 85].

In PathThinker, because the model can focus on either general abstraction or fine-grained detail, the layers involved in different trajectories (e.g., detail-focused vs. general-focused) can cross-attend to one another. This allows all pathways to operate in a shared hidden state space, enabling interoperability between semantic space, a concept explored in emerging research [86].

6.5 Reasoning training

A core challenge in PathThinker lies in how to ensure both consistency and validity of the reasoning process. These two notions must be treated independently, as a trajectory can be internally coherent (i.e., logically consistent) while remaining factually invalid.

To address this, we rely on three core signals:

- Trajectory continuity
- Attention coverage of the input
- Reversibility of the reasoning process

6.5.1 Trajectory reversibility learning

We propose the reasoning process forward-reverse-horizontal-iterate (FRHI) both used in training and inference :

- (Forward) Given an input, the model generates a forward trajectory.
- (Reverse) Using the final state representation and the input, the model attempts to reconstruct the trajectory in reverse.

- (Horizontal) The reconstructed trajectory is compared with the original, and the gap between the two is minimized through finding a trajectory between the two.
- (Iterate) The process is iterated.

This mechanism reflects the fact that initial trajectories are built incrementally with limited information about the final goal. Each step is a guess that accumulates approximation errors, detours, or local ambiguities. Since multiple next steps may appear plausible from a local perspective, errors can compound along the path.

Once the final state is reached, the model is given access to both the start and the endpoint representation, and asked to reconstruct a more globally optimized trajectory, mitigating previous uncertainty and error accumulation. This is conceptually similar to first navigating through unknown streets toward a destination, and then retracing the same path while now knowing where you’re going, thus choosing a more direct or consistent route.

The reverse trajectory mechanism is inspired by the concept of Reinforcement Learning Teachers (RLT) [87]. RLT models act as teacher agents that receive both a question and its solution, and are trained to generate step-by-step explanations that connect the two, effectively ”filling in the gaps.” These models are optimized not for solving problems from scratch, but for their teaching effectiveness, using dense reward signals based on how well a student model learns from the generated explanations. This approach mitigates exploration related challenges and even allows smaller teacher models to outperform larger models when generating high-quality training data. In PathThinker, the teacher and student are the same model, applied both during training and inference. This unified setup allows the model to self-generate reverse trajectories, improving reasoning consistency and interpretability without requiring external supervision.

We see that the companion model is multi-functional: it must represent the output space, but also be able to represent the trajectory from the input space perspective. It operates in an intermediate zone that describes what the trajectory model is doing. This means that, when conditioned, the model asks itself whether the output answers the input. But when unconditioned, the model asks what question the output raises, or begins to include some context from the input within its output to understand where the reasoning starts. As a result, the current architecture is particularly suited for tasks where the input and output spaces are shared, or for self-supervised setups, where the output signal only weakly aligns with the representation of the output, but is still expressed in the language of the input.

The model could also be tempted to cheat given the endpoint. Thus the reconstructed trajectory is then match against it group representation, and the unnormalized relative attention score required to follow it is measured. If the score deviates significantly from the expected pattern of sub-trajectories in that group, this signals either: a malformed trajectory, or an artificial adjustment made to fit the group representation.

This brings forward the possibility that the model cheats by producing a ”centric” group representation that overfits a single trajectory. To prevent this, group validity must be judged relatively, across a broader context of neighboring groups.

6.5.2 Trajectory ranking via neighborhood exploration

If we consider the model as a graph builder, then the validity of a trajectory (node) can be evaluated based on its neighborhood and its resemblance to previously seen data. We argue that the only available form of validation is what the model remembers, and how different or distant a new trajectory appears to be, essentially how much effort it would take to connect the current

node to memory. For example, we can validate a trajectory if it aligns with different subspace of multiple real memories representation. Validity becomes a matter of relative familiarity, rather than absolute correctness. This leads to a graph-based perspective on validity, similar to how PageRank evaluates the relevance of a web page, like :

- how connected it is.
- how often it is referenced.
- its place in loops or frequent pathways.
- how central it is to the structure.

A trajectory validity can be judged by

- how well it fit it's group representation
- how simple it is to access the base trajectory from top-level hierarchical representation.
- how simple it is compare to its neighbors.

Absolute validity is practically challenging. Even with a perfect validity landscape, we would still need to interpret it through local comparisons, to understand how a point relates to its neighbors in meaning and structure. Trajectory grouping naturally supports this principle : it builds hierarchical abstractions that point toward more common, well-structured, or reusable representations. The higher we move in the hierarchy, the more likely we are to reach a known structure, and the less likely we are to overfit a group to a specific, isolated, distorted trajectory.

This is conceptually related to sampling methods in diffusion, which approximate the partition function to estimate the probability of a path, not individually, but relative to a larger landscape. PathThinker follows a similar principle, but instead of estimating probability, it forces the model to organize its space hierarchically and to navigate smoothly from one context to another.

However, implementing such an algorithm is computationally expensive, particularly in online or real-time inference contexts. Additionally, we face cold-start challenges, where a significant number of initial trajectories may be required before the ranking signal becomes reliable, and slow convergence rates may limit its responsiveness.

Alternatively, simpler strategies can be employed, such as Process Reward Models (PRMs) that validate reasoning step-by-step, or mechanisms based on multi-sample generation followed by voting to approximate consensus. However, it is important to note that even models which natively estimate solution landscapes still require local exploration to evaluate the actual quality of a solution. In many cases, these models can follow a smooth trajectory through the landscape that converges toward an attractor, but the path itself may be semantically invalid, even if it is structurally continuous.

6.5.3 Trajectory transfer learning

In our setup, the trajectory from the initial to the reconstructed one is quite semantically different (while technically describing the same object), since it represents a trajectory between two trajectories. If the trajectory from input to output is considered a vertical trajectory, then the one connecting two such trajectories can be seen as a horizontal trajectory. Some approach align with that notion of bridging the gap between trajectories [72, 73].

The horizontal trajectory represents transfer learning : how to apply knowledge from one domain to another, how to connect domains, or how to reuse techniques across domains. However,

if we simply use both trajectories to produce a third one that helps transform the first, the model is highly prone to cheating (for example by simply producing a trajectory that is the sum of both). To counter this, we do not provide the model with the horizontal trajectory directly, but rather with its group representation (the most probable groups by sampling). Then, using the initial trajectory and this guiding group, which indicates how to transform it, the model generates a new trajectory. This process can be iterated using other likely group representations of the horizontal trajectory to incrementally add missing information (see figure 16).

Figure 16: Schema of the horizontal trajectory process

During training, we compare the obtained trajectory with the trajectory produced using the full horizontal one, and adjust it to match. At the same time, we ensure that using the full horizontal trajectory leads to the closest possible match with the desired trajectory. This prevents the model from losing information by simply aligning to the horizontal trajectory to the group one, which would contradict the group policy, specifically that no sub-trajectory should match too closely with the group representation.

The trajectory transformation is not an explicit manipulation. Instead, we condition the model on both the source trajectory and guiding information in order to let it perform the transformation. While it's possible to consider manual manipulation (e.g. a simple vector addition), this may be too reductive and perform poorly, since it would require both identifying the parts of the initial trajectory to preserve, and defining exactly how to modify them. We could alternatively consider that the model outputs trajectories in terms of Key (K), Query (Q), and Value (V) vectors, which we could manipulate directly. This might give more control and reduce the chances of cheating, but would likely be harder to implement and stabilize, with uncertain benefit.

We can think of a horizontal trajectory G as follows:

- We define a vector G' such that, for source trajectory A and target trajectory B , which can be expressed as single vector, we have :

$$\text{score}_{att}(A, G') \approx \text{score}_{att}(B, G')$$

- We compute θ , the angle between A and B
- In a nearly normalized space of dimension n , we compute:

$$G = (\cos(\theta) + \epsilon) \times G'$$

The idea is that in low-dimensional (or sparse) spaces, such as those encouraged by grouping, which focuses on specific subspaces, given A and G' , we can find a good approximation of B by solving and optimization process decomposing G' in θ and G in order to find an approximation of B .

Conceptually, groups for vertical trajectories enforce semantic clustering, representing how a trajectory is structured. And horizontal trajectories add directionality to know how trajectory are related. But both share the property $\text{score}_{att}(A, G') \approx \text{score}_{att}(B, G')$.

We do not enforce this constraint explicitly. The only requirement is that, given A and G , the model should be able to reach B , while avoiding to simply produce an abstract version of B (by enforcing diversity between B and G), which will defeat the explicit formulation of the transformation by doing in internally.

6.5.4 Role of reverse trajectory

The role of reverse trajectory in this architecture is crucial, as it introduces a double-bind mechanism :

- The model generates a trajectory based on its input and input and/or trajectory context.
- The model then re-evaluates that trajectory in a decontextualized setting.

By "context", we mean not just the input (which remains available), but more specifically what happens after the initial trajectory, the continuation, the updates, the refinements, which increasingly influences the outcome each time the model tries to reach a new state from the same input.

Moreover, our architecture is structurally asymmetrical by design: We can construct a trajectory from A to B, but that trajectory does not inherently encode the reverse path from B to A. Horizontal trajectories are unidirectional transformations as they describe how to convert one trajectory into another. This asymmetry is intentional, especially in the context of decentralized networks, where updates are local and propagated asynchronously. In such a setup, we can update the path from A to B without altering B to A, which may be managed by a different node.

Reverse trajectory provides a powerful tool to address this structural asymmetry. By generating reverse trajectories, the model can explore alternative origins for a given state, asking from what other direction this state could have been reached. This helps the model reason about symmetrical or reversible relationships, even in an architecture that does not enforce symmetry by default.

Furthermore, since the companion model relies on a fixed-size latent array conditioned on both input and output, it could help mitigate asymmetry at a global/abstracted level, even if it would not enforce token-level symmetry.

6.5.5 Input coverage

Input coverage is also an important component of the reasoning strategy. Once the model has produced an initial guess, it refines this result through iterations, aiming to improve the match between input and output. One way to assess this is by evaluating how well the output “responds” to the input. While this is part of the overall fitness score done through the FRHI, we can also complement it by analyzing which parts of the input are actually taken into account by the generated trajectory.

For instance, if a trajectory focuses on only a few elements from the input, it could mean:

- Those elements are the only relevant ones.
- Some parts of the input were (intentionally or not) ignored.
- The model failed to properly integrate all input information.

This idea aligns with Lookback Lens [88], which measures the ratio of attention given to the input context versus attention to previously generated tokens. It aims to reduce hallucination, based on the observation that both humans and models prone to hallucination tend to focus more on their own prior thoughts than on the original input.

Here, we extract the cumulative attention scores between trajectory steps and the input tokens that gives a view of which input segments the model focused on. And based on this, we can: force an attention mask on the overlooked parts of the input and generate a new trajectory specifically focusing on those.

If the new trajectory follows a similar direction to the initial one (or at least doesn’t contradict it. The notion of trajectory contradiction is detailed later in this paper), it may indicate that the initial solution aligns well with the full input. But if the trajectories diverge significantly or lead to concepts that are difficult to reconcile (e.g., requiring many FRHI iterations to connect), this could signal either: a problematic input (e.g., containing contradictions), or that the current chosen solution is not optimal.

We can then explore whether all generated trajectories can be aligned toward a common direction or merged into a shared conceptual solution, ideally requiring fewer iterations and yielding higher continuity scores.

6.5.6 Hypothesis generation

Being able to generate hypotheses is a central concept that we believe should reduce data usage. A hypothesis should be:

- Predictive (it predicts something)
- Testable (it is verifiable)
- Falsifiable (it is refutable)

In our setup, hypotheses are also part of the grouping strategy. A hypothesis occurs both when grouping trajectories and when creating horizontal trajectories between groups. Hypotheses heavily rely on abstracted representations through groups, because individual hypotheses are less useful and impactful. The goal in this architecture is to make strong assumptions about the relations between data, diversify these assumptions, and validate some of them later when new data are encountered.

Hypothesis in out setup :

- predict something : either that it was justifiable to group trajectories together (based on something we thought was common/shared by the trajectories), or that it was justifiable to create a link between groups/concepts.
- are verifiable, since when new data is encountered, we check whether it allows us to reach the target, either directly or indirectly.
- are falsifiable, since the model must produce both a group or horizontal trajectory and a trajectory that invalidates them (what links should not exist if the group is supposed valid).

The falsifying trajectory is a horizontal trajectory that allows reaching one group trajectory from another, but produces orthogonal representations on both groups. If we take again the formulation of horizontal trajectories explained before, the system still works if the group vector G is orthogonal to start trajectory A and end trajectory B , since in the attention mechanism, the vectors will be transformed and orthogonal of raw vector should not affect them.

Thus, the horizontal trajectory construction remains the same, but we add one constraint on the group raw vectors. Then, when following trajectories, we can evaluate if they should not be followed, meaning it's a known forbidden link (see figure 17). That also with such trajectory that we can map contradiction between trajectories, and spot part of discontinuity.

Figure 17: Conceptual schema falsifiable link

However, an invalidating trajectory is not as straightforward. First, we can encode falsifiable links between two groups, but if the trajectory needs support from more groups to be provable, we will not be able to encode such a relation. This means that invalidating a link will be a local invalidation. Moreover, we cannot erase/forget the group once supposedly invalidated, since it would create instability in the training and continuity process.

But, this compensates for another issue, the attribution problem : the grouping could be valid, but the validity condition (i.e., the falsifiable link) could be invalid. Consequently, invalidating a falsifiable link does not necessarily mean the hypothesis is wrong, but that the policy generating it

could be. What we can then do is train a policy to construct falsifiable links for a group, and when a falsifiable link is proven false (i.e., the link predicts that group A cannot exist if group B exists, but we observe data where both exist), the policy is updated on whether it correctly identified the validity domain of the group.

Moreover, not erasing the trajectory immediately helps stabilize the training of the policy and preserves previous mistakes as examples (thus acting like a repulsor in the landscape). The erasure of the group will happen over time when updating the model, where we simply stop enforcing the trajectory to remain.

Furthermore, reusing for new data a group that turns out to be a dead end, based through neighbor exploration could help identify incorrect reasoning. In this context, a dead-end group is a group nearly isolated group from which we can not really goes elsewhere because of the falsifiable link accumulating.

This is a crucial component in reasoning : the ability to remember errors and build corrections upon them. For example, we may have opposing concepts (e.g., left, right), which result in embeddings in opposite directions, but it's more challenging to encode negative relations (what should not exist). This is a form of contrastive learning with negative sampling, but here, the model generates the negative pairs itself through a policy and filters them later using positive pairs. Negative sampling is known to be unstable and slows convergence, partly because negative samples often carry positive information [89, 90]. This requires further exploration.

Another important aspect of hypothesis is how to differentiate them from real validated trajectories or generalized trajectories. And one advantage of horizontal trajectories is that they are context-dependent : we always start from one trajectory to go to another. Thus, we can leverage this to discriminate between hypotheses and facts (once hypotheses are confirmed by data/used to solve the input-output). By progressively updating the model to reproduce horizontal trajectories when validated but this time decontextualized (i.e., without a conditioned on another trajectory), we now have two ways to generate the same trajectory. The more likely a hypothesis is, the more probable the reverse trajectory during FRHI will also be, because reverse trajectory remain mostly decontextualized from other trajectories.

Nonetheless, both probabilities are implicit, as in diffusion models, and we still need to differentiate the probability of a hypothesis confirmed indirectly (e.g., by validating falsifiable paths, solving the problem using other parts of the trajectory graph, or finding that part of the graph reaches the target as an alternative path). One possible solution is by enforcing the model to lean toward these context-dependent trajectories, through conditioning, we generate implicit distributions, which can be measured by how much contextual guidance the model needs to lean toward one trajectory. That is : how many intermediate steps must be given to the model to reconstruct a trajectory, or starting from nearby trajectories, does it naturally converge to the correct one.

6.5.7 Replay Learning

Replay learning plays a crucial role in this architecture, as it allows for continuous meta-learning, the generation of hypotheses, and their later validation.

In particular, it plays an essential role in group training, first because diffusion models structurally allow the sampling of previous trajectories, and second because we can add constraints to the grouping mechanism to validate them : a modification on one sub-trajectory should be applicable to all trajectories of the group, since they must be semantically similar.

When updating a trajectory s_0 to match a desired final state, what we obtain is a temporary trajectory s_t , which we can condition the model on in order to produce the desired trajectory s_1 (for the same input, reaching the desired final state). In fact, we do not directly alter the model.

We can sample trajectories from the group of s_0 , and see whether s_t is either fully or partially beneficial to the other trajectories in the group.

Defining "beneficial" can be challenging here, since we do not have access to an explicit probability (even if we possibly could extract one from the companion model by analyzing the classification head over an internal vocabulary set). What can be done is to assess whether the modification helps the model become more confident about sub-trajectories either by observing attention maps to see if the distribution sharpens, or by verifying that it does not impact others, or by analyzing gradient changes and magnitudes at each step.

However, there's the case where the distribution would shift and yields better results, which we cannot confirm on a specific sample without relying on an external signal. In such cases, we can see if the final state result of trajectory remain the same, or we can integrate the new trajectory as a hypothetical learning trajectory, a horizontal trajectory from s_0 to s_1 . It's analogous to moving an object one day, going to retrieve it the next, returning to its old location first, and only afterward recalling the new correct place.

We can also register the modification itself, s_t , as a standalone trajectory that can guide future updates, meaning the model can incorporate its own modification without needing to reapply it every time, and can wait for multiple samples before deciding what should be applied. Obviously, the learning of such an s_t trajectory implies modifying the model, but we can do so by following the same FRHI method to better guide the update, and retain it for later gradient updates.

6.5.8 Error learning

Another form of training signal we consider is discretized loss, where the model receives only coarse feedback, such as binary classification ("good" or "bad") or a discrete evaluation scale (e.g., a score from 1 to 5). The objective is not to provide a precise gradient, but to encourage the model to reflect on its own output, identify potential inconsistencies, and re-evaluate its reasoning path toward the correct solution. While this type of signal is inherently less informative than continuous loss, it shifts the focus toward internal coherence and self-assessment. Such a mechanism can be used periodically to replace standard continuous loss functions, serving as a complementary training phase.

6.5.9 Memories and reliability of observations

Effectively retaining truly observed experiences is crucial. We could argue that remembering is just as important as generalization. Observed data carries inherently higher reliability, whereas generalized patterns should be continuously challenged to validate their relevance.

External score Among the strategies we explored is a continuous spiral-shaped embedding space, where a global temporal "tick" gradually shifts embeddings forward. When learning new data, we watermark them with the first tick. When a real trajectory is seen, its embedding is updated toward (by a small continuous step) current temporal tick. This structure supports smooth, time-aware learning and prevents collisions. Embeddings closer to the present tick indicate frequent updates, while infrequently visited memories stay closer to the start.

We also considered the idea of assigning a classification score to trajectories: "seen", "indirectly seen", or "invalid". However, these categories are not mutually exclusive, and even if they were, having the same model update both the trajectory and its associated score would create instability, as any change to the trajectory would in turn affect the classification, without a way to re-ground the score to its prior state.

Another approach is to train an auxiliary lightweight network to approximate the score established by neighborhood exploration. With such a network, the evaluation process can afford to be less stringent, since the primary goal is to approximate an explicit scoring method, one that can be switched to at any time for verification.

Moreover, the ranking algorithm itself can be parallelized, by exploring the model's state backward even during training as the model evolves. For this purpose, a dedicated model can be used to decouple score estimation from trajectory generation, thereby avoiding the instability that arises when the same model is responsible for both updating the trajectory and computing its fitness, since any update in the trajectory would recursively alter the score itself.

However all these approaches has the side effect of merging score. For example when merging trajectories across classes could result in implausible generalizations. For example, while both "tree" and "plane" might individually have high "seen" scores, a generated fusion such as "plane on a tree" should not inherit that level of certainty. This kind of composition could require a reset of associated scores, potentially introducing discontinuities in the representation space.

Memory scoring One strong candidate to address this is external neural memory [42], which can store final trajectory representations along with access frequency. Given that our architecture is explicitly designed to enforce continuity and consistency, memory updates should not lead to unintended forgetting.

Another possible strategy would be to segment memory into patches, allowing the model to learn which representations to store in each region, and how to associate patches to reconstruct memory outputs. Yet, as with internal memory mechanisms, modifying memory content may still indirectly modify the model's behavior, creating a feedback loop.

Alternatively, simpler memory systems such as vector databases [91] could be employed to store trajectory vectors along with their usage frequency. We can also have a background job which explore the database to merge clean it by merging vectors according to the model direction, effectively allowing to constraints the database size. This option requires further investigation but may provide a more stable interface for retrieval-based validation.

The currently preferred solution is the modern neural Hopfield memory, which can store an exponential number of patterns [42]. This memory is not used as direct storage, but rather as a scoring approximation for determining whether or not a trajectory has been previously seen. The idea is not to remember explicitly, but to imprint. By adding it at each layer, we can sum the reconstruction scores, compare the unnormalized attention scores to trajectory groups and their neighbors. Crucially, from any trajectory, we can gradually move toward the most stable pattern, which helps resolve whether a trajectory group is fabricated or aligns with previously memorized trajectories, or at least their remnants.

This can be achieved by freezing the most important dimensions of the representation that the Hopfield network focuses on, and maximizing the reconstruction for the other dimension. Alternatively, we can explore the neighborhood space to follow "natural" solutions that maximize memory retrieval. At the very least, we can use the dominant dimensions retrieved from memory to condition the model and guide exploration through the conceptual graph.

This, in effect, creates a positive feedback loop : inserting a new pattern into memory occurs only after the model determines the best trajectory that minimizes change, a decision itself guided by the memory's implicit scoring over the trajectories. However, further development is required to avoid circular dependencies or simply displacing the problem elsewhere. Hopfield memory es-

entially performs a similar role to hierarchical representation, but we believe they can create a sense of absolute scoring, allowing pattern retrieval scores to be compared directly between two trajectories. As previously stated, though, this is not sufficient to ensure coherence and validity, as neighborhood exploration remains necessary. What Hopfield memory can really offer is a way to prevent the model from cheating when assigning a group to a generated trajectory during the forward pass of the FRHI mechanism. It can also help guide the model toward more stable nodes directly. Still, the combination problem remains : even if we manipulate the attention map to push the trajectory forward in a given direction, we cannot be sure whether the result is an constructed optimal trajectory or a natural/realistic one. Nonetheless, we believe that the combination of the model’s natural implicit distribution with the Hopfield network’s memory dynamics could help address this issue. But more investigation is needed in this area.

Fast adaptation, which may not be possible with the slow diffusion-based training steps, could be compensated by modifying the memory filter (i.e., the linear layer matching patterns to memory). This doesn’t change the model directly but acts more like routing control. Early-phase learning can be done by adding such an overlay over memory, not changing the memory slots, but shaping the retrieval distribution. This enables us to leverage the stability of the base trajectory model while gradually incorporating modifications by switching between filtered and unfiltered memory access.

During training and inference, we can thus predict two solutions: one from the base trajectory model, one from the filtered memory path, and compare them for alignment.

This mechanism can also be applied across different memory time-scales, immediate, short-term, and long-term memory, which can be stacked hierarchically. Each is initialized as the identity, with its own learning rate aligned to its memory scope. Because each layer builds on the memory patterns of the previous one, integration becomes smoother and more gradual from top layer to bottom. Each memory layer encodes between the attractor ”interstices” of the preceding layer. Having such a mechanism, capable of recognizing whether a pattern lies between known ones, can be beneficial for learning policy.

This could also allow the model to handle rare or anomalous pattern detection, where such patterns can be stored in memory for later comparison instead of being overlooked. This aligns with the Titan memory architecture, which introduces a surprise factor to determine how much attention should be allocated to incoming data [48].

Additionally, we can separate memory for real trajectories and hypothetical trajectories, allowing the model to track usage frequency of a hypothesis and progressively promote it to a real trajectory. Instead of using distinct memories, we can allocate memory slots dynamically - e.g., 80% for real data and 20% for hypotheses, adjusting slots group (real/hypothetic) as hypotheses gain confidence and become confirmed.

Moreover, techniques such as SEAL [92], which use LoRA to fine-tune models while preserving prior projections, can be employed to combine stability and rapid learning. Dedicated fine-tuning layers for managing modifications [93], or neuromodulation-inspired mechanisms [94, 95], are also promising strategies.

But again, modifying the scoring function to alter the routing could lead to redundancy because we essentially alter non-invasively the distribution. However, what it could be particularly useful for is fine-tuning without retraining, and enabling its use during inference and across different tasks.

6.6 Training iteration

In our reasoning training strategy, there is a significant bottleneck due to the number of iterations required for the FRHI. However, we can first approximate each iteration with a single step by using a horizontal trajectory to estimate the direction of progression, approximating where we will land, using that to estimate the next step, and so on. The approximation is the same FRHI reasoning process but done in single-step. These single-step approximations can then be used as initializations for full trajectories processing in parallel. And periodically, we can perform full multi-step iterations to refine the process.

This fundamentally means that the model operates hierarchically. We can either perform back-propagation on the single-step sequence as a whole, and then, for each subsequence, based on the input-output updates derived from the single-step sequence, perform backpropagation independently. In this scenario, backpropagation is never applied across the full-length sequence, but instead broken down into independent subsequences, without gradient propagation across them all.

Alternatively, since the objective of the model is to learn how to reach the correct trajectory by learning transitions between trajectories, we can also initialize the same input from multiple different trajectories, either by sampling, randomly by unconditional start, or by running the model from a neighboring context rather than the one strictly induced by the input (which require to run the model one to explore the concept graph). This process can be parallelized, and periodically, few steps trajectory sequences can be followed to ensure continuity.

7 Graph memory usage

Having a multi-scale trajectory also allows the model to learn auto-encoding strategies, since it must be able to reconstruct a trajectory from a particular intermediate state. This means that the exploration of the space becomes more memory-efficient, as we can compress trajectories and still compare them with higher-resolution trajectories that contain finer-grained details.

This enables a form of arborescent thinking, similar to Monte Carlo, where for a given input, multiple concurrent branches can be generated. Exploring some of them benefits the unexplored ones through exploration policy based on the current trajectories context. Insights from explored branches can thus inform how to expand the others more effectively. Which means we could invalidate some trajectories even before expanding them. Or we could explore certain trajectories in just a few steps, examine their neighborhoods to uncover anomalies or overlooked issues in other full-length trajectories, which in turn could lead to terminating some of those active trajectories early.

All this to say : multi-scale processing in this architecture is not just about approximating scores or early termination. It should be able to become a way to explore conceptual contractions, to anticipate certain structures or contradictions before even deepening some concepts/trajectories, and to incorporate knowledge that emerges from multi-scale conceptual graphs. This should allow the model to reason through abstraction, to shortcut redundant exploration, and to refine its decisions using insights already present at higher abstraction levels.

We thus follow a system where the model can “zoom in” on an idea to elaborate details, then “zoom out” to verify coherence with the general structure, propagate updates in the compressed space, then “zoom in” again on another detailed trajectory to apply modifications, and so on.

8 Self-Attention method

Our architecture mostly relies on attention patterns and cross-attention, which are expensive to compute (the longer the input, the higher the computational cost) even though numerous acceleration techniques exist (LoRA, AdaLoRA, QLoRA, DoRA, FlashAttention [96], Sparse attention [97], Linear attention [98], Cached attention [99, 100]).

In our case, the most critical attention occurs between the trajectory model and the companion model, which produces a fixed-size array, thereby limiting the overall cost. But, in the case of multi-scale trajectories we apply cross-attention between steps of different trajectory lengths which can become costly. One solution is to limit the number of steps compared at each time. Or another alternative is the use of gated State Space Models (SSMs) [101], which offer efficient long-range interaction modeling.

In our setup, the most expensive component is where the model must retain context and share global information across the trajectory during reasoning which does not require for us explicit attention and thus SSMs can be used, providing a scalable and memory-efficient solution.

9 Continuous Meta-Learning

Many different meta-learning strategies exist, such as those designed to initialize neural networks for cold starts, minimizing the number of fine-tuning iterations required for new tasks. Some approaches even use the model itself to propose its own updates, like SEAL [102], which leverages a pretrained LLM to output, in natural language, the modifications it needs, apply it to a copy of the LoRA attention, in order to perform better on a new task. This follows the same philosophy as our architecture, where the model learns to adapt itself through internal policies.

The key difference in PathThinker is that we treat everything as the same object : a trajectory. This allows the model to reflect on data, hypotheses, updates, and policy changes. Even the inner working of attention can be modeled as a trajectory, since its modifications inside the model is also modeled as a trajectory. Thus, it should enables the model to represent its own learning process as a trajectory, within a unified and consistent representation : trajectories.

Our architecture could be aligned with the John’s Lambda Calculus, where all elements (numbers, operations, operators) are expressed using a minimal and unified representation, allowing arbitrary combinations like $+ = *$, $2/+$, or $2/0$, etc.

We believe that this could give rise to meta-cognition, where the model can reflect on the way it reasons, evaluate its own biases, and attempt to compensate for them. As with humans, no model will ever be entirely free of bias, but some forms of bias can be made visible and self-corrected.

What is already integrated into our framework is self-generated curriculum learning [103, 104, 105], where the model actively explores the dataset, flags data points, and revisits them later to test hypotheses and apply updates. Although we do not elaborate on it in this paper, we have covered it in depth in our previous work [3].

10 Sequence modeling

The downstream task creates a bottleneck on consistency because it constrains the reasoning to a specific task, potentially with information limitations, like classification, which collapses the reasoning process. One solution is to share the input space with the output space, as in autoregressive models used in LLMs. Since with PathThinker we want to develop an intrinsic language capability emerging from non-linguistic tasks, we aim to tackle scene recognition as sequence prediction without any textual language. The key idea is that the model should be able to predict a graph-based scene description with temporal relationships, without language (see figure 18).

Figure 18: Learning schema of scene description in the trajectory space

Different architectures in self-supervised training have achieved stability, such as BYOL [106], DINO [107, 108], and JEPA [22, 23, 24]. In our setup, we want to use a single model and avoid the standard Exponential Moving Average (EMA), which some methods support [68, 24].

We follow a slightly different approach where we use the temporal axis to enforce self-supervision. The model’s role is, from one frame to the next, to track semantic blocks, meaning, to identify a block in one frame and try to locate the same block in another frame without access to the positions of each block. This should avoid representation collapse (Bian et al., 2022; Jabri et al., 2020) [109, 110]. This can also be done with static images, but temporal data helps the model follow a coherent context across different frames and situations, gradually revealing context shifts, acting as a form of curriculum learning.

We then build a representation graph using trajectories of the model (since trajectories can encode bi-links between nodes in a graph). Thanks to the inherent hierarchical structure of such graphs, we can compress and extend them back to predict the next frame representations, which can be compared with the real ones.

The role of our model is to generate as many hypotheses as possible, which will lead to misalignment with reality in the input images. But this is expected : the goal is to generate hypotheses. What really matters is how the model discriminates between hypotheses to form a plausible world representation, alongside other ”imaginary” world representations.

In other words, the model must learn to group hypotheses into foundational representations, and propose different representations of the world. Then, the downstream task selects the one word representation that aligns most closely with reality. The primary goal always remain consistency, while the downstream task always serves to align the representation with the real world, not to

constrain or reduce it.

Moreover, monitoring the trajectories can reveal frequently used segments. Masking these segments forces the model to discover alternate trajectories, which helps it learn redundant and more robust representations, while reducing reliance on spurious correlations.

This is part of a mechanism that aims to balance correct prediction with novelty discovery. We want the model to make accurate predictions, but we also want to introduce a fatigue mechanism, where being too accurate at predicting the target triggers the discovery of new patterns. For example, the model may try to decouple a concept previously considered a single object, or differentiate between objects previously believed to be similar, akin to Hard Negative Mining [111]. Naturally, this may introduce instability and must be tuned carefully, this requires further investigation.

11 Alternative to diffusion model

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) present a compelling alternative to Diffusion Transformer (DiT) models and warrant future exploration. We identify two promising implementation strategies for RNN integration:

- Hidden states as denoising targets: the hidden states serve as the primary denoising objective, rendering the entire process parallelizable. This approach offers computational advantages similar to those achieved through MAMBA-based parallelization techniques [38], while maintaining the sequential modeling capabilities inherent to RNN architectures.
- Companion model integration: the hidden states of the RNN are used as the outputs of the companion model, with inputs and outputs representing denoised vectors at different timesteps. This configuration enables more direct integration with existing diffusion frameworks while leveraging RNN temporal dynamics.

The primary advantage of RNN architectures lies in their inherently fluid timestep management, which naturally facilitates multi-scale processing, temporal jumps, and structural utilization of hidden states.

These hidden states naturally serve as compact descriptions of performed actions, providing a more intuitive representation of trajectory evolution compared to attention-based mechanisms. This temporal fluidity aligns well with PathThinker’s emphasis on continuous trajectory modeling and adaptive reasoning processes.

However, we prioritize diffusion models here due to their more stable training dynamics and well-established theoretical foundations, while acknowledging that modern RNN variants present compelling alternatives for future exploration.

12 Distributed block processing

An important architectural consideration lies in distributed computation. Until now, we have described a model that processes the entirety of the input and output at each step. While this approach maintains coherence, it is computationally expensive and poorly suited to decentralized systems, particularly in scenarios where a minor modification still requires processing the full input, as is the case with image diffusion models.

One solution involves training the model to generate independent layers containing only a single semantic element (a background, a color, a face, an eye, ...) with an associated transformation

(e.g., rotation, translation). These layers can then be repositioned and added together without relying on the model itself. This means that layer can be composed independently with local updates, while tied to global synchronization, without regenerating unrelated content. However, this does not fully resolve the issue, as the model still expects full-sized inputs (e.g., full-resolution image layers), regardless of how sparse the content is.

Another strategy is to reduce the model’s perceptual and generative window, restricting it to local regions rather than the full canvas. The model is then no longer responsible for producing the entire output but only contributes to individual patch. These blocks can operate in parallel, and a coordination mechanism is introduced to ensure global consistency. Each block must also learn how to position itself and how to interact with other blocks based on shared context.

Synchronization between blocks could be achieved via a shared latent representation. For example a hierarchical generation, where the first block decide roughly objects and positions, then based on these indications we assign each part of the output canvas to a block that recursively do the same. And iterative up and down pass to handle fine-grained details on junction.

Or, we can also condition each model block on the intermediate output results produced globally. While this might initially appear to negate the computational benefits, since it reintroduces full-context dependency, needed full size attention, such conditioning can be sparsified or projected into a lower-dimensional space. Additionally, attention maps can be cached and selectively updated, limiting re-computation to only those regions around the generated bloc exceeding a certain threshold of difference

Finally, we can propose an approach in which each block independently produces both its content and an associated alignment vector. This vector is then matched, via an attention mechanism, to learned spatial slots in the output canvas. This strategy offers a flexible and scalable solution, as it enables dynamic spatial binding of content without requiring hard-coded positioning.

Among the methods discussed, this is the preferred approach, as it naturally extends to neuron-level decentralization, paving the way for fully distributed architectures.

However, this design introduces a non-trivial issue : the double assignment problem, i.e., when two blocks attend to and modify the same region. Several strategies exist to mitigate this [112, 113, 114, 115, 116, 117].

One possible approach involves the use of mobility constraints. Blocks that are better positioned or semantically more relevant to a region receive higher immobility scores, effectively claiming ownership over that area, while others are encouraged to shift their focus elsewhere. This competitive dynamic helps resolve conflicts and promotes specialization. And the process is repeated iteratively to find an equilibrium, allowing a block to find an optimum as the position pressure change the mobility score of all blocks. For example a block that frequently move could also be penalized, forcing it to settle which will increasing the pressure on other blocks too.

In this context, the architecture is no longer static, nor fully defined by the model’s internal weights. Rather, it becomes fluid and emergent. By viewing the model as a computational unit, constructing and synchronizing dynamic attention, we arrive at a form of neural virtualization, akin to how an FPGA or hypervisor dynamically reconfigures logic circuits. The base model thus serves as a neuron within a higher-level virtual network. That’s one of the ideas behind Path-Thinker: to observe itself from the outside, which can possibly be done by constructing a virtual network, or at least a virtual representation of itself, in order to study how it works.

This parallels human metacognitive mechanisms where explicit persona rules (professional codes, values) can modulate implicit behaviors. By adhering to a persona we create explicit rules of how it should behave in specific situations/anchor points, extrapolating implicitly the remaining. Which does not replace the implicit rules, essential for handling unknown, but implicit behaviors

are compared against the persona to better understand it.

13 Neuron-wise architecture

The base idea of the decentralized approach is inspired by the Brain Criticality Hypothesis [118, 119, 120], which suggests that the brain operates optimally when maintained at a critical point, a delicate balance between order and chaos. This maximizes its capacity for information processing, learning, and memory. It implies that signals can propagate through the brain almost instantaneously, effectively bypassing physical connectivity constraints.

Moreover, wave synchronization in the brain plays a crucial role in consolidating memory and facilitating learning [121, 122].

Therefore, we propose a hybrid network supporting both small-world and large-world representations [123, 124], where neurons are grouped by operating on the same carrier wave. In our setup, a neuron is in fact a small neural network, compensating for the relatively weak computational power of artificial neurons compared to biological ones [125]. Which may be necessary to reach a critical equilibrium between decentralization and local effectiveness.

In this configuration, multiple groups can communicate by aligning with each other’s carrier waves. Each group maintains its own wave, and a neuron receiving a signal attempts to decode it based on its own carrier wave. If the signal is irrelevant, it transmits it unchanged. This enables a model where physical neuron connections are no longer constraints for training, but instead represent communication costs, mirroring the physical reality of GPU clusters during distributed training and aligning with hardware-aware networks [126].

Figure 19: Conceptual schema of a decentralized network

The network can also benefit from a shared channel where all neurons can exchange information through a common carrier wave. This channel can be used both to propagate inputs and construct outputs. In this architecture, there is no explicit input or output layer, nor a strict bottom-up information flow, only a computational mass trying to converge toward a specific state. Some

approach have already proven that bottom-up hierarchical architecture is not the only learning paradigm possible [127].

Each neuron, in this configuration, attempts to communicate with others by aligning to their carrier wave. In other words, given an input signal, it seeks a wave pattern it can decode or that seems non-random. This design abstracts away the architectural layer, whether discrete or continuous, spiking or non-spiking.

This setup is particularly suited to PathThinker, whose goal is to find trajectories. Here, the output state of all neurons can be considered the final result of the diffusion process. This avoids issues such as gradient explosion since neurons are not explicitly connected. Each neuron (which is itself a small neural network) learns a transformation to reach its desired output.

Each neuron maintains its own activation history corresponding to diffusion timesteps and locally attempts to perform diffusion process, like in PathThinker. Grouping then becomes a decentralized synchronization mechanism. Since each neuron’s trajectory contributes to a global representation, especially via the output channel, we can use this same representation to condition individual neurons and locally learning to associate this trajectory to the conditioned context (the final representation). More precisely, each neuron tries to find a common representation such that, when conditioned on it, they each produce their expected (but distinct) trajectory. This process is progressively refined to reach full synchronization. Each neuron thus takes a vector as input and outputs a vector.

Regarding input/output, we aim to avoid having a centralized input/output layer that aggregates all neuron states. While effective, such designs impose strong synchronization constraints, as seen in Continuous Thought Machines [128], where MLP-based neurons synchronize through covariance of their scalar activation histories, and using a shared network for input/output distribution to the MLP-neuron that also don’t have links between them.

In our approach, each neuron has its own companion model focused only on a portion of the input or output. This raises the challenge of decentralizing input distribution and output collection. The latter (output) was previously discussed in this paper in the context of the double assignment problem. For the former (input), we face a similar challenge and will likely need local conflict resolution, presenting neurons with their best adaptation options and iterating toward a consensus. Due to its parallelizable nature, SSM could be a viable solution for synchronization representation, provided we implement a causality mechanism among neurons, such as temporally shifting information propagation.

And one major advantage of this architecture is the ability to define a virtual network topology, allowing us to simulate information flow over any topological space (e.g., a torus), where each neuron has a position and accesses information according to the geometry. We can even associate a virtual time to each position, determining how long it takes for information to propagate, a behavior implementable through weighted links between neurons (representing cost) or between position on the topological shape, which helps emulate temporal dynamics of Spiking Neural Networks or implement strategies like Winner-Take-All for assignment resolution.

Figure 20: Conceptual schema of a virtual network topology

Another update mechanism is forward-passing : once an output is generated, the model compares it to the desired input and reconditions itself on the difference, allowing gradual updates through reinforcement learning. This aligns with PathThinker’s goal and spontaneous activity [129], where the model learns to reach any target state, even if it concerns only a specific layer or sequence of layers.

14 Challenges

We acknowledge the significant implementation challenges associated with this framework, including stabilization, convergence, and achieving the delicate equilibrium required among policy objectives while managing hyperparameters. However, some solutions exist to tackle these problems [130, 131].

The establishment of robust stability and continuity measures remains crucial for fully realizing our objectives. Additionally, the computational overhead during the initial training phases may be important, though we anticipate these costs will be offset by long-term benefits, particularly given the possible optimizations presented herein.

While this architecture presents compelling conceptual advantages, the operational overhead required for implementation may not necessarily compensate for performance gains. Thus, empirical validation through rigorous testing and data collection is essential to substantiate our hypotheses.

A critical consideration is the model’s capacity to integrate all trajectory representations while maintaining resilience against the distribution shifts inherent in such a comprehensive approach. We believe that ensuring trajectory continuity and implementing validation mechanisms prior to update deployment can effectively mitigate these challenges.

15 Possible limitations

We identify several key limitations that warrant careful consideration :

First, the framework lacks direct probability estimation mechanisms and robust methods for tracking trajectory utilization frequency, making it difficult to determine whether a trajectory

has been genuinely encountered before. This limitation poses challenges for proper trajectory validation and reuse strategies. However, the proposed mechanisms to counterbalance this point could be sufficient to mitigate the issue.

Second, while horizontal trajectories represent a conceptually relevant approach, they may not adequately fulfill our intended objectives in practice. Their performance will heavily rely on appropriate formulation to fully capture their purpose. We introduce the concept of horizontal trajectories here with a minimal implementation prototype, but further investigation is required.

Finally, the decentralized approach, where neuron groups produce outputs that are then matched via attention, also requires careful design to avoid creating bottlenecks that could slow convergence, cause oscillations during training, or necessitate extensive use of backpropagation.

16 Conclusion

In this work, we introduced PathThinker, an architecture that reframes reasoning as a process of evolving trajectories within a conceptual space, rather than a mere sequence of predictions or static associations. Our core hypothesis is that intelligence does not lie in passive representation, but in the ability to construct, explore, test, and refine trajectories.

This approach raises many challenges in terms of stability, efficiency, and empirical validation, but it opens a path toward truly self-adaptive and exploratory systems within a coherent and comprehensive vision that aims to unify various AI methodologies, offering a framework that appears feasible.

References

- [1] W. Lotter, G. Kreiman, and D. Cox, “Deep predictive coding networks for video prediction and unsupervised learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1605.08104>
- [2] B. Millidge, T. Salvatori, Y. Song, R. Bogacz, and T. Lukasiewicz, “Predictive coding: Towards a future of deep learning beyond backpropagation?” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.09467>
- [3] B. Weber, “Reasoning beyond words ? exploring framework for hidden state reasoning,” *Zenodo*, 02 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14811456>
- [4] V. Mazzia, F. Salvetti, and M. Chiaberge, “Efficient-capsnet: Capsule network with self-attention routing,” *arXiv*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.12491>
- [5] S. Sabour, N. Frosst, and G. E. Hinton, “Dynamic routing between capsules,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1710.09829>
- [6] J. Gu, V. Tresp, and H. Han, “Capsule network is not more robust than convolutional network,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.15459>
- [7] U. F. Program, “Homotopy type theory: Univalent foundations of mathematics,” *arXiv*, p. 0, 09 2013.
- [8] X. D. Arsiwalla and J. Gorard, “Pregeometric spaces from wolfram model rewriting systems as homotopy types,” 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.03460>
- [9] S. Wolfram. (2020, 04) Finally we may have a path to the fundamental theory of physics...and it's beautiful. [Online]. Available: <https://writings.stephenwolfram.com/2020/04/finally-we-may-have-a-path-to-the-fundamental-theory-of-physics-and-its-beautiful/>
- [10] —. (2023, 10) How to think computationally about ai, the universe and everything. [Online]. Available: <https://writings.stephenwolfram.com/2023/10/how-to-think-computationally-about-ai-the-universe-and-everything/>
- [11] H. Wu, O. Isac, A. Zeljić, T. Tagomori, M. L. Daggitt, W. Kokke, I. Refaeli, G. Amir, K. D. Julian, S. Bassan, H. Pei, O. Lahav, M. Wu, M. Zhang, E. Komendantskaya, G. Katz, and C. Barrett, “Artifact for marabou 2.0: A versatile formal analyzer of neural networks,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 04 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2401.14461>
- [12] S. Bak, “nenum: Verification of relu neural networks with optimized abstraction refinement,” *Lecture notes in computer science*, pp. 19–36, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76384-8_2
- [13] A. O’Quinn and M. Taylor, “Automated synthesis of verified neural network controllers from linear temporal logic specifications,” pp. 26–34, 10 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3733823.3764517>
- [14] J. Yao, G. Ryan, J. Wong, S. Jana, and R. Gu, “Learning nonlinear loop invariants with gated continuous logic networks (extended version),” *arXiv*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.07959>

- [15] A. Zweiger, J. Pari, H. Guo, E. Akyürek, Y. Kim, and P. Agrawal, “Self-adapting language models,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 06 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2506.10943>
- [16] Z. Li, F. Zhou, F. Chen, and H. Li, “Meta-sgd: Learning to learn quickly for few-shot learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 07 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.09835>
- [17] A. Nichol, J. Achiam, and J. Schulman, “On first-order meta-learning algorithms,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 03 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1803.02999>
- [18] L. Zintgraf, K. Shiarlis, V. Kurin, K. Hofmann, and S. Whiteson, “Fast context adaptation via meta-learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 10 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.03642>
- [19] C. Finn, P. Abbeel, and S. Levine, “Model-agnostic meta-learning for fast adaptation of deep networks,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 03 2017. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1703.03400>
- [20] X. Cao, J. Jia, and N. Z. Gong, “Ipguard: Protecting intellectual property of deep neural networks via fingerprinting the classification boundary,” pp. 14–25, 05 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3433210.3437526>
- [21] Y. Ren, J. Pu, Z. Yang, J. Xu, G. Li, X. Pu, P. S. Yu, and L. He, “Deep clustering: A comprehensive survey,” 01 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.04142>
- [22] Q. Garrido, M. Assran, N. Ballas, A. Bardes, L. Najman, and Y. LeCun, “Learning and leveraging world models in visual representation learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 03 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.00504>
- [23] A. Bardes, J. Ponce, and Y. LeCun, “Mc-jepa: A joint-embedding predictive architecture for self-supervised learning of motion and content features,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.12698>
- [24] M. Assran, Q. Duval, I. Misra, P. Bojanowski, P. Vincent, M. Rabbat, Y. LeCun, and N. Ballas, “Self-supervised learning from images with a joint-embedding predictive architecture,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.08243>
- [25] Z. Wang, Z. Zhang, N. V. Chawla, C. Zhang, and Y. Ye, “Gft: Graph foundation model with transferable tree vocabulary,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 11 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2411.06070>
- [26] Z. Z. Ren, Z. Shao, J. Song, H. Xin, H. Wang, W. Zhao, L. Zhang, Z. Fu, Q. Zhu, D. Yang, Z. Wu, Z. Gou, S. Ma, H. Tang, Y. Liu, W. Gao, D. Guo, and C. Ruan, “Deepseek-prover-v2: Advancing formal mathematical reasoning via reinforcement learning for subgoal decomposition,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 04 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2504.21801>
- [27] C. Vignac, I. Krawczuk, A. Siraudin, B. Wang, V. Cevher, and P. Frossard, “Digress: Discrete denoising diffusion for graph generation,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 09 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2209.14734>
- [28] A. Jolicoeur-Martineau, “Less is more: Recursive reasoning with tiny networks,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 10 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2510.04871>

- [29] W. Guan, J. Li, Y. Sun, C. Xing, L. Changling, W. Yue, L. Meng, S. Sen, and Y. A. Yadkori, “Hierarchical reasoning model,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 06 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2506.21734>
- [30] W. Grathwohl, R. T. Q. Chen, J. Bettencourt, I. Sutskever, and D. Duvenaud, “Ffjord: Free-form continuous dynamics for scalable reversible generative models,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 10 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.01367>
- [31] Z. Z. Ren, Z. Shao, J. Song, H. Xin, H. Wang, W. Zhao, L. Zhang, Z. Fu, Q. Zhu, D. Yang, Z. F. Wu, Z. Gou, S. Ma, H. Tang, Y. Liu, W. Gao, D. Guo, and C. Ruan, “Deepseek-prover-v2: Advancing formal mathematical reasoning via reinforcement learning for subgoal decomposition,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.21801>
- [32] H. Zenil, N. A. Kiani, A. Adams *et al.*, “Minimal algorithmic information loss methods for dimension reduction, feature selection and network sparsification,” *Information Sciences*, vol. 720, p. 122520, 12 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2025.122520>
- [33] Z. Tu, S. J. Choure, M. H. Fong *et al.*, “Askcos: an open source software suite for synthesis planning,” 2025.
- [34] A. Sarti, G. Citti, and J. Petitot, “The symplectic structure of the primary visual cortex,” *Biological Cybernetics*, vol. 98, no. 1, pp. 33–48, 11 2007. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00422-007-0194-9>
- [35] D. McNeela, F. Sala, and A. Gitter, “Product manifold representations for learning on biological pathways,” 2024.
- [36] L. Ruiz, L. F. O. Chamon, and A. Ribeiro, “Graphon neural networks and the transferability of graph neural networks,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.03548>
- [37] P. Kaushik, S. Chaudhari, A. Vaidya *et al.*, “The universal weight subspace hypothesis,” 2025.
- [38] A. Orvieto, S. Smith, A. Gu, A. Fernando, Çağlar Gülçehre, R. Pascanu, and S. De, “Resurrecting recurrent neural networks for long sequences,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.06349>
- [39] K. Schürholt, M. W. Mahoney, and D. Borth, “Towards scalable and versatile weight space learning,” 01 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.09997>
- [40] S. Powers, E. Xing, and A. Gupta, “Self-activating neural ensembles for continual reinforcement learning,” 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.00141>
- [41] D. Liao, C. Liu, X. Sun, D. Tang, H. Wang, S. Youlten, S. K. Gopinath, H. Lee, E. C. Strayer, A. J. Giraldez, and S. Krishnaswamy, “Rnagenscape: Property-guided optimization and interpolation of mrna sequences with manifold langevin dynamics,” 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.24736>
- [42] H. Ramsauer, B. Schöfl, J. M. Lehner, P. Seidl, M. Widrich, T. Adler, L. Gruber, M. Holzleitner, M. Pavlović, G. K. Sandve, V. Greiff, D. P. Kreil, M. Kopp, G. Klambauer, J. Brandstetter, and S. Hochreiter, “Hopfield networks is all you need,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2008.02217>
- [43] T. Xie, C. Geniesse, J. Chen, Y. Yang, D. Morozov, M. W. Mahoney, R. Maciejewski, and G. H. Weber, “Evaluating loss landscapes from a topology perspective,” 2024.

- [44] X. Wang, Z. Fang, J. Wu, S.-Q. Xin, and Y. He, “Discrete geodesic graph (DGG) for computing geodesic distances on polyhedral surfaces,” *Comput. Aided Geom. Des.*, vol. 52-53, pp. 262–284, Mar. 2017.
- [45] F. Acosta, S. Sanborn, K. D. Duc, M. Madhav, and N. Miolane, “Quantifying extrinsic curvature in neural manifolds,” 2022.
- [46] S. Viswanath, H. Madhu, D. Bhaskar, J. Kovalic, D. R. Johnson, C. Tape, I. Adelstein, R. Ying, M. Perlmutter, and S. Krishnaswamy, “HiPoNet: A multi-view simplicial complex network for high dimensional point-cloud and single-cell data,” Feb. 2025.
- [47] J. Lee-Thorp, J. Ainslie, I. Eckstein, and S. Ontanon, “FNet: Mixing tokens with fourier transforms,” May 2021.
- [48] A. Behrouz, P. Zhong, and V. Mirrokni, “Titans: Learning to memorize at test time,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 12 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2501.00663>
- [49] H. Le, K. Do, D. Nguyen, and S. Venkatesh, “Beyond surprise: Improving exploration through surprise novelty,” Aug. 2023.
- [50] J. Ji, K. Wang, T. Qiu, B. Chen, J. Zhou, C. Li, H. Lou, J. Dai, Y. Liu, and Y. Yang, “Language models resist alignment: Evidence from data compression,” Sep. 2025.
- [51] DeepSeek-AI, “Deepseek-v2: A strong, economical, and efficient mixture-of-experts language model,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 05 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.04434>
- [52] J. Yoon, H. Cho, D. Baek, Y. Bengio, and S. Ahn, “Monte carlo tree diffusion for system 2 planning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2502.07202>
- [53] J. Harrison, A. Sharma, C. Finn, and M. Pavone, “Continuous meta-learning without tasks,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1912.08866>
- [54] K. Irie, R. Csordás, and J. Schmidhuber, “Automating continual learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.00276>
- [55] A. Jaegle, F. Gimeno, A. Brock, A. Zisserman, O. Vinyals, and J. Carreira, “Perceiver: General perception with iterative attention,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.03206>
- [56] L. Zhang and M. Agrawala, “Adding conditional control to text-to-image diffusion models,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.05543>
- [57] L. Hua, F. Liu, J. Su, X. Miao, Z. Ouyang, Z. Wang, R. Hu, Z. Wen, B. Zhai, Y. Long, H. Duan, and Y. Zhou, “Attention in diffusion model: A survey,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.03738>
- [58] D. Lukovnikov and A. Fischer, “Layout-to-image generation with localized descriptions using controlnet with cross-attention control,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.13404>
- [59] T. Team, L. Barrault, P.-A. Duquenne, M. Elbayad, A. Kozhevnikov, B. Alastruey, P. Andrews, M. Coria, G. Couairon, M. R. Costa-jussà, D. C. Dale, H. Elsahar, K. S. Heffernan, J. M. Janeiro, T. Tran, C. Ropers, E. Sánchez, R. S. Roman, A. Mourachko, S. Saleem, and H. Schwenk, “Large concept models: Language modeling in

- a sentence representation space,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 12 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2412.08821>
- [60] (2024, 01) Neurite. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/satellitecomponent/Neurite>
- [61] C. Chen, K. Liu, Z. Chen, Y. Gu, Y. Wu, M. Tao, Z. Fu, and J. Ye, “Inside: Llms’ internal states retain the power of hallucination detection,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2402.03744>
- [62] W. Su, C. Wang, Q. Ai, Y. HU, Z. Wu, Y. Zhou, and Y. Liu, “Unsupervised real-time hallucination detection based on the internal states of large language models,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 03 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2403.06448>
- [63] Z. Ji, D. Chen, E. Ishii, S. Cahyawijaya, Y. Bang, B. Wilie, and P. Fung, “Llm internal states reveal hallucination risk faced with a query,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 07 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.03282>
- [64] J. Binkowski, D. Janiak, A. Sawczyn, B. Gabrys, and T. Kajdanowicz, “Hallucination detection in llms using spectral features of attention maps,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.17598>
- [65] J. Kossen, J. Han, M. Razzak, L. Schut, S. A. Malik, and Y. Gal, “Semantic entropy probes: Robust and cheap hallucination detection in llms,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 06 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2406.15927>
- [66] S. Farquhar, J. Kossen, L. Kuhn, and Y. Gal, “Detecting hallucinations in large language models using semantic entropy,” *Nature*, vol. 630, pp. 625–630, 06 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07421-0>
- [67] G. Dudek and T. Rodak, “Hkan: Hierarchical kolmogorov-arnold network without backpropagation,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2501.18199>
- [68] A. Bardes, J. Ponce, and Y. LeCun, “Vicreg: Variance-invariance-covariance regularization for self-supervised learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.04906>
- [69] Z. Pan, B. Zhuang, D.-A. Huang, W. Nie, Z. Yu, C. Xiao, J. Cai, and A. Anandkumar, “T-stitch: Accelerating sampling in pre-trained diffusion models with trajectory stitching,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2402.14167>
- [70] Y. Luo, T. Hu, J. Sun, Y. Cai, and J. Tang, “Learning few-step diffusion models by trajectory distribution matching,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.06674>
- [71] J. Wang, H. Wang, H. Wen, G. Min, and M. Luo, “Trajweaver: Trajectory recovery with state propagation diffusion model,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 09 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2409.02124>
- [72] Y. Song, P. Dhariwal, M. Chen, and I. Sutskever, “Consistency models,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.01469>
- [73] G. Li, Y. Shan, Z. Zhu, T. Long, and W. Zhang, “Diffstitch: Boosting offline reinforcement learning with diffusion-based trajectory stitching,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2402.02439>

- [74] J. Yoon, H. Cho, Y. Bengio, and S. Ahn, “Fast monte carlo tree diffusion: 100x speedup via parallel sparse planning,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.09498>
- [75] J. Chung, S. Ahn, and Y. Bengio, “Hierarchical multiscale recurrent neural networks,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1609.01704>
- [76] D. Chen, Y. Bai, W. Zhao, S. Ament, J. M. Gregoire, and C. P. Gomes, “Deep reasoning networks: Thinking fast and slow,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1906.00855>
- [77] J. Li, X. Wang, and Z. Zeng, “A dual-stream recurrence-attention network with global-local awareness for emotion recognition in textual dialog,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.00449>
- [78] Z. Zhang, H. Zhang, L. Zhao, T. Chen, S. O. Arık, and T. Pfister, “Nested hierarchical transformer: Towards accurate, data-efficient and interpretable visual understanding,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.12723>
- [79] X. Zhu, W. Su, L. Lu, B. Li, X. Wang, and J. Dai, “Deformable detr: Deformable transformers for end-to-end object detection,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.04159>
- [80] X. Wang, J. Yang, and T. Darrell, “Segment anything without supervision,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 06 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.20081>
- [81] E. Gumaan, “Universal approximation theorem for a single-layer transformer,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.10581>
- [82] M. Dehghani, S. Gouws, O. Vinyals, J. Uszkoreit, and Łukasz Kaiser, “Universal transformers,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.03819>
- [83] M. Elbayad, J. Gu, Édouard Grave, and M. Auli, “Depth-adaptive transformer,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.10073>
- [84] P. Tang, P. Zhu, L. Tian, S. Appalaraju, V. Mahadevan, and R. Manmatha, “Deed: Dynamic early exit on decoder for accelerating encoder-decoder transformer models,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.08623>
- [85] J. Xin, R. Tang, J. Lee, Y. Yu, and J. Lin, “Deebert: Dynamic early exiting for accelerating bert inference,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2004.12993>
- [86] Q. Liu, W. Zhao, W. Huang, Y. Fang, L. Yu, and G. Li, “From layers to states: A state space model perspective to deep neural network layer dynamics,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2502.10463>
- [87] E. Cetin, T. Zhao, and Y. Tang, “Reinforcement learning teachers of test time scaling,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.08388>
- [88] Y.-S. Chuang, L. Qiu, C.-Y. Hsieh, R. Krishna, Y. Kim, and J. Glass, “Lookback lens: Detecting and mitigating contextual hallucinations in large language models using only attention maps,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 07 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2407.07071>

- [89] L. Wang, C. Du, P. Zhao, C. Luo, Z. Zhu, B. Qiao, W. Zhang, Q. Lin, S. Rajmohan, D. Zhang, and Q. Zhang, “Contrastive learning with negative sampling correction,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.08690>
- [90] T. Huynh, S. Kornblith, M. R. Walter, M. Maire, and M. Khademi, “Boosting contrastive self-supervised learning with false negative cancellation,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.11765>
- [91] (2019, 01) Faiss. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/facebookresearch/faiss>
- [92] A. Zweiger, J. Pari, H. Guo, E. Akyürek, Y. Kim, and P. Agrawal, “Self-adapting language models,” 06 2025.
- [93] N. Houlsby, A. Giurgiu, S. Jastrzebski, B. Morrone, Q. de Laroussilhe, A. Gesmundo, M. Attariyan, and S. Gelly, “Parameter-efficient transfer learning for nlp,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.00751>
- [94] E. Ben-Iwhiwhu, J. Dick, N. A. Ketz, P. K. Pilly, and A. Soltoggio, “Context meta-reinforcement learning via neuromodulation,” *arXiv*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.00134>
- [95] O. Ayoub, D. Andreoletti, A. Knapińska, R. Goścień, P. Lechowicz, T. Leidi, S. Giordano, C. Rottondi, and K. Walkowiak, “Liquid neural network-based adaptive learning vs. incremental learning for link load prediction amid concept drift due to network failures,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 04 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.05304>
- [96] T. Dao, D. Y. Fu, S. Ermon, A. Rudra, and C. Ré, “Flashattention: Fast and memory-efficient exact attention with io-awareness,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.14135>
- [97] C. Lou, Z. Jia, Z. Zheng, and K. Tu, “Sparsifier is faster and less is more: Efficient sparse attention for long-range transformers,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 06 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.16747>
- [98] K. Ahn, X. Cheng, M. Song, C. Yun, A. Jadbabaie, and S. Sra, “Linear attention is (maybe) all you need (to understand transformer optimization),” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.01082>
- [99] B. Gao, Z. He, P. Sharma, Q. Kang, D. Jevdjic, J. Deng, X. Yang, Z. Yu, and P. Zuo, “Attentionstore: Cost-effective attention reuse across multi-turn conversations in large language model serving,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 03 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.19708>
- [100] L. Ye, Z. Tao, Y. Huang, and Y. Li, “Chunkattention: Efficient self-attention with prefix-aware kv cache and two-phase partition,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2402.15220>
- [101] A. Gu, K. Goel, and C. Ré, “Efficiently modeling long sequences with structured state spaces,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.00396>
- [102] A. Zweiger, J. Pari, H. Guo, E. Akyürek, Y. Kim, and P. Agrawal, “Self-adapting language models,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.10943>
- [103] E. Zelikman, Y. Wu, and N. D. Goodman, “Star: Bootstrapping reasoning with reasoning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.14465>

- [104] T. Shi, Y. Wu, L. Song, T. Zhou, and J. Zhao, “Efficient reinforcement finetuning via adaptive curriculum learning,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.05520>
- [105] Q. Yu, K. Wu, Z. Chen, C. Zhang, M. Mei, L. Huang, F. Tan, Y. Du, K. Liu, and Y. Zhu, “Rethinking the generation of high-quality cot data from the perspective of llm-adaptive question difficulty grading,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.11919>
- [106] J.-B. Grill, F. Strub, F. Altché, C. Tallec, P. H. Richemond, E. Buchatskaya, C. Doersch, B. Ávila Pires, Z. D. Guo, M. G. Azar, B. Piot, K. Kavukcuoglu, R. Munos, and M. Valko, “Bootstrap your own latent: A new approach to self-supervised learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.07733>
- [107] M. Oquab, T. Darcet, T. Moutakanni, H. Vo, M. Szafraniec, V. Khalidov, P. Fernandez, D. Haziza, F. Massa, A. El-Nouby, M. Assran, N. Ballas, W. Galuba, R. Howes, P.-Y. Huang, S.-W. Li, I. Misra, M. Rabbat, V. Sharma, G. Synnaeve, H. Xu, H. Jégou, J. Mairal, P. Labatut, A. Joulin, and P. Bojanowski, “Dinov2: Learning robust visual features without supervision,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07193>
- [108] M. Caron, H. Touvron, I. Misra, H. Jégou, J. Mairal, P. Bojanowski, and A. Joulin, “Emerging properties in self-supervised vision transformers,” 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.14294>
- [109] Z. Bian, A. Jabri, A. A. Efros, and A. Owens, “Learning pixel trajectories with multiscale contrastive random walks,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.08379>
- [110] A. Jabri, A. Owens, and A. A. Efros, “Space-time correspondence as a contrastive random walk,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.14613>
- [111] J. A. Robinson, C.-Y. Chuang, S. Sra, and S. Jegelka, “Contrastive learning with hard negative samples,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.04592>
- [112] E. Pesce and G. Montana, “Learning multi-agent coordination through connectivity-driven communication,” *Machine Learning*, vol. 112, pp. 483–514, 12 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-022-06286-6>
- [113] L. Ratnabala, A. Fedoseev, R. Peter, and D. Tsetserukou, “Magnnet: Multi-agent graph neural network-based efficient task allocation for autonomous vehicles with deep reinforcement learning,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 02 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2502.02311>
- [114] A. Goeckner, Y. Sui, N. Martinet, X. D. Li, and Q. Zhu, “Graph neural network-based multi-agent reinforcement learning for resilient distributed coordination of multi-robot systems,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 03 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2403.13093>
- [115] H. Li, S. Zhang, D. Ma, and W. Mo, “An attention mechanism network based on the winner-take-all,” *Digital Signal Processing*, vol. 154, pp. 104 660–104 660, 07 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsp.2024.104660>
- [116] R. Tripathi, V. Singla, M. Najibi, B. Singh, A. Sharma, and L. T. Davis, “Asap-nms: Accelerating non-maximum suppression using spatially aware priors,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.09785>

- [117] J. Hosang, R. Benenson, and B. Schiele, “Learning non-maximum suppression,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1705.02950>
- [118] Y. Tian, Z. Tan, H. Hou, G. Li, A. Cheng, Y. Qiu, K. Weng, C. Chen, and P. Sun, “Theoretical foundations of studying criticality in the brain,” *Network Neuroscience*, vol. 6, pp. 1148–1185, 01 2022. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1162/netn.a_00269
- [119] J. M. Beggs, “Addressing skepticism of the critical brain hypothesis,” *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*, vol. 16, 09 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2022.703865>
- [120] J. M. Beggs and D. Plenz, “Neuronal avalanches in neocortical circuits,” *Journal of Neuroscience*, vol. 23, pp. 11 167–11 177, 12 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1523/jneurosci.23-35-11167.2003>
- [121] G. Xu, T. Mihaylova, D. Li, F. Tian, P. Farrehi, J. M. Parent, G. A. Mashour, M. M. Wang, and J. Borjigin, “Surge of neurophysiological coupling and connectivity of gamma oscillations in the dying human brain,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 120, 05 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2216268120>
- [122] E. G. Antzoulatos and E. K. Miller, “Increases in functional connectivity between prefrontal cortex and striatum during category learning,” *Neuron*, vol. 83, pp. 216–225, 06 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2014.05.005>
- [123] L. Q. Uddin, R. F. Betzel, J. R. Cohen, J. S. Damoiseaux, F. D. Brigard, S. B. Eickhoff, A. Fornito, C. Gratton, E. M. Gordon, A. R. Laird, L. J. Larson-Prior, A. R. McIntosh, L. D. Nickerson, L. Pessoa, A. L. Pinho, R. A. Poldrack, A. Razi, S. Sadaghiani, J. M. Shine, A. Yendiki, B. T. Yeo, and R. N. Spreng, “Controversies and progress on standardization of large-scale brain network nomenclature,” *Network Neuroscience*, vol. 7, pp. 864–905, 01 2023. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1162/netn.a_00323
- [124] P. N. Taylor, Y. Wang, and M. Kaiser, “Within brain area tractography suggests local modularity using high resolution connectomics,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 7, 01 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep39859>
- [125] D. Beniaguev, I. Segev, and M. London, “Single cortical neurons as deep artificial neural networks,” *Neuron*, vol. 109, p. 2727, 08 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2021.07.002>
- [126] H. Benmezziane, K. E. Maghraoui, H. Ouarnoughi, S. Niar, M. Wistuba, and N. Wang, “A comprehensive survey on hardware-aware neural architecture search,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.09336>
- [127] Q. Li, Y. W. Teh, and R. Pascanu, “Noprop: Training neural networks without back-propagation or forward-propagation,” 01 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.24322>
- [128] L. Darlow, C. Regan, S. Risi, J. Seely, and L. Jones, “Continuous thought machines,” 05 2025.
- [129] E. Plantec, J. W. Pedersen, M. L. Montero, E. Nisioti, and S. Risi, “Evolving self-assembling neural networks: From spontaneous activity to experience-dependent learning,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.09787>

- [130] J. Albrechts, H. Martin, and M. Tavakol, “Model-based meta-reinforcement learning for hyperparameter optimization,” *Lecture notes in computer science*, pp. 27–39, 11 2024. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77731-8_3
- [131] Y. Chen, X. Song, C. Lee, Z. Wang, Q. Zhang, D. Dohan, K. Kawakami, G. Kochanski, A. Doucet, M. Ranzato, S. Perel, and N. de Freitas, “Towards learning universal hyperparameter optimizers with transformers,” *arXiv (Cornell University)*, 01 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.13320>